

VALKYRIES

D5.5 Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

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Main Contributor: TASSICA

**Other Contributors: IND, SERMAS, ISEMI, PART, UMU, SSA,
NOV, BDI, KEM, HESE, ARA, USN, AREU, HRT**

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
M. Carmen Martín Curto	carmen.martin@tassica.com	TASSICA
Alberto Montarelo Navajo	alberto.montarelo@tassica.com	TASSICA
David Bravo Montarelo	david.bravo@tassica.com	TASSICA
Carlos I. Sierra Berrocal	carlos.sierra@tassica.com	TASSICA

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Beata Korpesio	ISEMI	D5.1 Section 3 State of the art, Landscape, Perception of needs
Rafael E. Caballero Cubedo	SUMMA 112/SERMAS	D5.1 S.5 Alerts and Warning. State of the art. Document Review
Enrique Claudio Romo	SUMMA 112/SERMAS	D5.1 S.5 Alerts and Warning. Standardization and certification. Document Review
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	D5.1 S1 State of the art – Crisis response planning (9.2.2)
Pedro Ramón y Cajal Ramo	Indra	Contribution and review of chapter 5.4
Guillem Puntí Sadurní	Indra	Contribution and review of chapter 5.3
José Cabezas Rodríguez	NOVOTEC	D5.1 Section 1, 2 and 3: Standards and Methodology, update and review
Ignacio Hernández Palencia	NOVOTEC	Methodology, update and review
Angel Giménez Celdrán	NOVOTEC	Document Review
Ioannis Chatzichristos	ARATOS	D5.1 S3 C2 Procedures D5.1 S4 Maintenance Logistics and Deployment Procedures D5.1 S4 COP procedures D5.1 S5 Alarms and Warnings Link with the findings of T5.3 Procedures and Risk Assessment of SIGRUN Operational Centre
Dimitrios Iliadis Iosif Vourvachis	HRT	Contribution to the use cases and the framework of Greece for the emergency Response. General review
Ioannis Dontas	ARATOS	Classification and characterization of findings and mapping of operational procedures with overall system design first draft
Marco Manso	PARTICLE	Contribution to C2 and COP
Pedro Miguel	PARTICLE	Contribution to C2 and COP
Barbara Manso	PARTICLE	Review on COP
Fernando Freire	PARTICLE	Review on C2

Name	Entity	Contribution
John Tsaloukidis	KEM	Review of chapters 20 "Command and Control and support to operational decision-making" and 31 "Common operational picture"
M. Kozarski	BDI	C2 intro
A. Kolev	BDI	C2 intro
R. Iliev	BDI	C2 intro
Manuel Ocaña	INDRA	Quality revision
Antonio Calero	INDRA	Edition of chapter 4.1
Mirko Pugliara	AREU	D5.1 State of the art, Landscape, Perception of needs, Review
Denise Amram	SSSA	Document Review and §6

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1. Executive Summary

This document D5.5 provides a Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters in the EU related to:

- Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- Maintenance, logistics and Deployment
- Command and Control and support to operational decision-making
- Common Operational Picture
- Alert and warning

Each of these sections is structured as follows:

- Introduction
- State of the Art
- Landscape
- Perception of needs

Finally, a reflection on the legal barriers and ethical concerns in developing a homogeneous landscape of new operational and procedural capabilities for first responders is included, and the main conclusions drawn from the work are summarised at the end of the document.

The annexes to this deliverable contain the list of bibliographical sources, the list of acronyms used in the drafting of the text and the questionnaire sent to the experts consulted.

The identification and thorough review of documentation, as well as consultation and discussion among experts close to the project is the basis on which this document is prepared.

This deliverable D5.5 is the final version of draft D5.1. To make it easier to identify the changes made in this final version compared to the previous one, they have been highlighted in yellow.

Listed below, in order of appearance in deliverable D5.5, are the main changes in this document compared to draft version D5.1. Links to the corresponding text are available under the same heading. Spelling or grammatical corrections, as well as minor variations in relation to some very specific terms or content, are not included in this list of changes.

1 Executive Summary (Addition of information about the final version of the document.)

2 Identification (No major changes)

3 Project Overview (List of the objectives modified).

4 Introduction

4.1 Objective (New section)

4.3 Methodology (New section)

4.4 Consultation strategy

4.4.7 Data analysis (Substantial change of content)

4.4.8 Reporting (Substantial change of content)

5 Tasks chapters

5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning (Enlargement of the content)

5.1.2 State of the art

5.1.2.2 Crisis response planning (Added introductory paragraph)

5.1.3 Landscape (Substantial change of content)

5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment

5.2.3 Landscape (Substantial change of content)

5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making

5.3.3 Landscape (Substantial change of content)

5.3.4 Perception of needs (Substantial change of content)

5.4 Common Operational Picture

5.4.3 Landscape (Substantial change of content)

5.4.4 Perception of needs (Substantial change of content)

5.5 Alert and warning

5.5.2 State of the art (Enlargement of the content)

5.5.2.4 Public response to alert and warning (Enlargement of the content)

5.5.2.5 Proposal for decision making in alert and warning (Enlargement of the content)

5.5.3 Landscape (Substantial change of content)

6 Legal barriers and ethical concerns (New section)

7 Conclusions (New section)

Annexes: (No major changes)

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters **M18**

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Linked project Work Package: WP5 Common practices, and operational procedures for first aid responses

Linked project tasks:

- T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment
- T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making
- T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning

Action: Study

Status: First Release **(Update from D5.1)**

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. Deliverable D5.5 is framed into the project WP5. The document D5.5 presents a Description of the procedural and operational opportunities identified and assessed during the working streams conducted at T5.1, T5.2, T5.3 and T5.4 **and is an updated version from D5.1.**

3. Project Overview

3.1. VALKYRIES Project overview

Mass casualty incidents (MCI) and multiple casualty disasters, where the number of victims far exceeds local resources and capabilities, are events that overwhelm the local health system, at least for a period of time.

The response of EMS first responders to these events often reveals insufficient resources (rescue personnel, medical personnel, facilities, etc.), communication difficulties and organizational interoperability problems, which are more acute in cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical actions.

Although the EU has evolved towards a strong capacity for joint coordination and cross-sectoral cooperation between Member States, studies such as the EU Mandate M/487 to establish EU security standards reveal that the Union is not yet at a stage where responders can interconnect information management systems from different organisations to share situation assessment or automate coordinated response procedures.

Echoing these needs, the project VALKYRIES (Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated Procedures for First Aid Vehicles Deployment on European Multi-victim Disasters) aims to analyse, improve and demonstrate infrastructures, protocols and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during deployment, intervention and local/remote coordination of first aid responders in multi-casualty disasters.

The VALKYRIES project aims to explore the impact of the emerging technologies, procedures and collaboration tools for supporting the cross-sectorial actuation of the first aid responders on cross-border disasters and major crisis situations. On these grounds, VALKYRIES will develop methodologies, adaptation tactics and decision criteria for their harmonisation according to the related pan-European ecosystems.

As the SIGRUN system, to be introduced as the result of the Valkyries project, is going to be “federated”, aka acting as the interoperability layer of existing technological systems working and parametrized to support different local workflows and procedures/ regulations or cross-border agreements, a minimum common workflow and operational procedures needs to be identified in order to support its functionality as such “federated system”.

For such harmonisation, discovery of regulatory opportunities, validation and demonstration will be documented and analysed, reporting practical field notes and guidelines able to feed standardisation and regulation bodies and serving as a reference for further related integrations.

3.2. WP5 Work package overview

VALKYRIES work has been split into seven work packages (WP). Three of them (WP4, WP5 and WP6) will embrace the three core blocks of working streams will be developed in parallel:

- Technologies and equipment (KARA): WP4
- Procedures and Operations (HERJA): WP5
- Collaboration and Training (EIR): WP6

The main aim of the reference integration, SIGRUN, is to provide a real use case driven implementation that allow applying the proposed normalizations on some of the discovered technological (KARA), procedural (HERJA) and collaborative and training (EIR) opportunities.

Figure 1 – Global vision of the VALKYRIES project.

VALKYRIES WP5: Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses, aims to provide a global information framework of the common EU operational plans and procedures, and deliver guidelines and harmonisation recommendations for practices and operational procedures for facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between actors in the first aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters. The WP5 will facilitate the understanding of the complex map of practises and operative procedures in aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters, by surveying, studying and analysing the common practices, reconnaissance, triage and care of victims, crisis response planning, maintenance, logistics, Command and control (C2) operations, development of a Common Operational Picture and alerting/warning.

In the course of WP5, partners will work at assembling draft standards or suggesting modifications of the existing ones for solving the gaps and harmonisation issues found, and lessons learned.

WP5 will address the following related tasks:

- **T5.1: Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning.** The objective of this task is to provide global information framework of the common EU operational plans and procedures, and deliver guidelines and harmonisation recommendations for reconnaissance procedures, triage and care practises, and crisis response planning. The task will provide a map of the related procedural opportunities, and the analysis of the identified regulatory and harmonization gaps, proposing a tentative roadmap for their EU-level capacitation. Based on end-users' requirements for the reference integration, a subset of these procedures will be harmonized by following the VALKYRIES harmonization tactics, resulting in recommendation for further related actions.

- **T5.2: Maintenance, logistics and Deployment.** The goal of this task is to plan, organise, implement and develop maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responses. Thorough study and analysis of the existing capabilities, debriefing principles for first aid relate pan-European exercises and cross-border crises in support of preparation of an adequate organisation of logistic and deployment for the European Emergency Medical Services. In this way, VALKYRIES will develop advanced skills in maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responders. The skills obtained will be e tested in multinational, cross-sectorial field and to support the process of harmonisation for first aid responders in case of cross-border and cross-hierarchical disaster situations. The task will deliver a map of the related opportunities, the analysis of the discovered normalization and regulatory gaps, and a tentative roadmap for their fulfilment. A subset of them will be harmonised towards serving the SGRUN reference integration.
- **T5.3: Command and Control and support to operational decision-making.** It is an objective of this task to explore existing gaps and emerging enablers towards defining an information network that allows emergency commanders to maintain situational awareness and obtain relevant information for decision making. It is also an objective of this task producing recommendations to develop new capabilities, harmonisation and integration regarding C2, on which the Consortium experts and supportive external advisory board will imbue all cross-sectorial, cross-hierarchy and cross-border perspectives. The subset of selected capabilities for harmonization will be reference integrated at the SIGRUN platform, serving at the project demonstrations
- **T5.4: Common Operational Picture and warning.** This task aims to define a VALKYRIES Common Operational Picture with all the relevant information that facilitate collaborative planning and the coordinated execution of the response by all the levels involved. This picture will incorporate and contextualize in real-time the key data points and streams from the VALKYRIES data-sharing framework, to support to the decision-makers in the disaster management. Another objective of this task is to provide recommendations and guidelines to issue alerts and warnings in disaster situations. To this end, the work methodology will be based on the analysis, discussion and agreement between the partners involved in the project, with the support of the panel of external consultants.

4. Introduction

4.1. Objective

As described in the project's harmonisation framework document (D2.5), the defined VALKYRIES harmonisation process has three main stages, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2 - VALKYRIES harmonisation process

The first stage of the harmonisation process is the description and analysis of the existing state-of-the-art.

The aim of this document is to complete this first stage by exploring new opportunities through an analysis of the existing landscape considering a cross-border, cross-sectoral and cross-hierarchical situation in first aid response.

4.2. Scope

D5.5 (Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters) will provide a description of the procedural and operational opportunities identified and assessed during the working streams conducted at T5.1, T5.2, T5.3 and T5.4, fulfilling the following established requirements:

BASE REQUIREMENTS

The following table lists the 2 base (mandatory) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_BASE_T5.1_1	P1	EU operational MCI procedures MUST be analysed	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.1_7	P1	Collection and analysis of needs related to C2 from the perspective of responders.	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection

Table 1 - D5.5 Base requirements

COMMON REQUIREMENTS

The following table lists the 37 common (optional) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.1_1	P1	Crisis management plans at the local, regional or national level, coordination and support plans at the international level MUST be studied and analyzed.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_2	P1	Emergency services SHOULD have specific action procedures to deal with incidents with multiple victims (disaster medical management plan)	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.1_3	P2	Organization and capacities of health systems	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_4	P2	Analysis of the event notification process that entails the activation of a response plan to a health crisis	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_6	P1	The operational structure SHOULD involve the division of tasks, including roles, responsibilities and authorities, as well as the coordination of	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection

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ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
		various medical and non-medical operational assets			
REQ_COM_T5.1_8	P2	Medical communications and information management	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_9	P2	Inventory of available health resources (human and material)	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.2_6	P2	Capacity of an emergency team to increase its operational resources in case more resources are needed than those available in the ordinary device.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_7	P2	It MAY be necessary to supply medical material and medicines to assist victims.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_8	P1	It MUST be ensured that the first responders have the basic means necessary to act in the disaster area: fuel, supplies, transportation, rest areas...	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration

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ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_9	P2	In disasters, a stable communications network may not be possible.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_12	P2	Logistical capacity MUST be available to house, if necessary, people affected by the disaster who must be evacuate	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_6	P2	Capacity of an emergency team to increase its operational resources in case more resources are needed than those available in the ordinary device.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_7	P2	It MAY be necessary to supply medical material and medicines to assist victims.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_8	P1	It MUST be ensured that the first responders have the basic means necessary to act in the disaster area: fuel, supplies, transportation, rest areas...	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_9	P2	In disasters, a stable communications network may not be possible.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_12	P2	Logistical capacity MUST be available to house, if necessary, people affected by the disaster who must be evacuate	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_5	P2	The initial contingency response MUST be protocolized to favor immediate intervention in the event of an incident.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_6	P2	An effective operational communications network MUST be established within incident response planning to ensure communications	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
		with teams deployed on scene.			
REQ_COM_T5.3_7	P2	An Incident Command Post MUST be established to ensure command and control on scene.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_8	P2	The basic actions for the containment of the damage caused by the incident MUST be initiated from the very first moment, to reduce the added risks for those affected and for the first responders.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_9	P2	The incident scene MUST be organized into homogeneous zones according to the level of risk and the operational objectives pursued in each zone.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.3_10	P2	Upon confirmation of an incident, a pre-established Emergency Operations Plan MUST be activated to ensure an adequate response.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_11	P2	An Emergency Response Coordination Center MUST be set up, bringing together all those responsible for the disaster command and control center. This center MUST have a unified command.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_14	P2	The necessary and appropriate resources MUST be mobilized to respond to the emergency.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_20	P2	There SHOULD be an effective system for detection, communication and provision of logistical needs, which guarantees adequate support for the efficient operation of the resources deployed on the scene.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

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ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_1	P1	The terms used in the COP MUST be defined and standardized	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_8	P2	The COP MUST show the updated information at all times.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_9	P2	The COP MAY indicate other possible risks in the area of operations (risk map).	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_10	P2	The COP MAY indicate elements of special vulnerability in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_11	P2	The COP MAY indicate logistics resources of interest previously registered in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_12	P2	Te COP SHOULD locate the hospitals of the health system in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_15	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the victims in the scenario of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

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ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_16	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of emergency vehicles in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_17	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the first responders in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_19	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the resources deployed to support the intervention of the emergency medical service on the scene of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_27	P2	Recommendations must be established regarding the emission of alerts and alarms through public address systems and other elementary resources in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

Table 2 - D5.5 Common requirements

4.3. Methodology

This first stage by exploring opportunities thought an analysis of the existing *landscape of emergency operational and procedural opportunities for first responder on multi-casualty disasters* has followed this methodology:

Steps of the methodology:

1. Define the scope of the landscape and the document.
2. Divide the analysis into areas of knowledge limited by the scope of the tasks.
3. Identify the state of the art of each of the areas. Based on:
 - Personal experience
 - Scientific studies
 - Reference standards and guidance
 - Expert consultation
 - etc.

There is a special section on consultation strategy (see point 4.4).

4. Filter the information on the basis on:
 - The scope of the task
 - Focused mainly on VALKYRIES use cases an
 - Focused mainly on the countries involved.
5. Identify future areas of improvement, where technologies are moving forward and what the next steps in these areas will be.
6. Pre-identify the needs of end-users and responders.
7. Pre-identify opportunities for improvement
8. identifying legal barriers that may affect the development of these opportunities
9. Finally, develop conclusions to outline the next steps in terms of opportunities in each of the areas.

4.4. Consultation strategy

The VALKYRIES project is committed in analysing, improving, and developing infrastructures, protocols and raising data exchange standardisation and harmonisation tactics able to increase the effectiveness and interoperability in emergency situations, such as those prevailing in operation of first aid vehicles or cross-frontier disaster response.

Three work streams will be developed in the project: First Responder Technologies and Equipment (KARA), First Responder Procedures and Operation (HERJA), and First Responder Collaboration and Training (EIR).

According to the general strategy of the VALKYRIES project, contained in the VALKYRIES D1.7 Consultation strategy D1.7, a common consultation strategy was designed for those 3 work streams of the project.

4.4.1. Objectives and motivation of the WP5 consultation

- **Motivation:** transversely to the different work packages outlined in the project, acquiring the vision from external experts plays a pivotal role, as it will lead to drive the harmonization of protocols and technologies consistently with the project objectives.

- **Objective:** generation of a report describing the procedural and operational opportunities identified and assessed regarding the work streams.

4.4.2. Tools and methods

Questionnaire distributed among technical and operational managers of different EU emergency services.

Three questionnaires were defined by WP4, WP5 and WP6 researchers, oriented respectively to each of the project's work streams:

- WP4 (KARA): Technologies and Equipment for first aid responders
- WP5 (HERJA): Procedures and Operation for first aid responders
- WP6 (EIR): Collaboration and Training for first aid responders

4.4.3. Targeted WP5 questionnaire stakeholders

- First round: first responders partners of the consortium, of the EAB and of linked projects. These results will be included, as an approximation of the reality at EU level, in the first draft of deliverable (D5.1).
- Second round: emergency services potentially involved in responding to mass casualty incidents or disasters in the EU. Each Emergency Service participating in the study would provide a single response to the WP5 questionnaire. These results are included in the final version of deliverable (D5.5).

4.4.4. Facilitators

Valkyries project researchers (emergency services contact and questionnaire distribution).

4.4.5. Timing

Distribution and completion of the first round of surveys: 27 May to 6 June 2022.

Distribution and completion of the second round of surveys: 28 October to 01 December 2022.

4.4.6. Data storage

The collected data will be cloud-stored in the general repository of the project. After the project, the report will be stored in the project official website to be used upon request for future actions related to the project objectives.

4.4.7. Data analysis

The objective assessment will be made on the basis of the information gathered from the consulted Emergency Services.

For the final round of interviews, 40 qualified contact persons from 40 Emergency Services across the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA) were contacted. The questionnaires were sent by email to each contact/service, after explaining the purpose of the survey and receiving their consent to participate.

In the end, a total of 14 fully completed questionnaires were received and analysed to describe the picture. These positive results to the questionnaire proposal were clustered in the most influential countries of the VALKYRIES consortium (Spain, Greece, Slovakia, Italy and Portugal) which is certainly a limiting factor for the significance of the obtained results.

Figure 3 - Distribution of completed WP5 questionnaires according to the region

Among the emergency services that completed the survey there is a clear predominance of Emergency Medical Services (EMS) followed by the fire services. The rest of services (Emergency Operations Centre (EOC), Civil Protection, Police and Military), for the purpose of analysis, were grouped under the umbrella term: OTHERS.

Figure 4 - Distribution of completed WP5 questionnaires according to type of Emergency Service

In relation to the possible involvement or not in response to cross-national MCIs or disasters, the responding emergency services were split 50/50, which was favourable for the matching of results between the two cases.

Figure 5 - Distribution of completed WP5 questionnaires according to type of Emergency Service and to its potential involvement or not in responding to cross-national MCI or disasters

The data were analysed and evaluated by the VALKYRIES tasks leaders in order to extract policy and recommendations on the possible exploitation of VALKYRIES solution.

The results are presented in an aggregated form, so that it will not be possible to identify the individual responses of each service.

The analysis of the results focused, among others, on the following aspects:

- Differences between different types of emergency services.
- Differences between services potentially involved or not involved in cross-national MCIs or disasters response.
- The homogeneity of the situation between the different EU/EEA countries surveyed. In this respect, the following levels of homogeneity were established according to the degree (%) of concurrence of the responses obtained:
 - 86% to 100%: Very High
 - 71% to 85: High.
 - 51% to 70%: Medium
 - 0% to 50%: Low

4.4.8. Reporting

The results will be accessible for:

- VALKYRIES researchers throughout the project life cycle.
- Reporting back to the Emergency Services consulted (if they are interested).
- Other related projects and third parties upon request it once the project is finished, under the terms established in the project's intellectual property agreement of VALKYRIES' s project.

5. Tasks chapters

As a result of the work of the WP5 tasks, and in order to structure the results in a clear and homogeneous way, the overview of EU common operational plans and procedures is presented in the following sections:

- Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning, reflecting the findings of the task T5.1
- Logistics and Deployment operational procedures, reflecting the findings of the task T5.2
- Command and Control procedures, reflecting the findings of the task T5.3
- Common Operational Picture (COP), reflecting the corresponding findings of task T5. 4
- Alert and Warning, reflecting the corresponding findings of task T5.4

5.1. Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning

Taking into account the different key aspects of mass casualty incident management, VALKYRIES will identify and analyse opportunities and standardization gaps in the different phases of mass casualty incident management, adapting them to the suggested harmonization.

These key aspects include situation assessment, triage and crisis response plans. It is also essential to have a core set of data derived from these processes to ensure harmonization, facilitate communication, interoperability and efficiency.

5.1.1. Introduction

5.1.1.1. Introduction

Disasters are situations in which widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses have occurred that exceed the capacity of the affected organization, community or society to respond and recover with its own resources.

From a health perspective, in all mass casualty situations (whether disasters or incidents), the response capacity of local health systems is overwhelmed, at least for a period of time.

In addition to this inability to cope with the situation with their own resources, there are other factors that determine the damage that occurs in disasters. These factors are risk and vulnerability.

Risk is defined as the probability that a given system or population will be affected by hazards. Risk combines the probability of an event occurring and the negative effects that result from it. Risks themselves are not disasters, but factors that can lead to negative effects that result if the disaster occurs.

In many cases, the impact of a disaster depends more on the vulnerability, preparedness and response capacity of the affected community than on the intrinsic magnitude of the event, and these variables are closely related to the level of development of a society.

Vulnerability is defined as the "damage response" capacity of society to a potentially catastrophic event, or the susceptibility of a population or system to the effects of the hazard. There are a number of factors that determine vulnerability: physical, economic, social, political, technical, ideological, cultural, ecological, institutional, and organizational.

Risk therefore depends on vulnerability, hazard and the coping capacity of the population. The relationship is expressed as follows:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Vulnerability} \times \text{Hazard} - \text{Coping capacity}$$

Disasters can be classified according to different aspects, one of the most commonly used being that which divides them according to the cause that originates them. Thus, they can be:

- Natural: geological, hydro-meteorological, biological...
- Anthropogenic or man-made: industrial, technological, social, etc.
- Natural-technological synergies

5.1.1.2. The disaster cycle: phases

Disasters unfold in a cyclical manner. Understanding the disaster cycle is the key to being able to investigate its risk factors, address its effects and put prevention mechanisms in place.

In any disaster, there are five distinct phases:

- Silent, inter-disaster phase
- Warning, pre-impact or pre-disaster phase
- Impact phase
- Emergency, relief or isolation phase
- Recovery or reconstruction phase

SILENT OR INTER-DISASTER PHASE

Long before a disaster occurs, authorities should provide for preparedness and prevention measures and conduct training and education programmes for the community. A number of preventive activities essential for proper emergency management should be carried out.

These include:

- Mapping specific sites of potential hazards, highlighting the possible associated risks (hazard maps). These maps constitute the cartographic representation of the relative importance of each risk analysed in each area
- Comprehensive community vulnerability analysis
- Inventory of available resources in the event of a disaster in order to rapidly mobilize and effectively coordinate these resources
- Plan prevention, preparedness and mitigation measures
- Conduct education and training of health personnel and the community

WARNING, PRE-IMPACT OR PRE-DISASTER PHASE

During this phase, several essential emergency management activities must be undertaken:

- Dissemination of early warning warnings based on forecasting systems
- Implementation of protective measures based on community preparedness and contingency plans

IMPACT PHASE

When the catastrophe occurs, destruction, injuries and deaths occur. The event may last for a few seconds, as in earthquakes, or for days or weeks, as in floods or droughts. The impact of a disaster on human health varies widely depending on different factors, such as the nature of the event itself, the population density, the state of health and nutrition before the impact, the climate and the organization of health services.

EMERGENCY (RELIEF OR ISOLATION) PHASE

This phase begins immediately after the impact and is when support and assistance must be provided to the victims. During this period, the affected community is isolated (isolation period) and many of the most urgent rescue tasks are undertaken by the survivors themselves, using locally available resources. The existence of community preparedness plans greatly increases self-reliance and aid effectiveness, contributing to the reduction of disaster-related morbidity and mortality.

The following actions should be taken:

- Immediate actions necessary to save lives
- Search and rescue operations
- First aid and emergency medical assistance
- Restoration of emergency communications and transportation networks
- Public health epidemiological surveillance
- Evacuation of areas still vulnerable

RECONSTRUCTION OR REHABILITATION PHASE

In this phase, the rehabilitation capacity of the social group becomes apparent. The restoration of pre-disaster conditions begins. The time spent in this phase is difficult to define; can start very early, even in the emergency period, and can last for many years.

The reconstruction phase that should lead to the restoration of those conditions includes:

- Restoration of normal local health services.
- Assistance, repair and reconstruction of damaged facilities and buildings.
- Reflection on lessons learned from the recent disaster that can help improve current emergency preparedness plans. - Reflection on lessons learned from the recent disaster that can help improve current emergency preparedness plans.

Figure 6 - Disaster Cycle

5.1.1.3. Civil protection

Civil protection is the public service that protects people and property by ensuring an adequate response to different types of emergencies and disasters.

Civil protection systems act in different phases of disasters. Thus, their actions are anticipation, prevention of civil protection risks, planning, immediate response to emergencies, recovery, and evaluation and inspection of the system.

Planning includes the elaboration and implementation of civil protection plans. These plans are instruments that provide the framework and mechanisms for mobilizing the necessary resources to protect people and property in the event of an emergency, as well as coordination between different administrations.

There are different types of civil protection plans depending on the scope of action (local, regional, state) and the risks they address (territorial or special).

The plans establish levels of severity or emergency situations according to the damage that may occur and the extent to which the response capacity is exceeded.

Emergency response comprises the action of all those intervention and assistance services that aim to prevent damage, rescue and protect people and property, ensure public safety and meet the basic subsistence needs of the affected population. It therefore includes emergency health, psychological and social assistance, shelter and initial damage repair to restore essential services, as well as other actions necessary to initiate recovery.

National civil protection systems, which are themselves composed of several administrative levels (local, regional, state) are based on solidarity.

In the event that national disaster response resources are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced, countries help each other through the European Civil Protection Mechanism.

5.1.1.4. Emergency Medical Systems

Health care in mass casualty incidents or disasters (MCI) is carried out by emergency medical systems (EMS). EMSs are made up of technical and human elements that deploy their capabilities within a multidisciplinary care system called the Emergency Medical Service (EMS). This integrated system is the one that optimizes patient care, from the onset of an urgent process to their social reintegration.

MCIs are characterized by the fact that there is a great disproportion between the care needs of those affected and the system's capacity to meet them. In addition to being overwhelmed, in many cases the EMS itself can also be hindered in its functioning by damage to its own structure or to other basic infrastructures in the environment where the disaster takes place (telecommunications, roads, supplies, etc.).

This is why in these situations, effective collaboration between different emergency services that usually work independently and do not always share common procedures is essential.

The objective should be to ensure that both procedures and planning are compatible and integrable.

There is no homogeneity in SEMs. Different aspects of the services can be assessed and classified in relation to each other.

- Depending on the coordination unit, the service can be centralised or satellite
- According to the analysis of the demand and the determination of the response: dispatching or health regulation
- According to the response options: single resource or staggered response
- According to the professional profile of its care structure: non-medicalised or medicalised

By way of example, EMS in the USA (and similarly in Canada, the UK, etc.) essentially operate with paramedics supervised by medical staff, with a "dispatching" type of demand regulation system (dispatching of calls according to predetermined protocols). The patient is systematically and urgently transferred to a hospital for definitive assessment and further care.

In contrast, the Spanish EMS model is staffed by technical, nursing and medical personnel, and aims to provide the patient with the urgently needed advanced care on site, while ensuring adequate continuity of care. The response to the demand for care is usually decided by medical regulation.

5.1.1.5. Health response to disasters or incidents with mass casualties

The health response to MCIs is a critical event that requires the adoption of specific operational and clinical criteria to ensure the maximum collective benefit, and perfect coordination between all the emergency services involved is essential.

In general, several phases can be defined in the emergency medical system (EMS) response to an ICM:

PLANNING

Defining, analysing and studying the objectives to be achieved, as well as the way in which they are to be achieved. Planning is the fundamental basis for an effective response when a collective emergency occurs.

ALERT

Full readiness for action pending a request for intervention. Early warning encourages an early response.

ALARM

Initiated when, having knowledge of the occurrence of an ICM, the response is triggered. For the activation of an EMS, basic information is required, such as:

- Type and characteristics of the incident to determine the specific resources and procedures for intervention.
- Location of the incident (precise location of each source, accessibility, terrain characteristics, etc.).
- Estimated number and severity of casualties.
- Identification of resources present and determination of those needed to develop the response.
- Estimated incident resolution time: to plan logistical support.

APPROACH

This is the phase in which the mobilized resources are initially directed and positioned in the intervention area. In the approach, as in the rest of the intervention phases, it is essential to take into account the safety of the entire team (attention to precautionary measures, use of personal protective equipment, etc.). No one will access the impact area without authorization from the director of the Advanced Command Post (ACP). The emergency services will initially be located outside this area, in a safe zone.

CONTROL

This is the phase in which everything necessary is in place to carry out the victim assistance work in adequate conditions for all those present in the crisis area.

In relation to the people affected, it would include the immediate measures necessary to protect those who have not yet been harmed from risk or to prevent further harm to those already harmed, where possible.

In relation to First Responders, it includes the measures necessary to work as coordinated, efficient and safely as possible at the scene.

The main objectives of the control phase are:

- To organize and ensure the safety of the area of action (by zoning) and in the impact zone (by acting on the active risks at the source: hazard control).

- Establish command and coordination mechanisms.
- Establish communications.

In order to ensure organization and safety in the area of action, the control phase involves zoning, which consists of dividing the area of operations of a collective emergency into 3 concentric zones, each with a specific function and specific resources:

- Rescue area (also called focus, intervention zone, red zone or ground zero). It is established around the area where the disaster has occurred, defined by a safety perimeter. It is a work zone initially reserved for search and rescue teams. The priority in this area is logically to control risks and rescue victims.
- Relief area (also known as the assistance area or yellow area), between the rescue area and the base area. It represents the health area par excellence, as it is in this area that the emergency health teams will deploy their eventual assistance structures (Advanced Medical Post, etc.) and will proceed to the advanced care of all victims.
- Base area (also called parking area, support area or green zone). This is the logistical and command area par excellence. The Forward Command Post, media and family care centres, base camp, etc. will be established within this area.

DEPLOYMENT

Phase of the intervention in collective emergencies in which the human and material resources mobilized to coordinate and carry out the assistance are placed in the intervention area.

The effectiveness of deployment depends fundamentally on the number and real response capacity of the resources available and the degree of organization of the intervention. In collective emergency response, most of the eventual structures are set up from trailers or quick-assembly tents. It is the responsibility of the Incident Command in coordination with the Medical Group Director, to decide on the location of the eventual structures for health response to the mass emergency.

INITIAL HEALTH CARE

Initial health care basically consists of:

- Rescue of the victims trapped or under risk.
- Establishment of the priority of care or "primary triage" (treatment triage) with the application of basic life-saving gestures (opening of the airway and control of active external haemorrhages, fundamentally) and labelling of the victims (making their priority of care visible).
- Stabilization: complex diagnostic and therapeutic manoeuvres would already be applied to optimize the patient's clinical condition so that the patient can be transferred at the most appropriate time.
- Establishment of evacuation priority or "secondary triage" (evacuation triage).

EVACUATION AND TRANSFER

Transfer of each victim to the appropriate place for definitive treatment, ensuring that the necessary care is provided to the patient on a continuous basis. In the receiving health centres there must also be prior planning in relation to both the overall organization of the response and the specific care procedures in collective emergency situations.

It would include the evacuation to safe shelter areas of the still unaffected population when necessary to protect them from risk.

Figure 7 - Zoning and deployment in MCI

WITHDRAWAL AND REACTIVATION

Organized collection and return of resources to a fully operational state after the end of the assistance.

ANALYSIS

Reflective study of the intervention following an MCI aimed at the continuous improvement of operational and care procedures.

The procedures for dealing with incidents or disasters with mass casualties establish figures responsible for those actions that are considered key to an adequate organization of the response and to be able to guarantee the traceability of the victim from their first contact with the emergency services until their arrival at the hospital. These figures are carried out by different agencies depending on the organization and structure of the civil protection system in

each country, region or municipality. These actions are described below in order to understand the systematic health response to a multi-casualty incident.

AMBULANCE REGISTRATION AND TRACKING

When ambulances arrive at the scene of the incident they must be informed where to park. That place is the parking area. In this area there should be a person in charge whose job is to receive incoming ambulances, tell them how and where to park, and who will tell them when to go to the evacuation station to pick up a casualty once they have been triaged (evacuation triage) at the forward medical station.

CASUALTY REGISTRATION AND TRACKING

When casualties are first triaged (treatment triage) they should be tagged for follow-up. The victim's tag must accompany them throughout the entire care process. Once the victims arrive at the advanced medical post, there is a person in charge of registration and filiation at the entrance to the post who registers their data such as triage card number if this has been used, age range, sex, etc.

TREATMENT TRIAGE (PRIMARY TRIAGE)

This is what is known as first triage or primary triage, and aims to establish which victims are treated first at the advanced medical station.

VICTIM STRETCHER CARRYING

The stretching of victims is carried out between the different areas of the incident or the structures deployed for victim assistance. For example, from the focus area to the casualty concentration area or casualty nest, or from this area to the forward medical post.

CASUALTY STABILIZATION

At the medical outpost, medical personnel assist the patient to return vital signs to normal and the patient can be evacuated to a hospital in the best possible conditions.

EVACUATION TRIAGE (SECONDARY TRIAGE)

This is the triage that decides the order in which patients should be transferred to hospital.

EVACUATION CONTROL

There must be a person in charge who controls all those victims who are waiting to be evacuated and ensures that their transfer to the mobile resources that are going to transfer them is done properly.

DETERMINING THE PATIENT'S DESTINATION HOSPITAL

Deciding the destination hospital for the victims is a key point in the management of a mass casualty incident. It allows, on the one hand, to ensure that the patient will receive the definitive treatment he/she needs for his/her injuries and, on the other hand, that hospitals receive only those patients they can actually treat.

Figure 8 - Key points in the health organization of an MCI

5.1.1.6. Reconnaissance interoperability and MDS

To contribute to the assessments of the situation, the first responders' teams must reconnaissance the incident sharing Minimum Data Set (MDS) with all the involved parts.

During the emergency, minimum data set must be known and shared in an interoperable way in order to carry out the emergency. For this reason, the Valkyries project is working on defining the minimum data set that must be shared among the members of the emergency to carry out the incident.

In the first part of the emergency the priorities may be to recognize the affected area, locate and remove the affected people, identify possible risks and threats that endanger the integrity of first aid responders and victims. These blocks of information are called in the minimum data set Pre-event settings and Incident MDS.

These data must be fully interoperable and known by all members of the emergency. The lack of one of these data by one of the members of the emergency generates a risk.

Next, minimum data must be known about the available resources in terms of vehicles and first responders involved in the emergency. These blocks of information are called First Responders and Vehicles in the MDS.

The information regarding the triage of the victims is key in any emergency. Different institutions can triage each of the victims and traceability must not be lost, so within this minimum and interoperable data there is a specific block of information for the victims on their identification and triage.

Finally, the resources available in the hospitals, location of hospitals, available beds. This is the block of hospitals MDS.

5.1.2. State of the art

The EU Civil Protection Mechanism brings together a total of 33 countries: 27 EU Member States and 6 participating states (Norway, Iceland, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey). This European civil protection 'family' shares similar operational challenges and approaches to disaster management, while the structure and composition of the emergency services of the 33 countries varies considerably from one country to another.

5.1.2.1. Reconnaissance and triage

MCI or disaster management is a process that must be developed and include a number of activities including: observation, information gathering, processing and exchange, situation assessment including forecasting, planning, decision-making and communication of decisions taken, implementation of decisions, feedback gathering and control measures¹.

Given the importance of information gathering, processing and sharing, it is considered important to have a systematic approach or model that allows information on an incident to be gathered in a consistent manner by all agencies involved².

The "METHANE" model, proposed by the Advanced Life Support Group (ALSG) in its Major Incident Medical Management and Support (MIMMS) course, brings structure and clarity to the initial stages of the management of any multi-agency or large-scale incident.

The METHANE model is an established reporting framework that provides a common structure for managers and their control rooms to share information on major incidents. It is recommended to use M/ETHANE for all incidents.

For incidents below the serious incident threshold, 'METHANE' is converted into an 'ETHANE' message. During the decision-making process using the joint decision-making model, there should be regular consideration of the "M" (representing "major incident") by the response agencies to establish whether a developing incident exceeds the major incident threshold.

Each response agency should send an M/ETHANE message to its control room as soon as possible. The first resources on the scene should send the M/ETHANE message so that situational awareness can be established quickly. Information received through multiple M/ETHANE messages will gradually accumulate to support shared situational awareness within responders and between control rooms.

The acronym stands for:

- M: Major incident
- E: Exact location
- T: Type of incident
- H: Hazards
- A: Access
- N: Number of casualties

¹ ISO 22320:2018. Security and resilience-Emergency management-Guidelines for incident management.

² <https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf>

- E: Emergency Services

Multi-casualty incidents represent a major healthcare challenge for emergency medical systems. The casualty triage procedure is a key element of healthcare and largely determines the outcome of the response³.

In MCI and disasters, the aim is to give priority care to those most likely to survive, trying to treat as many patients as possible in the shortest possible time, as it has been shown that proper prioritisation is associated with a decrease in morbidity and mortality.

Pre-hospital triage is a fundamental pillar in the management of MCIs and should be carried out in a systematised manner, using known and tested protocols that allow orderly and appropriate management.

Triage consists of classifying victims according to their severity, vital prognosis and according to the therapeutic time frame (maximum time a victim can remain without treatment and without suffering aggravation of their injuries or endangering their life).

Different countries have different health systems and different organisation of the pre-hospital response.

The ultimate goal of triage is to reduce the critical death rate by early identification of serious casualties, application of life-saving gestures and advanced life support if necessary. It is also important to manage minor casualties appropriately so that they do not consume too many care resources.

Multiple triage methods and different severity scales have been published in the scientific literature, but only a few have had some relevance and most with very limited scientific evidence. Many have been evaluated and validated with simulations, not with real events. Analysis in real incidents provides very useful information, but it must also be taken into account that the data are not comparable because the contexts are usually heterogeneous. Hence the importance of recording and analysing real MCIs to obtain useful and contrasted information.

There is therefore no scientific evidence on the effects of validated prehospital triage systems and on the effects of using the same triage system in two or more EMS settings. But the fact that there is no solid evidence on the effect of triage systems does not mean that they are ineffective. It means that we do not know whether they are effective, nor can we suggest the magnitude of a possible effect. This is why it is essential to conduct studies on the tools that are introduced in the emergency services⁴.

There are two main groups of triage methods: according to polarity and according to the families of variables that are assessed in the victim.

³ Castro Delgado, Rafael; Correa Arango, Adriana; Cuartas Álvarez, Tatiana; Arcos González, Pedro. Bases conceptuales del triaje prehospitalario en incidentes de múltiples víctimas. Evidentia. 2015 jul-dic; 12(51-52). Disponible en: <<http://www.index-f.com/evidentia/n51-52/ev9878.php>> Consultado el 15 de Junio de 2022

⁴ Lidal et al. Triage systems for pre-hospital emergency medical services-a systematic review. Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine 2013, 21:28

- Depending on the polarity, triage can be bipolar, tripolar, tetrapolar or pentapolar, depending on whether two, three, four or five options are chosen. For example: it would be bipolar to choose between alive-dead, tripolar to choose between walk-do not walk, but respond-all the rest, tetrapolar to choose between red-yellow-green-black or pentapolar to choose between the previous colour options and add blue.
- According to families of variables: they can be functional or physiological, lesions or anatomical or mixed.
 - Functional or physiological: they assign priority for medical assistance based on the victim's basic vital signs such as level of consciousness, respiratory rate or the presence of a pulse. Examples include the Glasgow Coma Scale, START (Simple Triage and Rapid Treatment), Trauma Score (TS), Revised Trauma Score (RTS), SHORT Triage, Rapid Method of Classification in Disasters (MRCC), CareFlight Triage, Sieve Method and CareFlight Method.
 - Injury or anatomical methods: based on the injuries found on the victim. Examples of this triage are the Injury Severity Score (ISS), the Abbreviated Injury Score (AIS), the Penetrating and Blunt Trauma Code (PBEL), the Wallace Rule of Nine and the Organ Injury Scale.
 - Mixed Methods: prioritise according to the status of the victim's vital signs and injuries. For example, the CRAMS Scale (CRAML/CRAMH), the Lindsey Scale and the Hospital Trauma Index.

Figure 9 - START triage method

In the pre-hospital setting, two levels of triage can be distinguished: first and second triage.

FIRST TRIAGE, BASIC OR PRIMARY TRIAGE

This can be carried out in the impact zone, provided it is safe. If it is not safe, it is carried out in the relief area, in a pre-established area that can be called the casualty concentration area or casualty nest. This triage provides an overview of the magnitude of the emergency and the resources needed to care for the victims. It should be quick, simple and replicable. It can be applied by non-medical personnel with basic training and who are trained in its application.

SECOND TRIAGE, ADVANCED TRIAGE OR SECONDARY TRIAGE

It is carried out in the relief zone, generally in the advanced health post. It prioritises stabilisation and/or pre-hospital treatment, and evacuation for definitive treatment. It should be carried out by emergency medical personnel.

Regardless of the method used, the classification of casualties is expressed by an internationally accepted colour code, which in order of priority are: red, yellow, green and black.

Triage cards can be used for the labelling of casualties which, in addition to the colour with which a casualty is classified, can include information about the care process (life-saving gestures applied, stabilisation measures, etc.). As an example, the TASSICA 3 triage card is included with the START triage method on the front side for the first triage and on the back side the data that would be necessary to record the stabilisation of the victim and to perform the evacuation triage on the basis of the Revised Trauma Score (T-RTS).

The image shows the front of a TASSICA 3 triage card. It is a form with various sections and checkboxes. On the left, there are gender and age selection boxes: MALE, FEMALE, PREGNANT, INFANT, CHILD, ADULT, ELDERLY. Below these are color-coded categories: DECEASED (D) in black, EXPECTANT (P4) in blue, IMMEDIATE (P1) in red, DELAYED (P2) in yellow, and MINIMAL (P3) in green. The main body of the card is titled 'PRIMARY TRIAGE SEQUENCE PRIORITY FOR MEDICAL CARE' and contains seven numbered steps with checkboxes and arrows pointing to a 'CATEGORY' column. Step 1: 'THE PATIENT CAN WALK' points to 'P3'. Step 2: 'BREATHING ABSENT AFTER OPENING THE AIRWAY' points to 'D'. Step 3: 'INJURIES INCOMPATIBLE WITH LIFE' points to 'P4'. Step 4: 'RESPIRATORY RATE >30 bpm (<15 OR >45 bpm UP TO 8 YEARS OLD)' points to 'P1'. Step 5: 'ABSENT RADIAL PULSES or CAPILLARY REFILL >2 sec' points to 'P1'. Step 6: 'UNABLE TO FOLLOW SIMPLE COMMANDS' points to 'P1'. Step 7: 'OTHER CONDITION THAT MAKES WALKING IMPOSSIBLE' points to 'P2'. To the right of the 'CATEGORY' column is a 'TASSICA 3 Triage tag' section with a 'DECONTAMINATED' checkbox and 'IMMEDIATE INTERVENTIONS' section with checkboxes for 'APNEIC CHILDREN: 5 RESCUE BREATHS AND RE-EVALUATE', 'UNCONSCIOUSNESS: GUEDEL TUBE', and 'CONTROL OF MAJOR HEMORRHAGE'. There are also fields for 'TIME:' and 'ANTIDOTE / PAIN trt.'. The TASSICA logo and website 'www.tassica.com' are visible on the right side.

Figure 10 - Front of triage card TASSICA 3 (first triage or treatment triage)

Tassica 3 Triage tag

NAME: _____ CONTACT PHONE: _____ 17-00001

EXTERNAL HEMORRHAGE CONTROL

A

SPINAL TRAUMA CERVICAL RESTRICTION
 AIRWAY OBSTRUCTION AIRWAY CLEARING
 AIRWAY INJURY AIRWAY CONTROL

B

APNEA CLOSED CHEST INJURY
 BRADYPNEA OPEN CHEST INJURY
 TACHYPNEA TENSION PNEUMOTHORAX
 OXYGEN THERAPY PLEURAL DRAINAGE

C

CENTRAL PULSE PALLOR
 PERIPHERAL PULSE CYANOSIS
 BRADYCARDIA CLOSED ABDOMINAL/PELVIC INJURY
 TACHYCARDIA OPEN ABDOMINAL/PELVIC INJURY

D

UNRESPONSIVE AGITATION
 RESPONSE TO PAIN ANISOCORY
 RESPONSE TO VOICE CLOSED HEAD INJURY
 ALERT OPEN HEAD INJURY

E

DATE AND SIGNATURE: _____

WARNINGS

TREATMENT

SECONDARY TRIAGE
PRIORITY FOR EVACUATION **P1** **P2** **P3** **P4** **D**

NAME: _____ CONTACT PHONE: _____
VEHICLE: _____
DESTINATION: _____
MAIN DIAGNOSIS: _____

17-00001

Tassica 3 Triage tag 17-00001

Figure 11 - Back of TASSICA 3 triage card (second triage or evacuation triage)

5.1.2.2. Crisis response planning

When a disaster strikes, the national civil protection authority of the affected country activates the necessary civil protection plans to manage the emergency response, requesting assistance from other EU countries if their response capacity is overwhelmed or needs to be reinforced. To ensure that assistance is provided where it is needed and to avoid duplication of relief efforts, it is essential that the EU response is coordinated. This coordination role is undertaken by the European Civil Protection Mechanism.

The operational core of the European Civil Protection Mechanism is the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC). This centre continuously monitors events around the world and coordinates the EU's disaster response efforts. The assistance that can be provided through this mechanism can be in the form of search and rescue operations, fighting forest and urban fires, deployment of medical personnel, medical supplies and medicines, water purification,

temporary emergency shelters or safe repatriation of EU citizens. In addition, the mechanism has a European Civil Protection Reserve; a voluntary pool of assets pre-allocated by member states for immediate deployment within or outside the EU.⁵

Any assistance arriving in a country is integrated into that country's civil protection system, forming part of the appropriate task force based on the functions defined in the civil protection plans. Key elements of the national disaster management system in the different EU countries, such as risk assessment, planning, emergency response, cross-border, European and international cooperation, are described below⁶.

AUSTRIA

Disaster management in Austria is a shared task between all levels of government (state, provinces (federal states) and municipalities). Disaster prevention is controlled at the national level by the responsible federal ministries in cooperation with the federal states and municipalities. Response rests with the federal states and is based on disaster response laws. These laws determine the declaration of disaster status and operational direction at municipal, district and federal state levels. Operational capacities are mainly provided by voluntary response organisations (fire brigades, red cross, mountain rescue etc.) acting as government services. At the national level, the responsibility for coordination lies with the ministry of interior through a national coordination committee. This ministry is also responsible for cross-border cooperation and international disaster relief.

Risk assessment is carried out at all levels of government. At the national level, 18 risk scenarios (11 natural and 8 anthropogenic) are considered. Pandemics and heat waves, power outages, floods and nuclear power plant accidents are considered relevant. Earthquakes and climate change effects are also considered.

Events to be managed at federal state level are not subject to national risk assessment.

With regard to planning, plans are drawn up at municipal, district and federal level on the basis of the risk assessment. For risks at the national level, national risk management policies exist and are governed by federal laws and regulations.

In relation to emergency response, most of the disaster response workforce is voluntary. Response plans exist in all municipalities, districts and federal entities. And for national scenarios, national response and contingency plans are in place.

They also have protection guidelines for different risks such as fire and radioactive incidents.

⁵ EU Civil Protection

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/es/policies/civil-protection/>

⁶ European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations. The national disaster management system.

https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/national-disaster-management-system_es

Austria maintains bilateral agreements on mutual assistance in case of disasters or major accidents with almost all neighbouring countries and several other states within and outside Europe. The Federal Ministry of the Interior is responsible for coordination in such cases.

BULGARIA

The national disaster management system in Bulgaria is regulated in the Disaster Protection Act which is implemented at national, regional and municipal level.

Risk management is based on several laws: Disaster Protection Act, Spatial Planning Act, Water Act, Environmental Protection Act, Safe Use of Nuclear Energy Act, Forestry Act and Regional Development Act.

Risk assessments are a mandatory part of regional and municipal plans. Risks assessed include earthquakes, floods, nuclear or radiation accident risk, geological disasters and forest fires.

Disaster risk reduction planning includes a national strategy, a national programme and sectoral, regional and municipal programmes.

Emergency response is organised through the Unified Rescue System which includes structures of ministries, municipalities, companies, volunteers and the armed forces.

Bulgaria, like all other EU countries, has several bilateral agreements with neighbouring countries.

CZECH REPUBLIC

Crises are defined as related or unrelated to the provision of Defence of the Czech Republic against external attacks. It is based on the Crisis Act which provides for 4 crisis states.

Regarding risk assessment, the country has documents (16) in the form of a checklist describing the emergency and appropriate measures to ensure an effective response.

The risk management capacity assessment includes floods, prolonged droughts and power outages.

Emergency response is carried out through an Integrated Rescue Service (IRS) that includes fire protection units, EMS providers and police. The performance of this service is set out in the Central Emergency Plan, according to which the governor, the mayor, the director of the regional fire brigade or the commander of the intervention, can request, through the operational and information centre of the regional integrated rescue system, assistance and resources not available in the regional rescue system. This document includes the deployment of the individual components of the IRS within the regions, the number of specialised equipment to be used, facilities, people and the time required to provide forces and resources.

In terms of cooperation, bilateral governmental agreements exist with neighbouring countries (Austria, Germany, Poland and Slovakia) and Hungary. These agreements specify joint training and education and mutual exchange of information.

DENMARK

The national crisis management system in Denmark serves to provide governmental coordination of incident response in Denmark or abroad. It is structured on three levels: state (ministries), regional and municipal. The Minister of Defence coordinates planning and sets guidelines for the preparation of plans by central government, regions, municipalities and municipal fire and rescue companies.

Risk assessment is carried out by the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) in close consultation with other authorities and organisations. The results are summarised in the National Risk Profile.

Regarding planning, in addition to the Emergency Management Act, risk management planning responsibilities are addressed in various plans, agreements and guidelines such as the National Emergency Plan, the Comprehensive Preparedness Planning guidelines and the National Strategy for Accident and Disaster Prevention.

The emphasis is on generic plans for all risks, focusing on crisis management regardless of scenarios.

In relation to emergency response, the fundamental principle is sector responsibility. That is, the authority or organisation responsible for a given area is also responsible for that area in the event of an emergency. There are fire and rescue services at municipal, regional and national level.

Denmark cooperates with international organisations in the EU, the UN, NATO, the Nordic countries, the Baltic Sea States and Germany. Procedures are in place in case assistance is required from another country.

ESTONIA

The risk management structure in Estonia is decentralised, with the government designating the authorities that are competent to manage each risk. The Ministry of the Interior establishes legislation in this area, coordinates emergency management and planning at national level.

Crisis committees are established at local, regional and national levels to oversee crisis management including emergency preparedness and response.

With regard to risk assessment, six main risks are considered: rescue, police, cyber, radiological/nuclear, health care and infectious animal disease.

Contingency plans are risk-based. These plans contain the mechanisms for inter-agency cooperation to develop the capacity to manage unforeseen or complex crises.

The emergency response system is based on a 4-tiered system (showing rescue capacity and resources) and 4 stages (determining the complexity of a rescue event). The emergency response depends on the Rescue Board which is based on professional and volunteer rescue teams and bomb squads.

Estonia has bilateral agreements with Finland and Sweden and a trilateral agreement with Latvia and Lithuania.

FINLAND

In Finland, rescue services operate under the Rescue Act and other similar laws. There are national services run by the Ministry of the Interior and regional services (which employ volunteer fire brigades).

In relation to risk assessment, the scenarios assessed include imposed threats to the stability of society, technology and logistics, as well as health security and large-scale accidents.

According to the Rescue Act, emergency preparedness planning and cooperation is the duty of the rescue services authorities. It is the Ministry of the Interior that coordinates the preparedness of these services, which are supported by the regional rescue departments.

Regarding emergency response, the emergency response centres (112) receive emergency calls for rescue, police, social services and health, and transmit the information to the relevant assistance authorities or partners.

The emergency response centre agency is under the Ministry of the Interior, and its management is carried out together with the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health.

Finland participates in international civil protection operations through the European Union and international organisations, in accordance with bilateral and multilateral international treaties.

GERMANY

Responsibility for disaster management in Germany is shared between the Federation and the federal states. The Federation is in charge of civil protection in the case of defence (times of war or armed conflict), while the federal states are responsible for disaster management in peacetime.

According to the Federal Law on Civil Protection and Disaster Response, the Federation conducts a nationwide risk analysis in cooperation with the federal states. The analysis of specific risks is complemented by the analysis of the federal states and local authorities.

At the national level, the following risks have been analysed: floods, extraordinary epidemics, winter storms, storm surges, release of radioactive substances from nuclear power plants, release of chemical substances, drought and earthquakes.

The national executive body responsible for civil protection is the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response.

Regarding emergency response, in the event of an incident, fire brigades and relief organisations form the operational and tactical units for immediate technical and medical assistance at the local level.

When requested to assist, the Federation can support local and regional authorities and federal states with its own operational forces and with services provided by the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance.

Germany has signed bilateral agreements on mutual disaster assistance with all its neighbouring states and the states of Belgium, Denmark, France, Lithuania, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Austria, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, the Czech Republic and Hungary.

GREECE

Civil protection in Greece is organised as a coordinated resource system in which national, regional and local authorities work together with local and public institutions and services. The coordinating body for planning and management is the General Secretariat for Civil Protection. In terms of risk assessment, the main risks identified are forest fires, earthquakes, floods and industrial accidents.

The National Civil Protection Plan establishes the national framework for effective risk management planning and provides for the development of scenario-specific plans at local, regional and national levels.

The General Secretariat for Civil Protection issues national plans and based on these, ministries, decentralised and local government authorities design their own.

The General Civil Protection Plan "Xenocrates":

- Identifies the services involved, the bodies and entities that direct and coordinate the operational forces at all levels
- Provides essential data for the assessment of the situation and risks, in order to draw up specific plans to deal with the risks in each case
- Guidelines are given for the formulation of strategies and tactics, for the appropriate organisation and equipping of services, for the timely mobilisation, activation, management and coordination of human resources and means
- It provides for the creation of logistics for dealing with the problems of both the operational forces and the citizens concerned
- The establishment of a communication and information flow system between the services involved and the crisis management actors

Regarding emergency response, depending on whether the disaster is general, regional or local, operational forces are deployed and coordinated by the relevant level.

Greece has bilateral agreements and/or memoranda of understanding with Bulgaria, Cyprus, France, Israel, Malta, the Russian Federation, Ukraine, the United States and Turkey.

There are regional, bilateral and multilateral agreements in different fields of civil protection such as technological and natural disaster risks, health and environment.

HUNGARY

In Hungary, the National Disaster Management Directorate General of the Ministry of the Interior is responsible for emergency planning and management.

Risk assessment is carried out at local level through disaster management departments, regional and national level through the Department of Defence Management.

Municipal and territorial emergency plans are drawn up and there is a central emergency plan.

The Department of Defence Management collects and processes information on emergency management, prepares proposals for decision-making and informs organisations involved in disaster management.

Regarding emergency response, the National Directorate General for Disaster Management (NDGDM) provides event-related information through the operation of a function and operations control system, and activates forces and assets necessary for liquidation. It carries out firefighting, technical rescue, protection, information and alerting of local authorities.

This Directorate General has an extensive international system of professional relations that can serve the internal and external interests of disaster management. The main areas of international relations are bilateral relations, regional relations, the EU system, the UN, NATO and international disaster management.

ICELAND

In Iceland, the supreme authority for civil protection is the Minister of Justice. Icelandic Search and Rescue (ICE-SAR) and the Red Cross are the backbone of civil protection.

The main risks are natural hazards: volcanic, earthquakes, floods, external weather, snow avalanches and landslides. Risk assessment is the responsibility of the National Police Commissioner/Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management.

Civil protection is structured in local districts and civil protection committees appointed by the local municipalities. The committees act in accordance with the Civil Protection Act.

In terms of planning, response plans are activated in three levels or phases (uncertainty, alert/danger and emergency/relief), each of which is identified with guidelines, speed of activation and scope.

The Department of Civil Protection runs a national coordination and crisis centre that coordinates and assists local crisis centres. The administrative levels of response are the on-scene command, the area command at local level and the national crisis coordination centre at national level.

In relation to cooperation, there is an agreement between the Nordic countries for cooperation during an emergency situation. Other international partnerships include HAGA, the Council of Baltic States, NATO and the UN.

ITALY

Law 24 February 1992, n. 225 establishes the National Civil Protection Service with the aim of protecting the integrity of life, property, settlements and the environment from damage or danger of damage resulting from natural disasters, catastrophes and other calamitous events.

The president of the Council of Ministers or, by his delegation, the minister for civil protection coordination promotes and coordinates the activities of the central and peripheral administrations of the State, regions, provinces, municipalities, national and territorial public

bodies and any other public and private institution and organisation present in the national territory.

In order to ensure the unified management and coordination of emergency activities, the Operational Committee for Civil Protection has been created. Its functions are:

- a) To examine the emergency plans drawn up
- b) To evaluate news, data and requests from the areas affected by the emergency
- c) To coordinate the interventions of all the administrations and entities involved in the rescue
- d) To coordinate the interventions of all the administrations and entities involved in the rescue
- e) Promote the implementation of directives issued in relation to the priority needs of the areas affected by the emergency.

The national operational structures of the National Civil Protection Service are:

- National Fire Brigade as a fundamental component of civil protection
- Armed Forces
- Police Forces
- Forestry Corps
- National technical services
- National scientific research groups, the National Institute of Geophysics and other research institutions
- Italian Red Cross
- Structures of the National Health Service
- Voluntary organisations
- National Alpine Rescue Corps-CNSA (CAI)

On the basis of the criteria determined by the National Council for Civil Protection, the operational structures, at the request of the Department for Civil Protection, carry out the activities provided for by the present law, as well as the tasks of support and advice to all the administrations that make up the National Civil Protection Service.

IRELAND

In Ireland, the agencies responsible for emergency response are the police force, the ambulance service, the fire service and the Irish coastguard.

At the national level, the government's working group on emergency planning coordinates and oversees emergency management activities.

With regard to risk assessment, at the national level this is carried out by the government working group with the support of academic involvement.

Also, at the national level there is an emergency coordination group (NECG) that liaises with local regional structures as necessary to respond to emergencies.

In relation to cooperation, there is a support guide for the main response agencies to address any problems that may arise in requesting, receiving and utilising any assistance or resources from outside the state by the main response agencies.

LATVIA

In Latvia, the national disaster management system is organised and regulated under the legislative framework of the Civil Protection and Disaster Management Act. It consists of state and local government authorities.

It is the state fire and rescue service that administers, coordinates and controls the functioning of the emergency planning system.

Regarding risk assessment, the State Fire and Rescue Service has developed recommendations for disaster risk assessment and a catalogue of potential hazards.

These assessments, developed by the responsible ministries, are incorporated into the state civil protection plan.

The authorities, taking into account the risk assessment and disaster management measures, develop and manage the implementation of various civil protection plans.

The Civil Protection and Disaster Management Act determines the subjects of disaster management and their area of responsibility for the coordination of disaster management.

In relation to cooperation, this is understood as civil-military assistance to allied forces and capabilities and organisations of the European Union and NATO, located, operating or transiting through the territory of Latvia as a host nation.

MALTA

In Malta, the management of natural and man-made emergencies is the responsibility of the civil protection department. During major incidents, the Civil Protection Council is the coordinating body that facilitates cooperation with other entities such as the Police Force, the Armed Forces, other government entities and civil society organisations.

The National Risk Assessment provides detailed information on major hazards such as earthquakes and tsunamis, hurricanes and floods, structural fires, epidemics and pandemics.

Each ministry within the government is responsible for structuring its prevention plans, while enhancing its framework of prevention-based operations and competencies.

With regard to emergency response, the Civil Protection Act sets out the duties of the Civil Protection department, which include helping to build the resilience of government entities, the public and other entities in the prevention, preparedness and response to identified disasters or incidents.

Malta has bilateral agreements and memoranda of understanding with several neighbouring states.

LUXEMBOURG

In Luxembourg, the Minister of the Interior is in charge of the organisation, coordination and implementation of civil security. Civil security is carried out by the Luxembourg Fire and Rescue Service (CGDIS).

The ministries and administrations are responsible for assessing the risks in their sectors and adopting appropriate strategies and actions.

The Ministry of the Interior develops the national rescue organisation plan which includes an analysis of technological and natural risks. The main risks identified are: cyber, terrorist, health, nuclear, risk of energy and water supply disruption and floods.

Major cross-border risks have also been identified such as disruption of communication and electricity systems, infectious diseases and industrial accidents.

Crises are managed at the national level on the basis of emergency response plans that are established for each major risk. These plans define the institutions dealing with the crisis, the process for alerting the authorities and providing information to the public, and define the emergency measures and associated actions, and the respective actors in charge.

Regarding the emergency response, the Fire and Rescue Corps leads the rescue operations and reports to the Minister of Interior. In case of a crisis with national impact, inter-agency coordination is led by the High Commissioner for Civil Protection.

In terms of cooperation, Luxembourg is in regular contact with the civil security, fire and rescue services of neighbouring countries. Bilateral agreements regulate mutual assistance in case of emergency or disaster in the border area, as well as mutual training or exchanges.

MONTENEGRO

The Directorate for Rescue and Protection, Ministry of Home Affairs, is in charge of rescue and risk management, disaster protection and emergency remediation management. This enables unified prevention, preparedness and response to natural, technical, technological and other disasters.

The Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction identified both natural disasters (geological hazards, hydro-meteorological and biological hazards and natural phenomena and hazards at sea) and technical-technological disasters (accidents at work and accidents in road transport of hazardous substances, railways and at sea, air traffic, nuclear and radiological, fires in public facilities and energy, air and chemical pollution).

The plans address different types of hazards and are established at three levels (national, local and corporate) and include preventive, operational and recovery measures to be carried out by protection and rescue actors.

Regarding emergency response, the management and coordination of protection and rescue activities are carried out by the Coordination and Rescue Team for the territory of Montenegro and the municipal protection and rescue teams. The coordination team includes all relevant ministries/municipal bodies and non-governmental organisations.

Montenegro has bilateral agreements on civil protection cooperation with Albania, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Greece, Slovakia, Ukraine, Slovenia, Serbia, Turkey, North Macedonia, Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. Memoranda of cooperation were signed between the Ministry of Interior of Montenegro and the competent institutions of Italy, Russia and Armenia.

NORTH MACEDONIA

Protection and rescue are organised as a single system regulated by the Law on Protection and Rescue, which indicates how responsibilities in this area are divided between the state, local authorities, public and private companies, facilities and services.

The Crisis Management Act regulates risk management from the local to the national level.

The risk assessment is carried out by the crisis management centre; it is a document of public interest and is drafted on the basis of the Crisis Management Act.

When a crisis is declared in the country, the crisis management centre is responsible for international communication and coordination with international institutions.

This centre developed a national platform with a database of national resources for cross-border operations. Related institutions declare their own capacities for international disaster response operations.

Regarding cooperation, North Macedonia has participated in several exercises, but has not been found in the referenced literature to have cooperation agreements or treaties.

POLAND

In Poland, the law on crisis management establishes the composition and functioning of the crisis management system and specifies the tasks to be performed by the state administration and territorial units of self-government at all levels.

The main crisis management authority is the Council of Ministers. In emergency situations, this responsibility rests with the Minister of Interior and Administration.

The main civil protection authority is the National Headquarters of the State Fire Service (KG PSP), which is subordinate to the Minister of the Interior and Administration.

Regarding risk assessment, the report on national security threats identifies approximately 50 risks that could have an impact at the national level.

The national crisis management plan is an initial document in the civilian planning process at central and regional level. There is also a national critical infrastructure protection programme.

In terms of emergency response, the national fire fighting and rescue system (KSRG) is a network of professional and volunteer rescue services, complemented by numerous agreements with agencies, associations and other entities. It is run by professional firefighters.

Poland has bilateral agreements with the following countries in the field of civil protection: Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia and Ukraine.

It also participates in the following multilateral disaster coordination systems: the European Union (EU), the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO) and the United Nations (UN).

PORTUGAL

The National Emergency Civil Protection Plan (PNEPC) is a support instrument for civil protection operations in the event of an imminent or occurring major accident or catastrophe in mainland Portugal, in order to enable unity of direction of the actions to be taken, technical and operational coordination of the resources to be deployed and the adequacy of exceptional measures to be adopted. As defined in the Basic Law on Civil Protection, this Plan is classified as general in purpose and national in scope.

The Director of the PNEPC is the Prime Minister, who will be replaced by the Minister of Internal Administration when he/she is absent or unavailable. The Director shall be responsible for directing, coordinating and controlling the PNEPC and the exceptional emergency measures, with a view to minimizing the loss of lives and property and the damage to the environment, as well as to re-establishing the minimum conditions for normality as soon as possible.

In this context, the PNEPC articulates directly with the Regional and District Civil Protection Emergency Plans and indirectly with the Municipal Civil Protection Emergency Plans, which describe at the respective territorial levels the action of the civil protection structures and refer to the responsibilities, the organizational mode and the concept of operation, as well as how to mobilize and coordinate the means and resources that are indispensable for the management of the relief. The PNEPC is also articulated with the National Operational Guidelines of the National Civil Protection Authority.

The PNEPC contemplates 18 main risks that can have a national impact, each with their subset of events, characterised through a hierarchy according to their relative risk, from forest fires to flooding, earthquakes, and NRBQ (nuclear, radiological, biological and chemical) perils.

REPUBLIC OF CROATIA

In the Republic of Croatia, the Ministry of the Interior is the central state body responsible for civil protection activities.

The Civil Protection Act defines the obligation to develop disaster risk assessment plans at national, regional and local level. Fifteen risk assessment plans have been developed (one per identified hazard). The most significant are earthquakes, floods and forest fires.

Risk management planning is defined in the Civil Protection System Law. There is a disaster risk reduction platform that will allow the planning of cross-sectoral projects and risk reduction measures.

Regarding emergency response, the Civil Protection Headquarters is an operational and coordinating body. It is established at the national level and at the level of local and county (regional) autonomous government units.

In terms of cooperation, the Republic of Croatia has signed 13 bilateral agreements (with Austria, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, France, Hungary, Montenegro, North Macedonia,

Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine) and 4 Memoranda of Understanding (with Israel, Italy, Kosovo, Netherlands).

The Civil Protection Directorate is involved in the provision of emergency and humanitarian assistance in the framework of NATO's EADRCC, the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and bilaterally.

REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS

In the Republic of Cyprus, the Minister of Interior coordinates the services and agencies declared essential for civil protection purposes. Therefore, the responsibility for civil defence lies with the Ministry of Interior.

There is a civil defence plan that defines the role, duties and responsibilities of all components of the civil defence system. Accordingly, each component of the system has to elaborate defence plans to cope with contingencies that may arise from natural hazards or man-made disasters.

With regard to risk assessment, the national report identifies the following: earthquake, tsunami, flash floods and urban flooding, sea level rise, maritime pollution, complex crises and cascading events, water shortages, large-scale technological accidents, forest fires, coastal erosion, climate change and soil desertification.

Planning is done through risk management plans that take into account the whole disaster cycle.

Specific national plans are prepared by the relevant services as agreed in the ZENON plan approved by the Council of Ministers. The plans foresee different levels of activation depending on the magnitude of the disaster. When the event is on a large scale, a special ministerial group is convened to coordinate measures.

The Cyprus Civil Defence, through the various action plans and specifically through an appendix to each national plan, undertakes to provide host nation support to all members of the teams/experts sent in the event of an emergency.

ROMANIA

In Romania, at the national level, the National Committee for Special Emergency Situations (CNSSU) is responsible for emergency management. At the strategic level, the Department for Emergency Situations (DSU) ensures and coordinates the human, material and other resources needed to deal with the emergency, including first aid and emergency medical assistance.

Regarding risk assessment, the main risks in Romania are: floods, droughts, forest fires, landslides, earthquakes, nuclear and radiological accidents, chemical accidents, major accident risks with collapse of buildings, installations and hazardous substances, epidemics, animal epidemics and zoonosis.

In relation to planning, the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations (IGSU) is the authorised body that develops the regulations in this field and is responsible for the supervision of public and private institutions as well as economic operators (private companies) that need to have contingency plans for the identified risks.

On emergency response, citizens in emergency situations can call 112, to request the assistance of services (ambulance, Mobile Emergency Resuscitation and Extrication Service, police, fire brigade, gendarmes).

Coordination between county and provincial inspectorate professionals ensures an efficient response.

In terms of cooperation, bilateral agreements concluded at governmental level are in force or under negotiation with neighbouring and other countries in the field of disaster prevention, preparedness and response.

SLOVAKIA

In Slovakia, the crisis management system is geographically divided and each level of public administration plays its role in the system.

The purpose of Law 42_194 on Civil Protection is to regulate the conditions for the effective protection of life, health and property from the consequences of emergencies, how to establish the roles and responsibilities of state administration bodies, autonomous regions, municipalities and the rights and obligations of natural and legal persons to ensure civil protection.

A comprehensive analysis of the territory of the Slovak Republic is regularly carried out at the national and regional level. Not at the local level. The competent authorities are the Ministry of Interior at the national level and the district offices at the regional level.

Regarding planning, the Ministry of Interior manages and develops annual plans in the field of civil protection (preventive, crisis and escalation action plans etc.). The most common example is the flood plan.

In relation to emergency response, local authorities have the main responsibility in case of an emergency on their territory. The mayor of the affected municipality is the head of rescue operations, the district head is responsible for the response at district and regional level. Emergency response is carried out by first responders who are coordinated by the Integrated Rescue System, which consists of the Fire and Rescue Service; the Emergency Medical Service; the Mountain Rescue Service; the Mine Rescue Service; the Chemical Control Laboratories, which are supported by local, corporate and volunteer fire brigades; the Armed Forces of the Slovak Republic, the Slovak Red Cross and other civil protection units.

An agreement exists between the Ministry of Interior and the Slovak Red Cross on the basis of mutual benefit. Mutual cooperation will be mainly in the field of humanitarian aid and dissemination of international humanitarian law, blood donation, education and training.

In the field of mutual assistance in the event of natural disasters and major technological accidents, the priority focused on mutual cooperation with the Slovak Republic's neighbouring countries. To this end, bilateral agreements (contracts) were concluded with the Czech Republic, the Republic of Hungary, the Republic of Poland, the Republic of Austria and Ukraine. The other European countries have similar agreements with the Republic of Croatia, the Russian Federation and the Republic of Slovenia. In the period before accession to the European Union, the Slovak Republic, as a candidate country, signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the

European Community on the participation of the Slovak Republic in the Community Mechanism to facilitate enhanced cooperation in civil protection assistance interventions. With the accession of the Slovak Republic to the European Union, it is its duty not only to implement the tasks arising from legislative acts adopted at the level of the European Union, but also, as a full member, to co-decide on concrete civil protection actions within the European Union.

There is an agreement on cooperation and mutual assistance between Slovakia and Austria. This agreement regulates the conditions of cooperation and voluntary provision of assistance in the event of a disaster on the territory of the other country (e.g. Slovakia or Austria) at the request of the other country, in particular the conditions of dispatch and deployment of assistance units or individuals dispatched to provide assistance and material.

Assistance will be provided through the dispatch of assistance units or individuals dispatched to provide assistance, the dispatch of assistance material or other appropriate means.

Assistance units or individuals dispatched to provide assistance may be deployed to carry out rescue and recovery work, to deal with the consequences of disasters, as well as to avert the threat of disasters. They must have the necessary training and equipment.

Transport of relief units or individuals sent for assistance, equipment and relief items may be by land, water or air.

SLOVENIA

Disaster management (civil protection) in Slovenia is organised as an integrated system that includes several parts: rescue units and services (professional and voluntary, civil protection), humanitarian organisations, research institutions, other organisations and government administrative bodies.

The national authority responsible for disaster management is under the Ministry of Defence.

Risk assessments are carried out at ministerial and local self-government community level, with a coordinating body at national level (Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief (ACPD)).

There are 15 individual risk assessments (for earthquakes, floods, health threats of biological, chemical, environmental and unknown origin, particularly dangerous animal diseases, nuclear or radiological emergencies, railway accidents, air accidents, major forest fires, terrorism, drought, sleet, accidents related to hazardous substances, accidents at sea, cyber risks, forest tree diseases and pests, and a national disaster risk assessment).

Risk management planning is carried out with an integrated cross-sectoral approach. National response plans are in place for earthquakes, floods, airplane crashes, railway accidents, nuclear or radiological emergencies, major forest fires, massive outbreaks of highly dangerous animal diseases, large-scale contagious diseases in humans, terrorist attacks with weapons or means of mass destruction or conventional means.

With regard to emergency response, command and operational coordination takes place at different levels. In cases of minor accidents, commanders of individual protection and rescue units lead the response (incident commanders).

The management of the response in major accidents or disasters is in the hands of the civil protection commanders and their staff at the municipal or regional level. In case of major disasters, the Civil Protection Commander of the Republic of Slovenia manages the response and is directly responsible to the government. He is assisted by the Civil Protection Headquarters, which consists of members of the respective ministries, experts in different fields and heads of different protection and rescue units.

SPAIN

In Spain, the Ministry of the Interior is the highest authority in charge of Civil Protection. Emergency situations involve the mobilisation of human and material resources. These belong to the public administrations - national, autonomous and local - together with public institutions, private entities and citizens.

The Autonomous Communities are responsible for the management and coordination of emergencies in their territory, unless they are declared a national emergency.

With regard to risk assessment, the Directorate General for Civil Protection and Emergencies set up a working group with all interested parties that agreed on the methodology for risk assessment. This risk assessment is reviewed periodically.

In terms of planning, the public administrations develop CP plans according to their competences in the field of civil protection foreseen in the law. Thus, there is a state plan, territorial plans at the level of autonomous community or municipality, special plans for specific risks (floods, earthquakes, chemical and radiological emergencies, transport of dangerous goods, forest fires, volcanic eruptions, tsunamis, biological emergencies and air crashes), and self-protection plans. The State is always responsible for the management of nuclear emergencies and war situations.

Three emergency situations or levels are established depending on the civil protection plan that needs to be activated (local, regional, national). This depends on the type of emergency and whether the local or regional resources are sufficient to deal with the situation.

Spain has bilateral civil protection assistance and cooperation agreements with Algeria, France, Morocco, Russia, Portugal and Tunisia.

SWEDEN

Disaster management in Sweden is based on an all-hazards approach and responsibility lies at national, regional and local levels.

National risk assessment is a continuous process that identifies anthropogenic, natural and biological hazards. There are others that can have catastrophic consequences such as a radiological event, a dam breach or a pandemic.

Risk planning and funding is included in the budgets of public sector agencies.

With regard to emergency response, both municipalities and county administrative boards have responsibilities within their geographical areas. At the local level rescue services etc. are maintained and at the county level regional coordination takes place.

Sweden is extensively involved in international cooperation in various fields.

5.1.2.3. Standards and methodology

This landscape analyses the principal tools or standards methodologies used for reconnaissance, triage for first aid response in emergency departments to evaluate the severity of incoming patients' conditions and assign treatment priorities.

The first part of an emergency is the reconnaissance of the victims of the any disaster. Reconnaissance and triage combined as part a system allows to evaluate the status of any victim and develop the tasks needed to save their life as soon and better is possible. As we see after, it depends of triage system choose the first reconnaissance and triage actions could be different.

The triage protocols are used by dispatch centres, ambulance services and In-hospital so the actors are similar but with differences and that make necessary to work in a standard for triage. Each of them uses triage protocols, standardized at national level and computerized recording⁷ associated to triage. Nowadays, the emergency departments use different triage systems, some of which are⁸:

- Australian Triage Scale (ATS)
- Canadian Triage and Acuity Scale (CTAS)
- Manchester Triage System (MTS)
- Emergency Severity Index (ESI)
- Sistema Estructurado de Triage (SET)

These 5-levels triage systems, each of which are related to an assessment and treatment schedule and the emergency department resources available at the time, so are safe and reliable so would be interesting to take common decision about which system would be preferred by Valkyries context. Some points to reach that decision are:

- Consider need of each emergency department
- Make a collaborative decision among all participants
- Deployment of specific training for professionals
- Evaluation about cost to modify or adapt current triage system to apply unique triage system for each Valkyrie team member

There is no gold rule to choose the best triage standard so each sanitary service of each country should review each characteristic and take a decision about which is preferred and make better all sanitary services of all countries.

⁷ https://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0003/114564/E92039.pdf

⁸ Christ M, Grossmann F, Winter D, Bingisser R, Platz E. Modern triage in the emergency department. Dtsch Arztebl Int. 2010;107(50):892-898. doi:10.3238/arztebl.2010.0892 . <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3021905/>

Sistemas de Triage	Lugar	Niveles de prioridad
<i>Korean Triage And Acuity Scale (KTAS)</i>	Corea	5
<i>Medical Emergency Triage and Treatment System (METTS)</i>	Suecia	5
<i>Echelle Liégeoise D'Index de Sévérité à L'Admission (ELISA)</i>	Francia	5
<i>Classification Infirmière des Malades aux Urgences o French Emergency Nurses Classification in Hospital Scale</i>	Francia	6
<i>Netherlands Triage System (NTS)</i>	Holanda	5
<i>Taiwan Triage and Acuity Scale (TTAS)</i>	Taiwán	4
<i>Clinical Gps (cGPs)</i>	Estados Unidos	5
<i>Swiss Emergency Triage Scale (SETS)</i>	Suecia	4
<i>South African Triage Scale (SATS)</i>	Sudáfrica	5
<i>The Soterion Rapid Triage System</i>	Estados Unidos	5
<i>One-Two-Triage (OTT)</i>	Estados Unidos	4
<i>CLARIPED</i>	Brasil	5
<i>Emergency Triage Assessment and Treatment (ETAT)</i>	Suiza	3
<i>Sistema de Triage 3M TAS</i>	España	5

Table 3 - Other triage systems⁹

From the crisis and disaster have different definitions related to causative factors, so the crisis is related to possible self-inflicted situations and the disasters can't be expected (earthquake, i.e.). The emergency planning is very important preparedness activity as it builds the community response system.

The crisis management should be considered like a continuous process of several activities:

- Crisis prevention
- Crisis preparation
- Crisis coping
- Crisis aftermath

The continuous management of these part try to build resilience for crisis and disasters.

5.1.3. Landscape

The questionnaire developed for this WP5 included five thematic categories of which two relate to this section "Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning".

These categories are "Crisis response planning" and "First aid operations".

In "Crisis response planning" the following aspects have been consulted on:

- Multi-casualty incidents or disaster situations in which your service might be involved (local, regional, inter-regional, national, transnational).
- Types of territorial crisis response plans: whether they exist and of what type (local, regional, inter-regional, national, transnational)
- Standardization at national level of the territorial crisis response plan
- Existence of a crisis response plan for specific hazards: B, A, climatological, geological, human, hydrological, N, technological, terrorism, other.
- Existence of a crisis response plan for other specific hazards.
- Standardization at national level of crisis response plans for specific hazards
- Availability of an emergency crisis operations centre
- Emergency agencies involved: rescuers, firefighters, EMS, police, army, civil protection, Red Cross, others.
- Other emergency agencies involved
- Which agency is responsible for activating the plan
- Whether other agencies also have responsibility for activating the plan
- Incident categorization criteria if included in the crisis response plan (number of casualties, type of risk, severity, extent)
- National standardization of the incident categorization criteria
- Elements that are included in the crisis response plan (plan activation criteria, activation procedure, hazard mapping/listing, resource mapping/listing, warning and alert planning, evacuation planning, assessment planning, shelter planning, operational planning, plan demobilization criteria, training planning, plan review planning)
- Needs/shortcomings in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

Under "First aid operations" the following aspects have been consulted:

- Availability of crisis operating procedure
- Whether the available procedure is standardized at the national level
- Availability of an operational procedure for specific hazards
- Existence of another hazard-specific procedure
- Whether the procedure for specific hazards is standardized at the national level
- Existence of a unified inter-agency crisis operating procedure (including different services and indicate which ones)
- Agency responsible on scene for:
 - Hazard control
 - Zoning
 - Access control

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- Ambulance registration and tracking responsibility
- Casualty registration and tracking
- Treatment triage
- Victims' stretcher carrying
- Casualty stabilization
- Evacuation triage
- Evacuation control
- Determining the patient's destination hospital
- Unified treatment triage procedure
- Unified evacuation triage procedure
- Needs/shortcomings existing in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

The questionnaires were answered by first-response partners from the consortium, the EAB and the related projects, as well as by EU and EEA emergency services.

Following the general picture described in the state of the art and the analysis of the questionnaires/surveys during the implementation of WP5 of the Valkyries project, the picture on operational planning/workflows/roles and practices engaged between the different countries is the following.

Items	Most common answers in the survey	Homogeneity between countries
Type of MCI o disaster potentially involved	Regional = Cross-regional > Local = National > Cross-national	High
Territorial Crisis Response Plan Types, if available	National > Regional > Local = Cross-regional > Cross-national	High
Territorial crisis response plan standardized at national level?	Yes	High
Hazard-specific crisis response plan, if available	Chemical > Biological = Hydrological = Geological > Climatological = Human > Radiological > Technological = Terrorism > Nuclear	High
Hazard-specific crisis response plan standardized at national level?	No	Medium
Crisis Emergency Operations Centre Available	Yes	Very high
Involved Emergency Agencies	EMS = Police > Firefighters > Civil Protection > Rescuers > Red Cross = Army	High

Items	Most common answers in the survey	Homogeneity between countries
Plan Activation Responsibility (Agency)	Civil Protection > Police > Firefighters = EMS > Rescuers > Red Cross	Very high
Incident Categorization Criteria, if included in Crisis Response Plan	By type of hazard > By extent > By severity = By number of victims	Medium
Incident Categorization Criteria standardized at national level?	Yes	Medium
Items included in Crisis Response Plan	Plan Activation Procedure = Alert and Warning Planning > Resources Mapping / List = Plan Activation Criteria = Evacuation Planning > Hazard Mapping / List > Operational Planning > Plan Training Planning > Sheltering Planning = Plan Demobilization Criteria > Evaluation Planning = Plan Review Planning	High

Table 4 - WP5 questionnaire: Planning answers

The data obtained in the surveys on the planning part of crisis response are analyzed through the graphs shown below.

Regarding to the existence of crisis response plans, it is observed that most of the plans are national and regional in scope. It should be noted that there is a high percentage of agencies that could be involved in transnational crises that are part of national response plans and a small percentage that are also part of transnational plans.

Figure 12 – Territorial Crisis Response Plan Types according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

On the availability of crisis response plans for specific hazards, the most common are chemical, biological, hydrological and geological risk plans.

Figure 13 – Available Hazard-Specific Crisis Response Plans according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

The chart below shows the agencies involved in response plans, the most common being police, EMS, firefighters and civil protection. There are no major differences depending on whether or not these agencies are involved in cross national crises.

Figure 14 – Involved Emergency Agencies according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Regarding which agency is responsible for the activation of response plans, in most cases the responsible agency is civil protection, especially in transnational crises.

Figure 15 – Plan Activation Responsibility (Agency) according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

On what criteria are used to categorise incidents, the most common is the type of hazard followed by the number of victims.

Figure 16 – Incident Categorization Criteria according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Finally, with regard to the items included in crisis response plans, the most common are warning and alert planning, activation procedure, resource mapping/listing, plan activation criteria and evacuation planning.

Figure 17 – Items included in the Crisis Response Plan according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Service Crisis Operational Procedure Availability	Yes	Very high
Service Crisis Operational Procedure Standardized at national level	Yes	Medium
Hazard-Specific Operational Procedures, if available	Biological> Chemical= Geological> Hydrological> Climatological> Radiological=Nuclear= Terrorism=Human> Technological	High
Hazard-Specific Operational Procedure Standardized at national level	Yes	Medium

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Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Unified cross-agency crisis operational procedure availability	Firefighter>EMS=Civil Protection>Police>Army>Rescuers	High
On scene hazard control responsibility (Agency)	Firefighters> Police> Civil Protection=EMS>Rescuers=Red Cross	Very high
Zonation responsibility (Agency)	Firefighters> Police> Civil Protection>EMS=Rescuers	Very high
On scene access control responsibility	Police>Firefighter=Army>Rescuers	Very high
On scene ambulances registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Rescuers>Firefighter=Civil Protection	Very high
On scene victims' registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Police>Firefighter=Rescuers>Civil Protection	Very high
On scene treatment triage responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Firefighter>Rescuers	Very high
Treatment triage procedure unified	EMS>Firefighter>Red Cross>Rescuers=Army>Civil Protection	Very high
On scene victim's stretcher carrying responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Firefighter>Rescuers>>Civil Protection=Red Cross>Army	Very high
On scene victimsstabilization responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Firefighter>Rescuers	Very high
On scene evacuation triage responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Firefighter>Civil Protection>Rescuers=Police=Army	Very high
Evacuation triage procedure unified	EMS>Firefighter>Civil Protection>Rescuers=Police=Army=Rec Cross	Very high
On scene evacuation control responsibility (Agency)	EMS>Firefighter>Police>Civil Protection>Army	Very high
Responsibility to determine the destination hospital of the patient (Agency)	EMS>Rescuers=Civil Protection=Red Cross	Very high

Table 5 - WP5 questionnaire: Reconnaissance and triage answers

The data obtained from the surveys on first aid operations are analysed in the following graphs.

On the availability of hazard-specific operational procedures, the most common, as well as response plans, are for biological, chemical, hydrological and geological hazards.

Figure 18 – Hazard-Specific Operational Procedure

In relation to the availability of a unified and inter-institutional crisis operating procedure, all the agencies consulted have one, especially the police, fire brigade and civil protection.

Figure 19 – Unified cross-agency crisis operational procedure according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

In relation to which agency is responsible at the scene of the emergency for certain functions, it should be noted that for all actions related to victim assistance (first and second triage, stabilisation, evacuation, stretcher-bearing, registration and tracking of victims and ambulances, and choice of destination hospital), the responsible agency is the EMS. In contrast, the agency responsible for access control is the police, and in the case of hazard control and zoning, the agency most involved is the firefighters.

Figure 20 – On scene responsibility agency

Regarding the existence of a unified triage procedure, both for treatment and evacuation, the agency that mostly has a unified triage procedure is the health agency, the EMS.

Figure 21 – Treatment triage procedure unified according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Figure 22 – Evacuation triage procedure unified according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

In addition to the surveys, information has been collected on the crisis management plans and operational procedures of the European countries in which the use cases will be carried out, in order to compare certain relevant aspects that could highlight opportunities for harmonisation and thus complement the data obtained in the questionnaires.

With regard to crisis management plans, all countries have them in place at the different administrative levels, which makes it possible to plan the response to disasters according to certain parameters such as the extent of the emergency, its severity, the number of victims, the associated risks, etc. There are differences in the degree of implementation and monitoring of the plans.

These crisis plans include where the centre of operations is established, which agencies make up the different action groups and what their functions are, etc. There are organisational differences due to the structure of the country's civil protection system, but they all follow a common outline.

With regard to operational procedures, there is no homogeneity. There are countries where there is an operational procedure for victim care at national level, while in others these procedures depend on the regions. And in some cases, there is no procedure that allows emergency medical services to work in a regulated manner, although in all countries the different actions to be carried out in victim assistance are defined, as well as the agency responsible for each action.

5.1.4. Perception of needs

Respondents have reflected in their answers a number of needs, among which the most important are the following:

- In relation to crisis response plans, the perception is that there is a lack of adequate implementation of such plans. The implementation of a plan implies a process of dissemination among those involved, education and training, as well as that the different emergency services draw up specific procedures for carrying out the actions entrusted to them in the plan. On the other hand, the plans must be maintained, which means that they must be reviewed and updated.

- In terms of procedures, the unification and connection between emergency bodies must be improved. Coordination between different institutions and between neighbouring regions is essential.
- The need for regular education and training of first responders.

5.2. Maintenance, logistics and Deployment

5.2.1. Introduction

For the provision of relief and assistance to victims of catastrophes, the only way to supply management can be used thought logistic. Unfortunately, there are no standard models, for using supply management to provide relief and assistance to people affected.

Characteristics of the supply chain in major disasters. The amount of goods that must be handled and transported could be really abundant, given the vast geographical area and number of people affected by the cataclysm. Typically, hundreds of tons of material must be transported and distributed, especially in the form of water, food, temporary accommodation, electric generators, medical supplies, cribs, blankets, tarps and clothing. Some of these items (for example accommodation) fall into the "one-time demand" category (question asked only once), while others are recurring (for example water) (Haghani e Afshar, 2009). Demand usually overwhelms the capacity of the distribution network (such as ports, highways or airports). The transport centres, in fact, have to withstand a flow of material that is much greater than their normal capacities (Balcik et al. 2010). Overloading these centres could not only delay the distribution of goods, but also increase the risk of loss or delivery errors. Another reason that undermines the transport network in emergency situations is the supply by donors of superfluous goods that are not required and not necessary for a specific type of disaster. For example, short-term food or clothing that is not suitable for the climate and season in which the catastrophe occurred (Murray, 2005). Different humanitarian organizations may employ their own unique supply chain structure, which governs the various types of facilities and warehouses used and the relationships between the components of the chain. For example FEMA has its own supply chain for disaster response and boasts 7 levels of facilities in its supply chain^[1]:

1. Safety and security
2. food water, sheltering
3. health and medical
4. energy (power and fuel)
5. communications
6. transportation
7. hazardous material

The first 3 are characterized by permanent structures for storing and shipping items, while the remaining 4 by structures used for temporary transfer, the number and location of which will be chosen during the response phase. Temporary relocation facilities are created to receive, organize and ship relief products through the distribution network. Each structure in the chain is subject to some capacity constraints. The latter are defined for the operations of sending, receiving and storing raw materials. These capacities are different for each plant and are determined based on the type, size, layout and availability of personnel and equipment. In general, capacity limitations can be defined in terms of the weight or volume of goods or in terms of the number of vehicles that are sent, received or parked at the facility in a given time

unit. These are two different aspects, both of which are very important for assessing the capacity of a plant. Transportation capacity is usually very limited in the first hours or days after a disaster.

In the field of emergency management can be summarized on three phases: **preparation**, **response** phases (which mainly involve planning activities) and **reconstruction**.

The preparation phase is characterized by activities that make it possible to deal effectively and promptly with disastrous events. It includes the development of immediate disaster response procedures, the design and installation of alarm systems, evacuation plans, drills to test emergency operations, and personnel training. A well-planned and studied preparation phase makes it possible to significantly contain and stem the consequences of a calamitous event. Let us take, for example, the two earthquake cases that occurred in Turkey and Japan; both countries were hit by a 7.2 magnitude earthquake, but while in the first case there were over 100,000 victims, in the second "only" 12 people lost their lives. The reason for this huge difference lies in proactivity. As Japan is frequently hit by devastating earthquakes, its buildings and infrastructure are reinforced to withstand earthquakes of this size. In Turkey, however, there has not been the same proactive approach to mitigate the effects of earthquakes.

Response entails ensuring that the necessary data and processes are in place. When faced with a developing catastrophe, such as the discovery of a wildfire, earthquakes, utilities must have the essential information infrastructure. This data must be available at all times in order to conduct a coordinated and well-planned reaction utilizing existing apps and analytics. Comprehensive situational awareness dashboards with real-time data streams are among them. When damage occurs, they must create real-time damage assessments, deploy mobile resources to monitor progress, and manage information flow. Finally, in order to minimize disturbance during the event, utilities must be able to assure a safe and equitable work plan.

Reconstruction is the action of rebuilding and recover. When an event expires, there may be obstacles such fallen wires, trees or bridges obstructing traffic. The recovery effort is rapid assimilation of data and close coordination to recovery all the utilities.

Figure 23 - Effects of crisis management, Natarajathinam 2009

The problems are mainly of three types:

Facility Location Problem (FLP): consists in deciding where to locate new plants (for example factories, warehouses or distribution centres) to facilitate the flow of material, through an efficient distribution system. In general, this problem can be defined as follows: for a given number of potential sites for establishments capable of serving a given number of customers, find which sites to select and for each determine which customers they should serve, in order to minimize the total cost. The development and acquisition of a new factory is typically a time-consuming and expensive process. For this reason it is first necessary to identify the optimal location and determine its capacity requirements (Hagani and Aftar, 2009).

Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP): is a generic name attributed to an entire class of problems in which a series of routes must be determined, for a given fleet of vehicles (assigned to one or more depots), for a certain number of cities or geographically distant customers. The VRP stands as a central problem in the field of transport, distribution and logistics. Usually, the goal of the VRP is to serve a given number of customers (whose demand is known) through routes that minimize the total cost of transportation (or distance). The point of origin coincides with that of destination; the fleet of vehicles, in fact, carry out the collection / delivery programs envisaged through a circular route that ends at the departure depot. The use of these models allows savings on the total travel costs, which oscillate between 5% and 20 (Hagani and Aftar, 2009).

Inventory Planning: managing stocks means checking the quantities available in the warehouse and deciding when and when how much to order, trying at the same time to minimize total costs and guarantee a satisfactory level of service. This can be done using inventory management models, i.e. simplified representations of reality through mathematical functions: that is, an objective function is constructed (which represents the overall cost of managing the warehouse, given by the sum of the procurement and maintenance costs of stocks), which must be minimized, determining the quantity of goods to be ordered for each supply, the number of orders to be made in a given period of time and the time between orders.

Figure 24 - Percentage of the model examined: (Facility Location Problem (FLP), Vehicle Routing Problem, Inventory Planning) as a function of the problem posed.

5.2.1.1. Emergency supplies design

Emergency supplies are those goods, materials and equipment used by organizations to meet the essential needs of people affected by disasters. These supplies cover a broad spectrum, from food, medicine and clothing to emergency equipment, electric generators, construction materials and tools. As mentioned earlier, these products come from different places. Some are procured by organizations in response to specific needs assessed at the impact site; most, however, are the fruit of the spontaneous solidarity of the national and international community. From the point of view of origin, the articles can be classified into two categories:

1. Those requested or acquired by organizations, based on the respective intervention profiles (medical, economic, reconstructive) and on the needs of the affected population
2. Those which correspond to the fruit of solidarity from the rest of the country or the world, but which do not necessarily satisfy local needs. Often they do not have a specific recipient and their management is the responsibility of the national emergency authorities, which identify the assets, their characteristics and conditions; the authorities must also assign a use to the supplies, select the recipients and coordinate the delivery

Categories based on the experience of many humanitarian organizations operating around the world and the hundreds of emergencies they have faced, it is possible to determine in advance what supplies and items may be needed. The World Health Organization (WHO) has adopted a standard classification that divides emergency supplies into 10 different categories. This form of

identification is particularly useful for sorting and registering products. The categories are as follows:

1. Medicines
2. Water and environmental health
3. Sanitary kits
4. Food
5. Shelters / Temporary Accommodation / Buildings / Electrical Equipment
6. Logistics / Administration
7. Personal Needs
8. Human resources

5.2.1.2. Engineering and planning of logistics activities

Logistics and emergency although the word "logistics" was originally used to define military procedures for the procurement, maintenance and transport of materials, structures and, today it finds practical application in the industrial field. It generally refers to a system, whose parts interact easily to achieve a goal effectively thanks to an optimized use of resources. Such an approach provides very profitable results, but it has a negative aspect: the failure of even one component of this system can irreversibly affect all the others, compromising the final result.

Logistic planning is a key component to reduce the impact of a potential disaster. All activities must be reasoned and planned, as adequate preparations are essential for the smooth conduct of emergency operations. It is necessary to abandon the idea that transport and other arrangements can be improvised. Preparation is, therefore, a necessary element, as it is generally possible to predict the occurrence of a disaster, the place where it will strike, in what intensity and consequently the various needs that this disaster will give rise to. Logistics, in fact, should be an active component of every national emergency response plan, as well as of the individual plans of the various organizations and fundamental institutions, such as schools and health care. Logistics must be strictly connected to all other operational activities in an emergency context. Planning and anticipation are therefore essential for the logistics system. The plan must be based, first of all, on a good knowledge of the geographical, political and social characteristics of the area where the emergency operations take place. This plan must not only be organized in advance, but must, above all, be understood and accepted by all the actors involved. It must provide clear answers to the following questions:

- What are the duties and tasks that need to be done? How do they relate to all other activities and what is the sequence of implementation?
- Who will be responsible for carrying out these tasks? (We mean organization or department, not individuals).
- Who will be responsible for the overall coordination of the logistics system?
- What resources are needed? How, when and where can they be found?
- What alternative actions can be taken if the system is disrupted? Once these questions have been clearly answered, it is possible to proceed with the drafting of a list of preparatory activities.

The greater the time and energy that is invested in these activities, the greater the return in terms of knowledge of the global theatre of operations, weaknesses, possible needs and alternative solutions according to the various scenarios. Preparation must also be based on

vulnerability and resource assessments. These assessments are carried out to develop a regional or national emergency response plan and logistics must be a basic component of each plan.

5.2.1.3. Vulnerability assessment of key infrastructures

The goal is to identify the strengths and weaknesses of public works and strategic structures in the region or country (highways, water systems, schools, hospitals) and alternative actions that may be required following a collapse of such infrastructures. The evaluation approach must take place in accordance with local conditions, but it certainly includes the following activities: Systematically map and evaluate national transport infrastructures (ports, airports, motorways, railways, etc.), taking into consideration the capacities and potential weaknesses of strategic pathways, of any bottlenecks, of the availability of communication resources and of the risks for infrastructures in the event of an emergency. It is essential to determine the vulnerability of ports and airports to natural disasters. Consider, for example, the exposure of hangars and warehouses or equipment intended for refuelling or loading, to the devastating impacts of an earthquake or hurricane.

Analyse the historical meteorological data of the region or country to assess the impact that bad weather could have on the capacity of the transport system at different times of the year.

Regularly monitor new construction or changes to existing structures, which could cause bottlenecks or the temporary need to find new routes, such as changes in the weight of a bridge or width restrictions, closure of a route due to repairs roads, etc.

Determine the availability of strategic resources for logistical support these resources are constantly changing, therefore they must be frequently reviewed and analysed, so that the information is always as up-to-date as possible. The review of these resources involves both the public and private sectors.

Establish a nationwide inventory of locations and sources of key supplies, such as medicines, medical equipment, food, clothing, fuel and other emergency equipment. Furthermore, it is necessary to consider, based on the position of such critical goods, the estimated delivery times to the points of destination where such emergency supply may be required. Analyse in detail the capacity of the transport system for the movement of people and supplies; that is, to evaluate potential sites for logistic bases, distribution centres and refuelling points. This assessment includes public and private facilities, large storage complexes, factories and other facilities that can be adapted for these purposes. Assess the availability of spare parts and repair services, including private and public workshops. Determine the capacity of ports and airports to manage emergency supplies under various scenarios: Ports: examine the capacity of port facilities to manage the arrival, storage and flow of shipments. Review with the port authorities the various procedures and formalities for a correct management of incoming flows of emergency material, etc. Airports: determine their capacity, which types of aircraft can land, which services are offered, availability of equipment and equipment for loading and unloading activities, availability of refuelling points, etc. Other Transportation Options: Determine alternative routes and options, such as waterways, in the event of an emergency.

To facilitate the identification of the contents, they should be marked with symbols and colours that international organizations currently use to recognize the various categories of articles:

- Green for medicines and medical equipment

- Red for food
- Blue for domestic material and clothing
- Yellow for equipment and tools

Each package must be correctly labelled and indicate the characteristics of the content ("fragile", "dangerous", "flammable", "fresh", etc.). Packages belonging to the same lot should be numbered "x of y", where "y" is the total number of packages in the lot. This makes it easier to check the quantities of the various packages arriving at a sorting centre. It is useful and advantageous, depending on the means of transport adopted, to reduce the weight and bulk of the packaging material as much as possible. Goods arrival and sorting centres are rarely equipped with loading, unloading and handling systems, such as, for example, forklifts. For this reason it is important that the packages have reasonable weight, volume and shape, so that they can be handled manually, without having to resort to the use of mechanical devices.

5.2.1.4. Storage procedures within the warehouses

A fundamental rule in warehouse management is never to store different categories of products together on the same pallet, on the same shelf or stack. In particular, hazardous materials should not be kept in stock together with food or other products for human use or consumption. Similarly, there are other important factors to take into consideration when planning the use of space, for example:

- Similarity and quantity: products of the same type should be stored together, not in several places within the same warehouse
- Demand: Items that are handled most frequently should be placed in areas that have the best accessibility
- Measurements and weights: the largest and heaviest packages must be kept low; the smaller and lighter ones stacked on top of the heavy ones or in the higher shelves
- Characteristics: it is necessary to keep in mind the particular characteristics of the goods, such as their index of danger to human health, their fragility, sensitivity to light and humidity, their perishable nature, etc.

The items must be stored by sectors, according to their type. To avoid humidity problems, the products must never be in contact with the ground or walls. In fact, the interposition of pallets or special platforms is necessary. This is also to allow handling and lifting by any forklift trucks. The maximum permitted storage heights are equally important, which vary according to the strength of the packaged materials, crates or cages and to prevent obstruction of ventilation and lighting. If the room is equipped with shelving, these should be arranged so that there is sufficient space between the corridors to allow easy freedom of movement for both staff and any trolleys intended for lifting and handling materials. Height and arrangement of the shelving must be made in accordance with the handling and lifting systems available to the storage site and the heating and air circulation systems. The stock rotation will be based on a "first in first out" logic: the items remaining longer in the warehouse must be positioned in the first rows of the shelves so that they can be distributed first, while the items arriving later must be allocated in the rearmost rows, sliding forward as the deliveries of the products in front of them are made. The same principle is applied for goods characterized by an expiration date.

All safety and quality standards related to the procedures for control, monitoring, storage and handling of goods, both inbound and outbound, must be correctly applied. For this purpose, the personnel assigned to these activities must be properly trained or, even better, with qualifications and experience in the sector. A control and registration system for each type of product should ideally be available, even better if computerized, which keeps track of what, when and how much enters and leaves the warehouse, as well as the positions / sectors in which the various items are kept in stock.

Types of transport and their characteristics the existing means of transport are different and have, from the point of view of operational needs, both advantages and disadvantages, in terms of costs, capacity and speed of transport. There are two issues that need to be considered when deciding which means of transport to use: what is really needed and the possible forms of transport.

Needs: what goods are urgently needed? What kind of goods must be transported? With what weights and dimensions? What is the destination? How much distance must be covered?

Possible forms of transport: what means of transport are available? How much do they cost? Given the weather conditions and the state of the roads and routes available, how difficult is it to reach the destination? Sufficient resources will not always be available to afford the ideal form of transport, or, conversely, the ideal form of transport itself may not be usable. Even if a vehicle is available, it is necessary to evaluate the conditions in the field, which could render it unusable. It is therefore not enough to understand what is needed, but it is equally important to assess the feasibility.

For each means of transport chosen there should always be an alternative (if circumstances prevented its use)

Rescue sizing: once it has been ascertained what type of catastrophe is being faced, it is possible to arrive at preliminary conclusions on the type of assistance that will most likely be needed, and therefore organize an appropriate response phase until more in-depth assessments are not they will reveal, in more detail, the needs to be met. During this step, general answers must be provided to the following checklist:

1. What is needed?
2. How much is needed?
3. When is it needed (is it urgent)?
4. Where is it needed?

The type, quantities, urgency or otherwise and the place of transport of the material and emergency supplies are then determined. In the event that the catastrophe is large-scale and the demand exceeds local / state capacities and resources, international aid is required (intergovernmental humanitarian organizations and NGOs).

Management of picking, transport, stocks, orders: the rescue process is activated and the ESC (Emergency Supply Chain) is implemented. This last phase will continue for as long as the emergency is managed. Temporary deposits near the areas affected by the emergency are selected and activated. It is well known that disasters are dynamic and constantly evolving processes. Consequently, such an assessment is not only intended to identify the current

situation, but also to predict likely future needs. The evaluation process, in fact, is incessant and continuous. It follows the evolution of events and demand, which varies from hour to hour. Based on the results of the assessment, the sizing of the supply chain and the related replenishment and inventory allocation processes are continuously adapted.

5.2.2. State of the art

Humanitarian logistics is a branch of logistics which specializes in organizing the delivery and warehousing of supplies during natural disasters or complex emergencies to the affected area and people. However, this definition focuses only on the physical flow of goods to final destinations, and in reality, humanitarian logistics is far more complicated and includes forecasting and optimizing resources, managing inventory, and exchanging information. Humanitarian logistics is the process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient, cost-effective flow and storage of goods and materials, as well as related information, from the point of origin to the point of consumption for the purpose of alleviating the suffering of vulnerable people.

All humanitarian operations depend on logistics, and logistics should be treated as a key priority in all humanitarian projects. The humanitarian community has long recognised the need to up-date its approach to logistics to support a more efficient and effective delivery of aid, and to reduce the carbon footprint and environmental damage of aid delivery, in line with the Do No Harm principle.

Logistics should be embedded in project conceptualisation and planning, and then considered at all stages of the project cycle, including evaluation. Organisations should ensure that sufficient staff resources are committed to logistics, and that relevant competency frameworks should include logistics competencies. Where an organisation has dedicated logistics staff, they should ensure they are included as early as possible in the project conceptualisation and planning stages. Logistics is a specialised area that requires staff with the specific technical competencies needed to understand, conceptualise and deliver the logistics aspects of programmes.

The DG ECHO on “logistic policy” manual encourages humanitarian actors to consider the following indicative key logistics elements during all phases of humanitarian intervention:

1. Staffing

- Appropriate staffing on logistics, ensuring staff with appropriate technical expertise are consulted at all stages of project conceptualisation and implementation.
- Training needs on logistics, standards and compliance

2. Planning and monitoring

- Conducting assessments and mapping of resource and logistical needs
- Monitoring tools, to assess logistics and supply chain performance, improve performance, and understand the market. This could include using digital tools, satisfaction surveys of aid recipients, conducting market surveys, etc.

3. Procurement

- Considering sources for the procurement of items, taking into account issues such as the possibility of using existing stocks, prepositioned items, the possibility of using the local market, opportunities to work with other organisations through e.g. joint procurement, common services and the use of Humanitarian Procurement Centres. Particular attention should be paid to the procurement of medical equipment and medicines, which can prove more difficult and involve relying on international markets.

- Framework for Operations Key considerations during project life span from conceptualisation to implementation and evaluation Logistics should be embedded in project conceptualisation and planning, and then considered at all stages of the project cycle, including evaluation. Organisations should ensure that sufficient staff resources are committed to logistics, and that relevant competency frameworks should include logistics competencies.

4. Warehousing and transport

- Warehousing and storage requirements, including the opportunity for shared warehousing.
- Management of stocks, including maintaining data on location of stocks, stock levels, shelf-life and turnover of stock.

5. Customs and other administrative requirements

- Administrative requirements, such as customs clearance processes, recognition of qualifications for medical workers etc.6. Joint approaches
- Opportunities to work jointly with other organisations to reduce costs and bureaucracy through e.g. shared services, joint procurement, sharing of information on the local market and infrastructure.

7. Greening

- Consideration should be given to end-of-life of packaging waste and distributed items, including possible ways to reuse or recycle packaging and NFIs. This also applies to the end-of-life of vehicles
- Likewise, consideration should be given to future use and re-use of equipment employed during the operation or remaining humanitarian items.
- An open approach to information sharing with other organisations working in the country can promote efficient (re-)use of resources post implementation. Planning of transport routes and methods should also be prioritised to ensure the reduction of carbon emissions.
- Use of appropriate means of transport to reduce the consumption of fossil energy.
- Use of renewable energy sources whenever possible along with appliances with lower energy consumption.

8. Humanitarian-Development-Peace nexus approach

- Possible opportunities for humanitarian development peace nexus approaches related to logistics, for example in areas such as localisation, transport infrastructure, or disaster preparedness.

5.2.2.1. Disaster response logistics in the framework of the European Union

The EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) was first established in 2001 and it coordinates the response to natural and man-made disasters at the EU level. Its objective is to foster cooperation among national civil protection authorities, increase public awareness and preparedness for disasters and enable quick, effective, coordinated assistance to affected populations.

The rescEU reserve establishes a EU reserve of resources which includes a fleet of firefighting planes and helicopters, medical evacuation planes, as well as a stockpile of medical items and field hospitals that can respond to health emergencies.

The EU civil protection mechanism includes a European civil protection pool. This is a voluntary pool of capacities pre-committed by member states for immediate deployment inside or outside the EU.

The following are some standardised teams and modules set out in the European Civil Protection Mechanism for disaster response:

- **Advanced medical post (AMP):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. 2) Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment.
- **Advanced medical post with surgery (AMP-S):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. 2) Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment. 3) Perform damage control surgery.
- **Aerial forest fire fighting module using planes (FFFP):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose task is: Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by performing aerial firefighting using airplanes.
- **Aerial forest firefighting module using helicopters (FFFH):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose task is: Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by performing aerial firefighting using helicopters.
- **CBRN detection and sampling (CBRNDET):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: a) Carry out/confirm the initial assessment, including: a) the description of the dangers or the risks, b) the determination of the contaminated area, c) the assessment or confirmation of the protective measures already taken. 2) Perform qualified sampling. 3) Mark the contaminated area. 4) Prediction of the situation, monitoring, dynamic assessment of the risks, including recommendations for warning and other measures. 5) Provide support for immediate risk reduction.
- **Emergency Temporary Camp (ETC):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Provide emergency temporary shelter, including staff to assemble the camp, mainly in the initial stages of a disaster in coordination with existing structures, local authorities and international organisations until handover to local authorities or humanitarian organisations, where the capacity remains necessary for longer periods. 2) Where a handover takes place, train the relevant personnel (local and/or international) before the pull out of the module.
- **Field hospital (FHOS):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Provide initial and/or follow-up trauma and medical care, taking into account acknowledged international guidelines for foreign field hospital use, such as World Health Organisation or Red Cross guidelines.
- **Flood containment (FC):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose

tasks is: Reinforce existing structures and build new barriers to prevent further flooding of rivers, basins, waterways with rising water levels.

- **Flood rescue using boats (FRB):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Water search and rescue and assist people trapped in a flooding situation by using boats. 2) Provide lifesaving aid and deliver first necessities as required.
- **Ground forest fire fighting (GFFF):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: To contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using ground means.
- **Ground forest fire fighting using vehicles (GFFF-V):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: To contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using vehicles.
- **Heavy urban search and rescue (HUSAR):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Search for, locate and rescue victims located under debris (such as collapsed buildings and transport incidents). 2) Provide lifesaving first aid as required, until handover for further treatment.
- **High capacity pumping (HCP):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: Provide pumping: 1) in flooded areas, 2) to assist firefighting by delivering water.
- **Medical aerial evacuation of disaster victims (MEVAC):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Transport disaster victims to health facilities for medical treatment using helicopters/planes with stretchers.
- **Medium urban search and rescue (MUSAR):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Search for, locate and rescue victims located under debris (such as collapsed buildings and transport incidents). 2) Provide lifesaving first aid as required, until handover for further treatment.
- **Technical Assistance and Support Team (TAST):** the human and material resources set-up by one or more Member States to fulfil support tasks, as referred to in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams). Their tasks are provide or arrange for: 1) support for set-up and running of office, 2) ICT support, 3) logistics and subsistence support, 4) transport support on site.
- **USAR in CBRN conditions (CBRNUSAR):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Special search and rescue operation in a contaminated environment, using protective suits, in accordance with the requirements of the medium and heavy urban search and rescue modules as appropriate.
- **Water purification (WP):** module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Provide drinkable water, from surface water sources, according to the

applicable standards and at least to the level of the WHO standards. 2) Perform water quality control at the outtake point of the purification equipment.

The Regulation (EU) 2021/836 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 amending Decision No 1313/2013/EU on the Union Civil Protection Mechanism reinforces the European Civil Protection Mechanism by increasing financial support and improving prevention, preparedness and response planning. In addition:

- Allow the Commission to directly procure emergency capabilities in cases where national capacities are overwhelmed. For example, the procurement of equipment to deal with unforeseen emergencies.
- Strengthen the EU Emergency Response Coordination Centre with enhanced operational, analytical, monitoring, information management and communication capabilities.
- Provide Member States with adequate transport means and logistical solutions, e.g. to repatriate EU citizens stranded outside the Union to a safe place, and to transport medical personnel and medical and therapeutic equipment. The EU provides 100% funding for transport and logistics as part of the EU's rescue capabilities.
- In order to make the best use of the experience gained so far with trusted logistical networks managed by relevant international organisations inside the Union, such as the UN Humanitarian Response Depots, the Commission will consider such networks when acquiring, renting, leasing or otherwise contracting rescEU capacities.

5.2.2.2. Disaster response logistics in the framework of the United Nations and of the World Health Organization

In an international, multi-organizational response environment, coordination of activities will require a more participatory process than that found in typical national disaster management structures with more hierarchical decision-making systems. Humanitarian coordination is a more process-oriented system which combines traditional disaster management approaches with the guiding principles of GA Resolution 46/182.

In 2005, under the leadership of the UN Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC), the Humanitarian Reform Agenda and the Cluster Approach assigned, for each strategic sector of humanitarian action, certain institutions that would act in a preferential manner: these are the Clusters. The aim is to facilitate coordination and the creation of partnerships and synergies between institutions in order to improve the effectiveness of humanitarian response.

Figure 25 - UN Humanitarian clusters¹⁰

The United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC) team can be deployed immediately to the affected country to assist national and local authorities in identifying relief needs and coordinating efforts.

All UNDAC teams deployed in an emergency must be fully operational and self-sufficient from the moment they land in the affected country. UNDAC teams may therefore need to bring their own telecommunications, technology, office equipment, tented accommodation and food. UNDAC teams often arrive on the scene in the first moments after a disaster. These teams are often required to initiate logistical preparations or to advise on the planning and implementation of basic logistical programmes.

Assessment and Analysis is an essential component of UNDAC missions to help understand a humanitarian situation by identifying the main problems, their source and consequences. It includes:

- Assessment – This can be defined as a way to identify and measure the humanitarian needs of disaster-affected societies
- Analysis – This can be defined as the process of interpreting available information, including 'raw' data, to identify significant facts, trends and anomalies to inform decision-making

¹⁰ UNITED NATIONS DISASTER ASSESSMENT AND COORDINATION. UNDAC. Field Handbook. UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. 2018. https://www.unocha.org/sites/unocha/files/1823826E_web_pages.pdf

Logistics coordination in UN humanitarian missions will normally be carried out by the World Food Programme (WFP) as the global lead of the Logistics Cluster. In this role, WFP's mission will normally be to assist the humanitarian community in its logistics efforts and to be a focal point for any areas of logistics coordination that require host government support. The Logistics Cluster, if activated, will offer a range of services to the humanitarian community. Depending on the situation, these include logistics information exchange, transport and warehousing services.

WHO, as the UN health cluster leader, should serve as a support to Ministry of Health authorities and international humanitarian actors in the health sector; it should ensure that international humanitarian actors support the national effort, develop and maintain appropriate contacts with relevant governmental and local authorities and local civil society organisations dealing with health-related activities.

Regarding WHO EMT Teams, logistics technical standards govern the operational functionality and self-sufficiency of EMTs. They are, in summary:

- Power and fuel: ensure sufficient, safe, sustainable and context appropriate fuel, power supply and lighting for their facilities, clinical care and support services
- Communications: have the ability to transmit by voice and data to local and national coordination structures with at least one level of redundancy in case of failure
- Transportation and fleet: effectively coordinate the transport of equipment and personnel to the site and throughout the operation
- Food: provide food requirements for all staff, inpatients and caregivers
- Warehouse management: have a warehouse management system with processes and procedures that address preparedness requirements and an ability to respond in the field to manage consistent availability of supplies
- Pharmacy supply chain and medical stock management: be self-sufficient with enough pharmaceutical, medical consumables and medical equipment to deliver the patient care per type of team
- Donation management: have policies in place compliant with national and international standards, for anticipated donation of medical consumables, pharmaceuticals, equipment and/or their entire field facility
- Safety and security: demonstrate due diligence for the safety and security of their personnel and patients during deployment by putting in place management plans and practical measures that are appropriate to the operational context and communicating these to those concerned
- Facility environment and structures: provide suitable and acceptable facilities for clinical care and staff needs
- Mobilization: mobilize in the shortest possible time with a plan stated in established SOPs
- Site Assessment and Planning: assess possible site locations and adapt their layout and configuration to local conditions, including the possibility of working within/reinforcing existing health facilities
- Sequential build: prioritize the establishment of the facility in such a way that areas and services necessary for urgent patient care are established first, while the rest of the facility is completed, allowing certain functions to be operational before deployment is fully completed

- Demobilization: have plans and procedures for coordinated demobilization that maximizes the time of operation and minimizes disruption, supporting recovery of normal local health services and local environmental impacts

5.2.2.3. Disaster response logistics in the framework of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies

The Disaster Relief Emergency Fund (DREF) belongs to the International Federation of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC). It supports national Red Cross and Red Crescent societies in the immediate aftermath of a disaster.

The Red Cross response to disasters is established through 2 programmes:

- Immediate / urgent relief plan (first and second intervention).
- Sustained relief project

The IFRC has different mechanisms and tools to support disaster response. They are designed to ensure rapid and efficient assistance to affected people through the provision of funds, experienced and trained human resources and services appropriate to emergency situations.

FIELD ASSESSMENT AND COORDINATION (FACT) TEAMS.

In a humanitarian emergency, the National Society of the affected country may request assistance from the IFRC. The IFRC then alerts FACT team members from around the world, who are asked to be available within 12 to 24 hours. They are composed of experienced disaster management specialists from the Federation and National Societies, with skills in various fields such as relief, logistics, health, nutrition, public health and epidemiology, water and sanitation, finance, administration, psychosocial support.

The FACT team together with Local National Society counterparts, members of Regional Teams and the ICRC (International Committee of the Red Cross), and in coordination with local authorities, UN agencies and other non-governmental organizations conduct a first standardized assessment of the situation.

EMERGENCY RESPONSE UNITS (ERU)

ERUs were created to provide a rapid, high-quality, standardised response to emergency situations. They provide essential services in accordance with the standards of the recipient country.

There are currently nine different types of highly specialised units (health and relief, water and sanitation, logistics, information technology and communications), all using standardised equipment and trained personnel. The units have a self-supply capacity of one month and can stay in a country for up to four months.

They are requested either by FACT assessment teams or because the disaster response plan advises the deployment of one or more ERUs. The National Societies sponsoring these units then review their implementation and if the deputy director of the secretariat's coordination and programme division gives the go-ahead, the ERUs become part of the Federation's response to the emergency situation.

From activation, all material and equipment must be ready for dispatch within 48 hours. Within one week, the ERU must be ready to operate on the ground.

The teams are composed of specialised personnel ranging in number from 3 to 20 people (doctors, nurses, technicians, engineers, logisticians). Each unit has its own survival equipment (food, bedding, tents, tents, power generators, communications and office equipment) stored in lightweight, easily transportable containers. All members must work in the agreed language and observe the federation's rules of conduct.

5.2.2.4. Standardisation of humanitarian supplies

The economic cost of relief and rehabilitation actions have also been rising sharply, making it necessary to address actions to optimise the cost-effectiveness of interventions, initially based primarily on coordination of efforts.

The objectives of standardisation are basically:

- To ensure quality standards and promote compliance with international specifications for different products
- To facilitate the selection, planning, mobilisation, shipment, storage, exchange, etc. of appropriate supplies
- Facilitate the operability of supplies in the crisis area: familiarity with the use of resources, compatibility of equipment, availability of spare parts, etc.

WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO) CLASSIFICATION OF HUMANITARIAN SUPPLIES

According to their nature, the World Health Organisation (WHO), in consultation with other international organisations, has adopted a standard that groups humanitarian supplies into 10 categories. The SUMA system uses this classification to manage the data on supplies entered in its registration tables:

1. Medicines (pharmaceuticals)
2. Water and environmental sanitation
3. Health (non-pharmaceutical products)
4. Food / beverages
5. Shelter / housing / electricity / construction
6. Logistics / administration
7. Personal needs / education
8. Human resources: although not a supply as such, this category was created to classify the specialties of personnel arriving, especially from abroad, to assist during the emergency
9. Agriculture / livestock
10. Unclassified. This category includes all supplies that are out of date, unknown, unusable, in poor condition or too mixed to be classified in the initial or critical phase of the emergency

UNITED NATIONS CATALOGUE OF EMERGENCY RELIEF ITEMS (UNECE)

Building on a strategy document entitled "An Initiative to Improve Emergency Preparedness" developed in the early 1990s, OCHA promoted the development of the Emergency Stockpile Register, the Commercial Emergency Supply Suppliers Database and the Emergency Relief Items Catalogue by UNDP's Inter-Agency Procurement Services Office (IAPSO).

Its objective is to develop generic specifications for emergency relief items that can be used for disaster assistance by various organisations during the initial phase of a disaster. It has built on years of experience and expertise accumulated within the UN system and the international aid community.

The Emergency Relief Item Catalogue shows by product group the complete specifications for all selected items, together with information on weight and shipping volume. These specifications include, for example, the WHO Interagency Emergency Health Kit (IEHK).

RED CROSS EMERGENCY ITEMS CATALOGUE

The International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies and the International Committee of the Red Cross, supported by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies and in collaboration with UNDP (United Nations Development Programme), IAPSO (Inter-Agency Procurement Services Organization) and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies have established an Emergency Items Catalogue for the standardization, improvement and harmonization of emergency relief and medical items provided by humanitarian organizations and donors.

The Catalogue contains several thousand elements or items extracted from a database containing many more, and is available on-line at: <https://itemscatalogue.redcross.int/>

5.2.2.5. New technologies in humanitarian logistics

Technology is a key factor to achieve better results in disaster logistics. Setting up a communication mechanism in geographies that are remote and devoid of internet or phone networks, implementing up-to-date information or tracking systems & using humanitarian logistics software which can provide real-time supply chain information, organizations can enhance decision making, increase the quickness of the relief operations and achieve better coordination of the relief effort. Biometrics for identifying persons or unauthorized substances, wireless telecommunications, media technology for promoting donations, and medical technologies are some more aspects of technology applied in humanitarian operations. There are four main developments in this field: bar codes, AMS laser cards, radio frequency tags and satellite based internet services.

AMS CARD

Automated manifest system (AMS) cards have been used by the United States government to store substantial amounts of information about shipments. The cards have become more popular in humanitarian logistics as they are able to provide various aspects related to:

- Stock number
- Requisition number
- Shipment date
- Quantity
- Consignee

The AMS cards are attached to both pallets and containers and inserted to a processing unit which can give all details about a delivery. The use of those cards is beneficial to both shippers and beneficiaries in humanitarian logistics management because beneficiaries can plan resources, especially food and medicines, or find alternatives. Therefore, this application can make the process more flexible and efficient. In addition, AMS cards are cheap, reusable, and resistant to extreme weather.

RADIO FREQUENCY IDENTIFICATION TAGS AND LABEL

The tags are useful in identifying information about delivery routes. They are attached to different types of vehicles, including pallets, trucks, vans, and large containers, to position the location of shipments on route. In addition, they can read information when the vehicles pass through points along the route. After that, the information is stored on a label. Together with the AMS cards, they can provide an effective solution to humanitarian logistics to increase its transparency and responsiveness.

BAR CODES

One major concern in humanitarian logistics management is the reliability of product sources because the most popularly-procured item is food. In the past, there were cases regarding food unsafety caused by the unclear origins of products. Recently, bar codes have been a feasible solution to address this problem in humanitarian logistics. Bar code labels make it possible to represent alphanumeric characters (letters and numbers) by means of bars and blanks of varying widths that can be read automatically by optical scanners. This system recognizes and processes these symbols, compares their patterns with those already stored in computer memory, and interpret the information. This standardized coding system means that there can be a one-on-one, unique, non-ambiguous relationship between the pattern and that to which it refers. At present, bar codes are mostly used in:

- Product packages
- Identification cards
- Catalogue or price lists
- Product labels
- Forms, receipts, and invoices

SATELLITE BASED INTERNET SERVICES

Communication, especially in the remote disaster zones is often difficult due to absence or damage to the mobile communication networks. During the war in Ukraine in 2022, Starlink (Satellite internet) services opened a new possibility to restore this vital service capability.

5.2.2.6. Standards and methodology

To keep the level of services related to first air response on multi-casualty disasters is needed to maintain capabilities of the resources ([Emergency medical services systems in the European Union](#)) so here is the importance about education for disaster management and crisis management for EMS personnel.

- Maintain control of the resources
- Coordination of the different areas
- Well-defined chain of command and control
- Expertise EMS jobs
- Skills-Know-How-Experience in management critical situations

Also, is necessary to test the plan to verify and improve the management to face a real threat. Test and exercises represent the tool between education and response. This test should be performed once year.

From European Union pursuits a standard formal education but until now is a challenge. Is interesting to create and maintain a coordinated level of educational specialist training for each

country ([Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union :Education / Education and training initiatives for crisis management in the European Union](#)).

5.2.3. Landscape

The following items have been consulted in the WP5 questionnaire in relation to this section Maintenance, logistics and deployment:

- Standardized Service Ambulances at national level? (Equipment, Crew, Crew training)
- Indicate the logistical support items available in your service for MCI or disaster response (Communications vehicle, Logistic vehicle, Signalling elements, Triage tag, Personal protection equipment (PPE), Advanced medical post facility, Victims wearables (location, monitoring, etc.), First responders wearables (identification, location, monitoring, etc.))
- What elements of the previous logistical support items are standardised at the national level? (Communications vehicle, Logistic vehicle, Signalling elements, Triage tag, Personal protection equipment (PPE), Advanced medical post facility, Victims wearables (location, monitoring, etc.), First responders wearables (identification, location, monitoring, etc.))
- Select the specific mobilisation procedures that exist in your service in relation to MCI and disasters (Activation procedure of supplies for MCI, Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders, Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours)
- What elements of the previous specific mobilisation procedures are standardised at the national level? (Activation procedure of supplies for MCI, Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders, Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours)
- Indicate the items for which stock procedures exist in your Service, in relation to MCI or disasters, if available (List of medical supplies, Sanitary equipment, Medications, Emergency clothing, Food and water, Gasoline, Electric energy and power supplies, Bathrooms and showers, Communication equipment to be used on the site of MCI)
- Indicate the available First Responders support hardware devices (Mobile phone, Tablet, Laptop, Walkie-Talkie, Transmitter, Satellite, Others)
- Other Devices included (free text)
- Description of the Service First Responders support hardware (free text)
- Features of the Service First Responders support hardware (Available, Available on scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability)
- Perception of needs (Free text): Needs/shortcomings existing in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

Following the analysis of the questionnaires/surveys during the Valkyries project WP5 execution, the Landscape picture is as in the following table.

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Standardized Service Ambulances at national level	Equipment > Crew > Crew training	Very high
Logistical support items available for MCI or disaster response	Personal protection equipment (PPE) > Triage	Very high

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
	tag > Advanced medical post facility > Communications vehicle = Logistic vehicle = Signalling elements > Victims wearables = First responders wearables	
Standardized elements for logistical support items at the national level	Personal protection equipment (PPE) > Triage tag > Signalling elements, > Communication vehicle > Logistic vehicle = Advanced medical post facility > Victims wearables = First responders wearables	High
Specific mobilization procedures that existing in relation to MCI and disasters	Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders > Activation procedure of supplies for MCI > Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours	High
Elements of the previous specific mobilisation procedures are standardised at the national level	Activation procedure of supplies for MCI > Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders	Very high
Items for which stock procedures exist in relation to MCI or disasters	Medications = Electric energy and power supplies > Sanitary equipments > List of medical supplies = Emergency clothing = Food and water = Gasoline, = Communication equipment to be used on the site of MCI > Bathrooms and showers	Medium
Service First Responders Communications Network Description	Tetra > Analogical radio = Mobile phone network	High
Service First Responders communication support features	Available > Available On Scene > Dedicated > Cross-agency Capability	High

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Service First Responders communication support available devices	Laptop > Mobile phone = Transmitter > Tablet > Walkie-Talkie = Satellite	High

Table 6 - WP5 questionnaire: Maintenance, logistics and deployment answers

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS:

From the results of the questionnaires, it appears that there is extensive standardisation within each nation in terms of ambulances equipment, ambulances crew and crew training. This degree of standardisation is somewhat higher in those emergency services with no potential involvement in cross-national disaster response.

Figure 26 – Nationally standardised aspects of ambulance services according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Is predominant the availability of the following logistical support items for ICM or disaster response:

- Communications vehicles
- Logistic vehicles
- Signalling elements
- Triage tags, sometimes standardised at national level
- Personal protection equipment (PPE), sometimes standardised at national level
- Advanced medical post facilities

On the other hand, in these cases, the availability of wearables applied to first responders or victim care is minimal.

The degree of standardisation of these means at national level is still low except for Triage tag, Personal protection equipment (PPE) and to a lesser extent Signaling elements.

Figure 27 – Logistical support elements within the Service for response to MCIs or disasters

Based on the results obtained in the questionnaires, it seems that there is a high degree of implementation of procedures, but there is no unified cross-agency maintenance, logistics and deployment procedures for crisis response. These are generally non-standardised procedures at the national level. Procedures usually exist for those items, in relation to MCI or disasters:

- Activation procedure of supplies for MCI.
- Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders
- Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours

Figure 28 – Specific mobilisation procedures available within the Service for response to MCIs or disasters according to to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Items for which storage procedures exist in relation to MCI or disasters are:

- List of medical supplies
- Sanitary equipment
- Medications
- Food and water
- Gasoline
- Electric energy and power supplies
- Communication equipment to be used on the site of MCI

Figure 29 – Specific storage procedures available within the Service for response to MCIs or disasters according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

In the specific field of FR communications logistics, the survey results show that emergency services' communications solutions are still almost universally based on TETRA, with less than 40% of services still using analogue radio frequency or relying on commercial mobile telephony to support their operational or C2 communications.

Figure 30 – Service First Responders Communications

In relation to the communication support devices available to First Responders, the following predominate, although none of them individually exceeds 50% of the Services surveyed, and with data showing a situation of clear inferiority in the case of EMS compared to firefighters and to other emergency services.

- Laptop
- Mobile phone
- Transmitter

Figure 31 – Service First Responders communication support available devices according to the type of emergency service

5.2.4. Perception of needs

In relation to other needs perceived by the experts surveyed, the following needs emerged from the questionnaires carried out:

- Coordination of different institutions and between different regions
- Needed training
- Standards and procedures between emergency agencies are not completely unified and connected

5.3. Command and Control and support to operational decision-making

5.3.1. Introduction

5.3.1.1. Concepts in command and control (C2)

- **Command:** The act of managing, directing, ordering, or controlling by virtue of explicit statutory, regulatory, or delegated authority.
- **Command & control (C&C, C2):** Activities of target-orientated decision-making, including assessing the situation, planning, implementing decisions and controlling the effects of implementation on the incident
- **C2 system:** System that supports effective emergency management of all available assets in a preparation, incident response, continuity and/or recovery process.
- **Control:** The application of authority, combined with the capability to manage resources, in order to achieve defined objectives.
- **Disaster:** Situation where widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses have occurred that exceeded the ability of the affected organization, community or society to respond and recover using its own resources
- **Disaster management:** The organization, planning and application of measures preparing for, responding to and recovering from disasters.
- **Emergency communications centre:** A set of call takers operating under common management which receives emergency calls for service and asynchronous event notifications and processes those calls and events according to a specified operational policy.
- **Emergency operations centre (EOC):** Officially designated facility for the direction and co-ordination of all activities during the response phase a disaster. The physical location at which the coordination of information and resources to support incident management (on-scene operations) activities normally takes place.
- **Incident commander:** The individual responsible for all incident activities, including the development of strategies and tactics and the ordering and release of resources. The Incident Commander has overall authority and responsibility for conducting incident operations and is responsible for the management of all incident operations at the incident site.
- **Mass Casualty Incident (MCI):** An event which generates more patients at one time than locally available resources can manage using routine procedures.
- **MCI management system:** A coherent and interrelated set of established procedures, policies, and plans that contribute to the shared objectives of optimizing the baseline capacity to deal with patient populations expected in a mass casualty incident, and efficiently increasing this capacity during the response to a mass casualty incident.

- **Operational plan:** Plan focused on effective management of resources with a short time framework, converting objectives into targets and activities, and arrangements for monitoring implementation and resource usage.
- **SIGRUN Operational Center:** The Valkyries / SIGRUN centre to provide secure interoperability of federated systems and the COP sharing created by all sources (nationally or cross-border sharing)
- **Unified command:** In incidents involving multiple jurisdictions, a single jurisdiction with multiagency involvement, or multiple jurisdictions with multiagency involvement, unified command allows agencies with different legal, geographic, and functional authorities and responsibilities to work together effectively without affecting individual agency authority, responsibility, or accountability.

5.3.1.2. Disaster management responsibility

MCI or disasters are situations that exceed the normal response capabilities of the emergency services, and require planning and preparedness, specific procedures, additional resources over and above normal resources, and effective coordination of the response.

This coordination requires a process of communication between the actors involved in the response, from the authorities responsible for disaster protection to the first responders deployed on the ground.

Emergencies are high-stress situations in which first responders have to act with operational procedures that are different from those they use under normal conditions. They are also situations that are unfamiliar and not easy to train for, and their occurrence often evokes intense feelings of stress, and insecurity.

During an emergency situation, first responders will have to understand the situation at any moment from the often inaccurate, incomplete or even contradictory received information, deciding actions in a short period of time.

Disaster management requires the involvement of multiple actors at multiple levels of responsibility and in different physical settings.

In the EU environment, first responders on the scene (rescuers, fire fighters, law enforcement, emergency medical services, etc.) are generally technically trained and resourced to ensure a high level of quality in dealing with typical emergency situations. Even in more complex and stressful situations such as MCI, the effective intervention of these first responders is also usually guaranteed when it comes to resolving situations similar to those they usually face (rescue, extinguishing, maintenance of security, medical assistance to victims, etc.).

Where problems often arise is in the overall management of the intervention: the coordination of different disciplines, of different agencies, of different administrations not used to working together on a day-to-day basis. In any emergency effort to allocate a particular resource, there are many specific functions involved, and it must be clear to all involved who is the person who performs a specific function at a specific time.

Crisis response plans in the EU context generally address all activities associated with response management together and incorporate the organisational responsibilities of these emergency services. However, this is not the case when it comes to procedures for first responders on the ground in a disaster, which in many cases rely on the existence of procedures within each service

(more usual) and procedures for joint action between different services or agencies (much less frequent).

The importance of clarity in defining operational and coordination responsibilities seems clear. In general, responsibility for coordinating a disaster is established by law, and usually respects the principle of subsidiarity. This principle, one on which the European Union is based, states that a matter should be resolved by the authority closest to the subject of the problem whenever possible.

Local agencies are generally the pillars of emergency response and recovery at their level of competence. Regional or state authorities are usually designated for the coordination of more complex crises, which by their nature may sometimes require cross-cutting, inter-agency or even inter-state coordination.

5.3.1.3. Phases of disaster response management

Classically, a disaster can be divided into phases in chronological order: pre-event, preparedness, warning, threat, impact, rescue, reconstruction, rehabilitation.

In relation to disaster response actions, Jennex considers emergencies as a series of four phases bounded by five critical events:

1. SITUATION ANALYSIS PHASE: includes a series of ongoing activities aimed at enabling early detection of the INITIATING EVENT when it occurs
2. INITIAL RESPONSE PHASE: is triggered immediately upon detection of the initiating event, and is aimed at verification of the emergency, generation of early warning alerts, initialisation of pre-planned preliminary actions and activation of the emergency response plan
3. EMERGENCY RESPONSE PHASE: This phase begins directly after the emergency response teams have taken over control: CONTROL EVENT. This is the actual command and control phase, during which the emergency response plan is implemented and the coordination of responders, deployment of resources and allocation of resources begins. It requires emergency responders to monitor the conditions and progress of response operations and adjust them accordingly. It ends when emergency responders determine that emergency conditions are under control and, therefore, no further response actions are required: RESTORATION EVENT
4. RECOVERY RESPONSE PHASE: This phase begins with the restoration event and includes long-term activities aimed at normalising the situation, analysing the event and identifying areas for improvement. This phase ends when a return to normality has been achieved: NORMALIZING EVENT. after this phase, the situation analysis phase would return, thus closing the cycle.

Jennex¹¹ also differentiates a TERMINATING EVENT that can determine the termination of the response in any of its phases (e.g. in case of a false alarm).

¹¹ Jennex, ME. Modeling emergency response systems. In: Proceedings of the 40th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. 2007, Waikoloa, Hawaii, USA. Washington DC, USA, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE).

https://www.academia.edu/31038972/Modeling_Emergency_Response_Systems

5.3.1.4. *The command and control function in disasters*

Command and control is a critical management function during all phases of emergency response. It basically consists of:

- Analyse the emergency situation and decide how to respond quickly, appropriately and effectively.
- Directing and coordinating the efforts of the various response forces.
- Coordinate with the response efforts of other agencies or jurisdictions.

The way the situation is managed will determine the effectiveness of the operation as a whole. A harmonised approach to disaster management involves a common picture of the situation, by merging information, which is spread across several stakeholders. In order to obtain an overview of the situation, information is exchanged between stakeholders. According to Sagun, there are four main channels of information flow during disaster management:

- Within a participating organisation
- Between organisations
- From people to organisations
- From organisations to people.

5.3.1.5. *Command and control dimensions*

Following the authors Chumer M and Turoff M,¹² C2 can be broken down into three basic dimensions:

C2 AS PROCESS

C2 resembles a process in which there is a beginning and an end, as well as a reason for the process itself. As the basis for a successful C2 process, some authors have postulated Boyd's OODA LOOP model¹³, which can work at the individual level or at the level of the collective, and which distinguishes four steps or elements:

1. **OBSERVE:** This first step suggests both a perception of information and a focus on the information that matters. Perception of our surroundings usually occurs visually, but all senses are involved. It involves the observation of the situation as well as the follow-up of the actions resulting from the ACT Phase to evaluate its outcome.
2. **ORIENT:** This step involves the integration of all the perceived data, making sense of it quickly in the midst of often uncertain or ambiguous situations. This level of integration helps an incident commander get the big picture of the situation as it exists and develops. Visualisation technologies support high-level C2 functions more than data mining and other methods that reduce data streams to meaningful components.
3. **DECIDE:** Once the orientation to data (or lack of data) has occurred, the decision-maker develops an idea of reality and makes what he or she considers to be the best possible

¹² Chumer M, Turoff M. (2006). Command and Control (C2): Adapting the Distributed Military Model for Emergency Response and Emergency Management. Proceedings of ISCRAM 2006 - 3rd International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management. http://www.dodccrp.org/events/11th_ICCRTS/html/papers/005.pdf

¹³ Boyd, John, R., The Essence of Winning and Losing. 1995. <https://web.archive.org/web/20110324054054/http://www.danford.net/boyd/essence.htm>

decision. Different models of decision making have been enunciated, among which are the following:

- o Rational actor model: rational assessment of all alternatives and the potential risks associated with each alternative
 - o Organizational model: what worked in the past
 - o Political model: taking into account the interests of different stakeholders. Too often, the resulting decision is a compromise that does not reflect the best solution that the most talented members could have come up with. It is an average outcome
4. ACT: This is the last step of Boyd's LOOP. It is initiated after a decision has been made and consists of communicating the suggested action and then monitoring the action to determine whether it has resulted in the expected change in the situation.

Figure 32 - OODA loop over target critical infrastructure

C2 AS FUNCTION

The second dimension of the C2 is its construction as a function, with both physical and virtual features, such as an Emergency Operations Centre or even an Incident Command Post.

- o PHYSICAL C2: The integration of human beings and information and communication technologies and systems in a physical space. It can be fixed or mobile, as well as single, redundant or distributed.
- o VIRTUAL C2: The knowledge needed to respond to certain situations does not always reside in those who are physically present in a specific place. A virtual C2 would allow

the integration of different knowledge in a network, taking advantage of competences that are not and should not be found in the organisations that make up the physical C2.

C2 AS ORGANISATION

Organisations themselves, by their very nature and structure, by their capacity to adapt or collaborate, how they behave, how they communicate, how they make decisions, or how they make sense of and react to signals from the environment, also determine the disaster management response.

Such organizations need to maintain their own risk assessment and risk management methods against any cyber, physical or logical threat.

5.3.1.6. Levels of command and control of a disaster

The emergency response command structure should be established before the emergency occurs, so that when the response begins, there is no confusion about who assumes what tasks and who reports to whom. This will help ensure that everyone involved understands their responsibilities and is prepared to implement them when an emergency occurs.

In disaster management, several types or levels of functions can be distinguished in the command and control structure:

- **OPERATIONAL FUNCTIONS:** These are the activities of first responders carried out directly at the disaster site. These are activities at the lowest level of coordination: the execution of the operation. At this level all parties involved have a very local and limited view of the overall operation. Some operational managers may have basic command functions, controlling and deploying resources according to their authority within their own organisation, and within a specific functional or geographical area, and executing the directions of the tactical command. Despite being at the bottom of the chain of command and control, operational staff must establish lines of communication that allow them to receive the instructions and issue the information necessary to work together in a coordinated manner and to keep higher echelons of command and control informed.
- **TACTICAL FUNCTIONS:** These are the tasks relating to the deployment and resupply of units on the ground, as well as the control of the different relief operations taking place simultaneously at the scene of the disaster. They would be one step higher than the operative ones, involving coordination of teams, collection and assessment of information on the situation, and decision-making in their specific area of competence and aligned with the strategic vision established at higher levels. Effective joint working with other services, and access to efficient communication systems, is essential among tactical responders. Those working at the tactical level should be located in a mutually agreed location where they can maintain effective joint command of the operation. Where circumstances preclude co-location of responders at any level, arrangements for robust communication should be implemented, using interoperable communications.
- **STRATEGIC FUNCTIONS:** This is the highest level at which all activities in the disaster relief process are overseen based on information obtained from lower levels. Each strategic commander has overall authority on behalf of his or her organisation. They are responsible for identifying and allocating resources and developing the strategy for their own organisation. They may delegate decisions to their respective tactical commanders.

In this phase, an overall picture or overview of the disaster is generated and an overall disaster relief strategy is developed, which should include capacity for additional resources, pre-emption, etc.

It is important to emphasize that the military command structure differs to the civilian structure:

Civilian	Military
Strategic	Strategic
Tactical	Operational
Operational	Tactical

Table 7 – Civilian versus military command structure

Emergency personnel adopt levels of command when responding to incidents. The level does not necessarily indicate professional category or rank, but rather the role a person plays at any given time in the incident.

There should always be a clear and identifiable commander or representative on the ground who is responsible for coordinating activity at each level of command.

It is important that all persons who might be first on the scene of an incident are empowered to initiate the declaration of a major incident for their organisation and understand the implications of declaring or not declaring it and therefore initiating the process of activating the relevant response plans.

They must also be able to transmit information about the disaster, for example using the M/ETHANE model.

In the early stages of an incident, first responders are likely to be in the best position to assess the scale of any incident and the possible need for a wider response.

At this point, it is likely that in the initial stages of an incident, first responders will have to assume tactical responsibilities. Once the scale and nature of the incident is known, the emergency services will designate officers to act as tactical commanders for their organisation.

In turn, the tactical commander is likely to be on the scene before the strategic commander and it is likely to be the senior commander at the scene of the relevant emergency service who initially takes overall command of the incident before the strategic commander has had a chance to set a strategy.

5.3.1.7. Characteristic failures in disaster response management

During emergency response operations, Chen et al.¹⁴ identify three characteristic types of delay:

- TYPE 1: This is a delay in dispatching the necessary emergency teams due to limited situational awareness and understanding of the scope of an incident. To reduce this type of error, the following are proposed:
 - o Geographic location-based information systems.

¹⁴ Chen, R., Sharman, R., Rao, H. R. and Upadhyaya, S. (2007) Design principles for critical incident response systems. Information Systems and E-Business Management. [Online] 5 (3), 201-227. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220385080_Design_principles_for_critical_incident_response_systems

- o Recording all information and analysing it for potentially useful content.
 - o With the ability to integrate and present appropriate, accurate and up-to-date information about the incident, the surrounding environment and response operations in real time.
 - o With decision-support resources based on these information concepts that allow decisions to be adjusted to each moment of reality.
- TYPE 2: This is the delay or error attributable to the lack of preparation of the responders for the execution of their tasks. It may include lack of knowledge of the specific procedures for action, errors in the identification of personal protective equipment in relation to the type of risk, delay in accessing the accident area due to insufficient knowledge of the location of the event, etc. It can be reduced by adequate training and coaching before the event and, after the event, by optimising the coordination of personnel in the response phase.
- TYPE 3: This delay can occur during the process of information acquisition, communication and decision-making. It can be addressed by facilitating shared knowledge of the situation among the interveners.

5.3.1.8. Classic C2 models in MCI and disasters

Typically, disaster response plans and procedures regarding mass casualty incidents (MCI) or disasters use a centralised management and control system, an on-site control system or a combination of both.

On the other hand it has to be clarified that , in most cases, different C2 centres operate even within a country (Fire Brigade, EMS, Police, Volunteers, Army, Municipalities providing logistic support to first responders, Civil Protection Authority etc. In most cases, such C2 do not have the same view of the event as they do not share today any tactical or operational information that could be considered as crucial for the synchronization.

The management and control system to be used must be established in advance, and be known and respected by all those potentially involved in the response.

CENTRALISED C2

In this model, an Emergency Operational Centre (EOC) centralises the overall coordination and strategic direction of the emergency response, under the command of an "overall director" of the response plan.

This method is very useful, for example, when preventive plans are activated in the event of a significant increase in the level of a given risk. In these situations, it may be necessary to issue emergency information to the public, limit or even suspend access to places, services or rights, determine evacuation actions, plan mass care actions, etc.

This method is also useful in large-scale disasters that severely affect several jurisdictions, to allow a global picture of the situation in all affected jurisdictions, to ensure coordination with all representatives of the jurisdictions and agencies involved, to expedite effective decision-making to meet the needs as required by the disaster situation, etc.

Examples of centralised command are, in general terms, the emergency response plans of civil protection systems in EU countries.

Figure 33 - Organizational chart of the Territorial Civil Protection Plan of the Community of Madrid PLATERCAM¹⁵

ON SCENE C2

When central control of the emergency response is not essential, the actions that actually minimise the impacts of the emergency event and save lives are taken by the first responders on the scene. In these cases, the imposition of a centralised command and control system could complexity and slow down the response and make it less effective.

Coordination is one of the key objectives of on scene command structure planning. The response may involve personnel from various services, agencies or jurisdictions, as well as volunteers. The mechanisms to be used to coordinate the efforts of all these different types of responders should be established before the emergency occurs.

The on-scene control system gives ultimate command and control responsibility for all response actions to an individual who has responded to the scene of the emergency. This "Incident Commander" or IC has the authority to coordinate the use of resources and personnel at the scene of the emergency.

The person designated as the IC, regardless of service, agency or jurisdiction, is responsible for overall incident command. Under this arrangement, a fire service official may direct fire, police and other department personnel.

¹⁵ Modified from: PLATERCAM: Acuerdo de 30 de abril de 2019, del Consejo de Gobierno, por el que se aprueba el Plan Territorial de Protección Civil de la Comunidad de Madrid.
https://www.comunidad.madrid/transparencia/sites/default/files/plan/document/acuerdo_de_30_de_abril_de_2019.pdf

Incident command responsibility may change as higher level personnel arrive on scene. In other cases, the individual designated to serve as IC may depend on the type of hazard (e.g. a fire command at a fire, or a law enforcement command at a violent act), a management decree or law, etc.

Examples of on-scene command are the US Incident Command System (ICS) or the United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination System (UNAC).

TRANSITION

In both C2 models, centralised and on scene, the evolution of events may mean that direction and control may have to move from the scene(s) to the EOC, or from the EOC to the scene(s).

It is vital to understand that only one person can have ultimate command of the disaster response. The relationship between centralised command authority and the IC must be clearly established when both ICS and centralised methods of direction and control can be used.

- **TRANSITION FROM EOC TO SCENE:** In some emergencies, the establishment of a field command may not be possible or appropriate during the initial response phase (e.g., in the early stages of a terrorist attack), and several actions may even be necessary before an emergency boarding location can be established (e.g., in the early stages of a terrorist attack). Consequently, many of the initial C2 actions of the response must be carried out remotely, in an EOC. As the emergency situation becomes clearer and when a specific emergency scene is defined, command may be transferred to an IC over the scene. Once command authority is transferred to the IC, the EOC would provide support and would not be responsible for operational decision-making.
- **TRANSITION FROM SCENE TO EOC:** In other cases the opposite may be the case: an event that initially appears to be limited in scope is managed from the scene by an IC, but as the emergency takes on disaster proportions or as outbreaks multiply, it may become necessary to coordinate all operations through the EOC.
- **TRANSITION FROM ONE EOC TO ANOTHER EOC:** It is also possible that a disaster that is initially being centrally managed by the EOC of one agency or jurisdiction, when the damage becomes more complicated or widespread and involves higher levels, may result in the transfer of ultimate responsibility for C2 to another EOC in another agency or another jurisdiction. In this case, it would generally entail the integration in the new EOC of the heads of the different affected administrations, both for the management and coordination of the emergency and for the necessary transfer of responsibilities.

5.3.1.9. Cross-border disasters

The term cross-border disaster management would apply when transnational collaboration of disaster managers is necessary to respond sufficiently.

Cross-border disaster relief processes require coordination and collaboration activities between all parties involved that are even more complex than those for localised incidents in a single country.

In particular, the cross-border activation of information-sharing process is a very important aspect of the disaster response process.

In transboundary events, coordination of disaster management can be a crucial point for an effective disaster response. Interlinked prevention and mitigation strategies, as well as effective

emergency response processes, require harmonised coordination of the layers of different organisations and regions and information-sharing practices.

Cross-border cooperation in the EU is based on international, national, regional and local legislation, and may be regulated by bi- or multilateral agreements at all these levels, in addition to the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism or international agreements on humanitarian aid. These regional initiatives aim to strengthen capacities and improve coordinated actions in the framework of protection and response measures to common threats. They allow for the exchange of data, improved forecasting and prevention, rapid communication of information on emergency situations, as well as coordinated mutual assistance in case of emergency. Coordination efforts include mainly resource management, situational awareness and command and control activities.

In the political context of the European Union, the heterogeneity of mandates, different structures of responsibilities (e.g. centralised structures versus federally organised states) and technical asymmetries in information and communication processes call into question the interoperability of disaster management.

The EU has two main instruments at its disposal to provide a first response to disasters: civil protection and humanitarian aid.

5.3.1.10. C2 model in emergencies in USA: the ICS

The National Incident Management System (NIMS) is a programme of the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), which focuses on a comprehensive approach to emergency response.

The NIMS model for incident management is the Incident Command System (ICS) which was developed in the 1970s following a series of catastrophic fires in California's urban interface.

The ICS is a standardised on-scene emergency management organisation designed to assist in the management of resources during incidents. It is applicable to all jurisdictions, institutions, agencies and services with disaster management and support responsibilities.

When organisations use the ICS model as the basis for their disaster planning, they adopt a predefined management hierarchy, processes and protocols that come into play in an emergency.

The complexity of the incident is assessed on a five-point scale ranging from Type 5 (the least complex incident) to Type 1 (the most complex incident).

The ICS command structure provides an orderly chain of command that is consistent across all response organisations. This chain of command may be headed by a single individual, the Incident Commander (IC), or by a multi-agency team, referred to as the Unified Command. All other elements of the command structure are the same regardless of the form of command, but the ICS organisation can easily expand from a very small size for routine operations to a larger organisation capable of handling catastrophic events.

This organisation includes five main functional areas, staffed for a given incident: Command, Operations, Planning, Logistics and Finance/Administration. A sixth ICS function, Intelligence/Investigations, is used when the incident requires these specialised capabilities.

Figure 34 - Organizational chart of the USA ICS¹⁶

The following characteristics are the basis for incident command and coordination within NIMS and contribute to the strength and efficiency of the overall system:

- Common terminology
- Modular organisation
- Management by objectives
- Incident Action Planning
- Manageable control range
- Facilities and locations of the incident
- Integrated resource management
- Integrated communications
- Establishment and transfer of command
- Unified command
- Chain of command and unity of command
- Responsibility
- Dispatch/Deployment
- Information and intelligence management

5.3.1.11. *United Kingdom: the JESIP Joint Doctrine*

The Joint Emergency Services Interoperability Programme (JESIP) was established in UK in the 2012 by the Association of Chief Police Officers, the Association of Chief Fire Officers (National Resilience) and the Association of Ambulance Chief Executives (AAACE).

The JOINT DOCTRINE provides those responsible for responding to an incident, at all levels, on the scene or elsewhere, with generic guidance and principles on the actions to be taken when responding to multi-agency incidents of any scale. It is not a rigid set of rules, but aims to establish commonly agreed, flexible and adaptable models and principles for effective emergency response.

¹⁶ Modified from: National Incident Management System. FEMA. 2017.
https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-07/fema_nims_doctrine-2017.pdf

It sets out the following fundamental principles for working together, which can be applied in a different order if necessary:

1. **CO-LOCATION:** Generally speaking, co-location of actors should occur as soon as reasonably possible. Co-location has many advantages, such as improved communication and understanding that favour working together. It helps responders to jointly agree on objectives and a coordinated plan to effectively resolve an incident. The operational and tactical commanders of each response organisation should be easily identifiable at an incident. This is often achieved by wearing function-specific tabards. With the use of technology, co-location can be virtual. If there is any delay in co-location of responders, interoperable communications should be used to begin to establish shared situational awareness.
2. **COMMUNICATION:** Meaningful and effective communication between response teams and response organisations is the basis for effective joint working. Communication links start from the moment of the first call or contact, instigating communication between control rooms as early as possible to initiate the information sharing process. Individuals should start from a position of considering the risks and harms if information is not shared. Sharing information in a way that can be understood by the recipient helps to develop a shared understanding of the situation, which underpins the best possible outcomes of an incident.
3. **COORDINATION:** Control rooms should engage in multi-agency communications as early as possible to carry out the initial actions necessary to manage the incident. Coordination underpins joint working by avoiding potential conflicts, preventing duplication of effort and minimising risk. For coordination to be effective, one organisation usually needs to take the lead role. Specific guidance exists for some types of incidents, highlighting which organisation should take the lead role. If military assistance is required, Defence assumes a supporting role to ensure that tasks are properly allocated.
4. **JOINTLY UNDERSTAND RISK:** Each organisation should carry out its own risk assessments and then share the results so that control measures and contingencies can be planned more effectively together. The results of the individual dynamic risk assessment can be used to develop the analytical risk assessment of the incident. By jointly understanding the risks and associated mitigation measures, organisations can promote responder safety and reduce the impact that risks can have on members of the public, infrastructure and the environment.
5. **SHARED SITUATION AWARENESS:** Shared situational awareness is a common understanding of the circumstances, immediate consequences and implications of the emergency, together with an appreciation of the available capabilities and priorities of response organisations. Achieving shared situational awareness is essential for effective interoperability. Whenever possible, control rooms should use pre-defined electronic data transfer to share information (e.g. M/ETHANE). This can reduce voice channel congestion, avoid misunderstandings and eliminate "double keying" information. However, direct data transfer does not eliminate the need for early dialogue between control room supervisors to achieve shared situational awareness. A common information sharing platform called ResilienceDirect is the means to collaboratively share and manage information to support joint decision-making. There are considerable advantages to using an electronic system. For example, automating aspects of data

collection, combination, analysis and presentation will be much more useful and efficient for those using it.

Figure 35 - JESIP fundamental principles¹⁷

5.3.1.12. The WHO incident management system (IMS)

The WHO Incident Management System (IMS), which provides a standardised, yet flexible, approach to managing WHO's response to the emergency. WHO applies the IMS regardless of the underlying hazard or the scale or operational context of the emergency.

STANDARDISED EMERGENCY FUNCTIONS:

There are key management functions that must be performed for any emergency response, regardless of the number of people available or involved in operations.

For the WHO, the main functions of the IMS are:

- Leadership
- Coordination of partners
- Information and planning
- Health operations and technical expertise
- Operations and logistics support
- Finance and administration

¹⁷ JOINT DOCTRINE: The Interoperability Framework. JESIP Joint Doctrine. 2021.
https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/media/pdf/JESIP_Joint_Doctrine_Guide_OCT21.pdf

- Standardised terminology: Consistent use of terminology across the Organization improves communications and limits ambiguity. As far as possible, WHO aims to use terms similar to those of its partners, to optimise interoperability (see below).
- Flexibility, adaptability and scalability: The IMS is applicable to all types and scales of emergencies. It can be easily adapted, while maintaining standards and predictability. The organisational structure can be expanded or reduced as needs evolve, with sub-functions being added or removed. Similarly, the number of staff designated to each function is scalable.
- Interoperability: The implementation of the IMS enables WHO to interact and work more effectively with operational partners. This includes functional interoperability (e.g. use of standardised terminology and procedures) and technological interoperability (e.g. standardised telecommunications). Interoperability is also promoted through WHO's consistent adherence to inter-agency protocols and procedures, e.g. the IASC humanitarian programme cycle.

UNIFIED STRUCTURE

An initial Incident Management Team (IMT) is established in-country to cover critical IMS functions. This will initially be done through the re-use of country office staff. The IMT is established as close to the emergency as possible, and this is almost always in-country. However, flexibility may be necessary, especially for:

- Emergencies where high levels of insecurity do not allow for the presence of international staff in-country. In these cases, IMT elements may be located in a neighbouring or nearby country, providing remote support to IMT members in-country.
- Emergencies that occur in countries where WHO does not have a country office. This may occur when a developed country requests technical and operational support from WHO, especially for outbreak response. In these cases, the IMT would be located in the Regional Office.
- Multi-country and multi-regional emergencies. An IMT can be established in Regional and/or at Headquarters Offices.

An Emergency Manager and an Incident Management Support Team (IMST) to coordinate organisation-wide support for emergency response.

In the case of protracted emergencies, the role of the incident commander will change to that of a long-term emergency manager and the IMT will become an emergency management team. However, emergency operations should follow the key principles of the IMS and most of the critical functions of the IMS should be maintained. Response management will be guided by the Protracted Emergency Framework.

Figure 36 - Organizational chart of the WHO IMS structure¹⁸

5.3.1.13. The United Nations disaster assessment and coordination system (UNAC)

The United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC) is part of the international system for responding to sudden-onset emergencies.

The UNDAC system was originally established in 1993 by the United Nations (UN) and the International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) to ensure effective coordination between national disaster management agencies and incoming search and rescue teams in large-scale and sudden-onset emergencies.

Today, UNDAC teams are not only deployed in sudden-onset disasters, but also provide valuable support in protracted crises, technological and other emergencies, and play an increasingly important role as a tool and service of the United Nations to support governments in the event of disasters.

UNDAC teams can be deployed at short notice (12-48 hours) anywhere in the world. They are provided free of charge to the disaster-affected country and are deployed at the request of the UN Resident or Humanitarian Coordinator and/or the affected government.

Assessment, coordination and information management are the primary mandates of UNDAC in an emergency response mission. UNDAC teams establish and manage the On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (OSOCC) to help coordinate the international Urban Search and Rescue

¹⁸ World Health Organization Emergency response framework. 2017. ISBN 978-92-4-151229-9. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

(USAR) teams responding to the disaster, which is essential for USAR assistance to function effectively.

COMPONENTS

The UNDAC system consists of four components:

- **Staff:** Experienced emergency managers placed at the disposal of UNDAC missions by their respective governments or organisations. UNDAC members are specially trained and equipped for their task.
- **Methodology:** Predefined methods for establishing coordination structures and for organising and facilitating assessments and information management during the first phase of a disaster or sudden-onset emergency.
- **Procedures:** Proven systems to mobilise and deploy an UNDAC team to arrive at the disaster or emergency site within 12-48 hours of the request.
- **Equipment:** Personal and mission equipment to make UNDAC teams self-sufficient in the field when deployed for disasters/emergencies.

LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT OF UN TEAMS

In UNDAC teams, the idea of collective or shared leadership is promoted by the whole team, although it is differentiated, especially in larger missions:

- UNDAC Team Leader has a more external role, aimed at supporting the Government, the RC/HC and the HCT.
- Deputy Team Leader/OSOCC Manager has a more internal role, focusing on the functioning, processes and procedures of the team.

The distinction is far from clear-cut and there may be a number of overlaps. Both roles should incorporate elements of the other, while remaining mindful of their respective overall responsibilities. Managing the details of the internal work processes of an UNDAC team is usually the responsibility of the deputy team leader or OSOCC manager.

OSOCC

The On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (OSOCC) is a rapid response tool that provides a platform for the coordination of international response activities in the immediate aftermath of a sudden-onset emergency or a rapid change in a complex emergency.

It is both a methodology and a physical location for on-site emergency response coordination. The OSOCC has two main objectives:

- Provide a means to rapidly facilitate cooperation, coordination and information management on the ground between international responders and the government of the affected country in the absence of an alternative coordination system.
- Establish a physical space and act as a single point of service delivery for incoming responders.

The OSOCC generally reports to the UNDAC Team Leader, who in turn ensures that OSOCC activities are aligned with the strategic direction of the RC/HC and the Humanitarian Country Team (HCT) and are supported by OCHA.

The OSOCC works in support of the affected government in coordinating the efforts of international response organisations. Within the affected country, the Local Emergency Management Authority (LEMA) is responsible for the overall command, coordination and management of the response operation, so the OSOCC maintains a strong liaison with the LEMA throughout the operations.

In addition to the entities within OCHA and within the affected country, the OSOCC supports and collaborates with cluster coordinators and response teams. This can be done through integration into the OSOCC structure, including physical location in OSOCC facilities, and/or through formal or informal liaison.

Figure 37 - UNAC global organization¹⁹

Location of the OSOCC

The location of the OSOCC should ideally be close to the disaster site, the LEMA and other agencies/organisations providing humanitarian assistance. This will facilitate cooperation and information sharing. The site should also maximise the effective use of communications equipment, e.g. on higher ground and not surrounded by hills or other natural obstacles, and should have effective slope and drainage. Consideration should be given to a location that facilitates appropriate security procedures, including ease of access and evacuation and an easily guarded perimeter.

It is important to note that some coordination cells may need to be forward located to minimise the time between the onset of the disaster and the operational activities of the response teams. This is especially true for Operations Function cells involved in life-saving activities such as USAR and EMT.

Structure of the OSOCC

¹⁹ UNITED NATIONS DISASTER ASSESSMENT AND COORDINATION. UNDAC. Field Handbook. UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. 2018. https://www.unocha.org/sites/unocha/files/1823826E_web_pages.pdf

The OSOCC is generally structured into four functions, each of which may be composed of multiple cells. Not all functions or cells may be necessary in every situation.

- Function: refers to a broad organisational component of the OSOCC, i.e. Management, Situation, Operations, Support. These functions should be considered for each OSOCC mission and at each stage of the mission.
- Cells: are components under functions that can be used to further organise the OSOCC into common subgroups reflecting the key areas of responsibility for that function.

OSOCC staff will be drawn from the UNDAC team, OCHA, OSOCC support staff, international organisations, USAR teams, EMTs and non-governmental organisations (NGOs).

Figure 38 - OSOCC structure²⁰

UNDAC MISSION SOFTWARE (UMS)

The UNDAC Mission Software (UMS) supports UNDAC teams allowing them to collaborate remotely, produce, share and archive documents using one single space, synchronizing in a local area network or over the internet.

It also provides access to key standard guidance and templates to be used on mission (called the UNDAC Toolbox) and can be used when offline.

The UMS user manual is available at:

<http://portal.undac.org/pssuportal/portalrest/filessharing/download/public/wwfVZOw5ry8RqBq>

²⁰ UNITED NATIONS DISASTER ASSESSMENT AND COORDINATION. UNDAC. Field Handbook. UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. 2018. https://www.unocha.org/sites/unocha/files/1823826E_web_pages.pdf

5.3.2. State of the art

Command and control are established through statutory authorities, typically in the form of a disaster management **law** or similar act aimed at **civil protection**. However, the establishment of command and control does not guarantee their effectiveness. Systems for command and control must be instituted, taught to those who will use them, and exercised. Although several terms are used to describe these systems and their various components, the fundamental components are consistent wherever they are found throughout the world.

The command structure must create and establish workable command relationships throughout the chain of command, and provide a clear definition of the functions to be performed at each echelon within that chain of command. This national Command and Control structure can be considered as having four command levels; namely National, Strategic, Operational, and Tactical.

Command and Control (abbr. C2) is a set of organizational and technical attributes and processes that use human, physical, information and other resources to solve problems and accomplish (rescue) missions in order to save lives, health, property and important values of particular entity.

Planning, Organizing, Leading and controlling loop represents the outline of the decision-making process in any type of situation in which Command shall decide on objectives, the tasks required to achieve them and the resources needed to do so.

Figure 39 - Outline of the decision-making process

From Planning stage it is an exercise itself for Emergency Command which a set of information is required in order to manage and deploy as fast as possible the resources and choose in a correct way which will be essential for first rescue services.

Gathering all the information increasing the situational awareness for coordination. The forecast of how it will evolve, the knowledge of human and material resources, the setting of objectives and the distribution of resources to achieve the objectives.

Organize comprises the selection and structuring of the operational resources needed to meet the objectives set out in the planning stage. It is setting up different emergency bodies to which are assigned specific missions aimed at achieving the established objectives.

The next stage of the emergency management process is that of directing, which comprises the set of orders and instructions given by the Commander for the development of operations. Within this stage, and due to the high stress involved in emergency situations, the facilitating actions for the achievement of the following characteristics are of special importance such as: motivation, communication, leadership and delegation of authority.

As the intervention of the emergency services it is deployed, the Emergencies Commanders will check new information of the situation and the results from first decisions. This is the fourth stage of the process, control, which is simultaneous with the intervention stage and shall be permanent, since the feedback that the Emergencies Commanders continuously receives allows to check the effectiveness of their decisions or if there are suggestions to modify them because they do not correspond to the real evolution of the situation. In fact, the control stage must be linked to a review stage, when the intervention orders issued at the beginning of the process do not give the expected result, either because new unknown factors appear, or because the troops present are not sufficient or for any reason, it will be necessary to change the initial plan, revising the objectives and the intervention orders, thus linking back to the planning stage.

The differential factor for this sort of activities following the cycle proposed above is time. In emergency situations in command and control it works against us. Therefore, we have to optimize and try to harmonize the available resources and make an adequate use of the information available to the coordinators of the emergency agencies.

The command and control platforms and applications have numerous tools that provide a guide to help coordinators. Depending on the type of incident, the software recommends which agencies may be involved depending on the type of incident, the final decision will always be up to the operator. In the emergency coordination centre of the community of Madrid they use GEMMA software for incident management which has an automation of some decision processes such as:

- **Teletranslator:** Attending the call in 80 different languages
- **Adaptive system for hearing impaired people:** The call that have been discharged is converted into SMS (chat with the caller)
- **GIS Location:** Mobile call and through triangulation have the area. It allowed us to focus.
 - AML Project (European Project): Location of all cell phones through the deployment of the total set of antennas present.
- **Inverse 112 system:** By zones, send mass alerts (USA present). The population will receive a message whoever is in that area.
- **Typification Incident questions:** To be performed in order to make the activation. They have been reduced.
 - 1) What does the caller communicate?
 - 2) What do the emergency services need in order to be activated?
 - 3) Categorization. In order for the manager to have a quick emergency call sign. When the categorization is transferred to the emergency services. Prioritize resources only with the code you are reading.
 - 4: It is a test

- 3: It is a query or information
 - 2: It is an emergency (traffic accident)
 - 1: It is an emergency with injured (yellow level)
 - 0: It is a catastrophe.
- **Emergency points of interest:** The most significant points are noted or introduced for a correct management of the emergency. It evaluates in an agile way environments such as theatres, shopping centres, etc. Also to locate people who do not know where they are. For example, subway stops, bus stops, etc.
 - **Associate file by incident number:** Traceability. File for each call
 - **Calls:** If you receive a call where there is an open incident, the SW recommends you to associate that call to that incident (it is probably the same one).

For example in Slovakia current coordination centres and their interconnection with operational centres is provided by information system called CoordCom, which is customized to specific requirements of the Integrated Rescue System in Slovakia. The installed system represents communication centre solution with integrated call reception and dispatching. CoordCom integrates functions for telephone, radio as well as data communication between incidents notifiers, operators and other means, such as police, fire brigade and rescue corps, rescue medical service and other service providers.

The CoordCom system has 3 applications: (1) CoordCom Operator – provides support in solving various types of incidents, assists the operator in managing of incoming calls, classifies calls, obtains information and acts according to plan. (2) CoordCom Business Administrator – this application is used for configuration of the system and its behaviour. (3) CoordCom Education is used for training purposes.

The main objective for VALKYRIES is to identify which command and control tools are currently available. In addition, we will evaluate, analyse and investigate which alternatives at the operational level are in the development stages to meet the needs of the first responders described in the requirements and in the surveys sent during this first version of the deliverable.

5.3.2.1. C2 Mechanism at EU level

A **Community Civil Protection Mechanism** was established by Council Decision 2001/792/EC, Decision No. 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a UCPM strengthens cooperation between the Union and the Member States and facilitates coordination in the field of civil protection in order to improve the Union's response to natural and man-made disasters.

The **Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC)** is the heart of the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. It coordinates the delivery of assistance to disaster-stricken countries, such as relief items, expertise, civil protection teams and specialised equipment. The centre ensures the rapid deployment of emergency support and acts as a coordination hub between all EU Member states, the 6 additional Participating States, the affected country, and civil protection and humanitarian experts. The ERCC operates 24/7 and can help any country inside or outside EU. The ERCC can liaise directly with the national civil protection authorities of the country in need.

The **Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS)** enables communication and sharing of information between the ERCC and the contact points of the

Member States and of other participants in the context of the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism. The CECIS shall include the following three components:

- A network layer, connecting the competent authorities and the contact points in Member States and the ERCC
- An application layer, consisting of the databases and other information systems necessary for the functioning of the Union Mechanism and in particular those needed:
 - for communicating notifications
 - for ensuring communication and information sharing between the ERCC and competent authorities and the contact points
 - for disseminating lessons learnt from interventions
- A security layer, consisting of the set of systems, rules and procedures necessary for ensuring the authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of the data stored in and exchanged via the CECIS

The European Civil Protection community shares operational challenges and similar approaches to managing disaster, while the structure and composition of emergency services in the 33 countries varies from country to country. Under the UCPM, countries stand ready and prepared to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced.

5.3.2.2. C2 Mechanism at national level

After reviewing C2 mechanism separately in EU countries, each country's Command and Control is based on different either Law, Act, Doctrine, Constitution, etc. under specific Ministries.

AUSTRIA

Disaster prevention is controlled at the national level by the responsible federal ministries in cooperation with the federal states and municipalities. The main responsibility for disaster response lies with the federal states. The legal basis for response is provided by the disaster relief acts of the federal states, which determine the declaration of the state of disaster and the operational direction of response at municipal, district, and federal state level. Operational capacities are mainly provided by voluntary response organisations (fire brigades, Red Cross, mountain rescue and others), which act as governmental services in the event of a disaster. On the national level, the responsibility for disaster management coordination lies with the Ministry of the Interior. Coordination is ensured by a national coordinating committee which is chaired and managed by the Ministry of the Interior. The Ministry of the Interior is also responsible for cross-border cooperation and international disaster relief.

Emergency response refers to all measures taken by authorities, response organisations, enterprises, individuals and affected parties to mitigate the consequences of an emergency or disaster. The goal is to ensure public order and security, to rescue victims, to provide basic services, to protect the environment and to start early recovery measures. Disaster response encompasses all measures from the official declaration of a disaster until its end. In most cases, disaster response starts at the local or regional level. At the national level, coordination takes place within the framework of a coordination committee at the Ministry of the Interior.

In Austria, the Federal Alarm Centre (FAC) at the Operations and Coordination Centre is the 24/7 contact point for international requests for assistance in cases of disaster.

Department II/13 of the MOI represents Austria in the committees and working groups in the framework of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism and is the national coordination point in the case of assistance. The Federal Alarm Centre (FAC) at the Operations and Coordination Centre is the permanent contact point for requests for assistance.

BELGIUM

The **National Crisis centre, Ministry of Home Affairs**, is responsible for the coordination of the emergency planning and crisis management policy.

Emergency planning and management in Belgium is implemented at 3 different levels: municipal, provincial, or federal level. At each level generic and risk specific emergency plans are drawn up.

Starting at the federal phase, 3 bodies are activated within the National Crisis centre: an evaluation and assessment, a coordination, and an information cell. Each one contributes to the overall decision process within their respective competence.

At operational level, each emergency is handled by intervention services. Their tasks are divided into 5 so-called disciplines (sectors) within a command post.

Each one of these disciplines is competent/responsible for a specific set of tasks and draws up a mono-disciplinary intervention plan that outlines their own modus operandi.

The 5 disciplines in the Belgian Emergency response are:

- Assistance operations
- Medical, sanitary and psychosocial assistance
- Police tasks
- Logistical support
- Information to the public

BULGARIA

The National Disaster Management System is regulated in the Disaster Protection Act, and disaster protection is carried out at the national, regional, and municipal levels.

The emergency disaster response is organised through the Unified Rescue System, which includes structures of ministries, municipalities, companies, volunteers, and the armed forces.

The **National Operations Centre (NOC)** of the DGFSCP operates as a point of coordination and information for the Unified Rescue System. The NOC is in permanent connection with the 28 Regional Operations Centres in the country.

The NOC carries out around-the-clock duty for the forces and resources of the DGFSCP. It maintains a permanent connection and information exchange on disaster response, fire, and emergencies as a 24/7 national point of contact with the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC), the NATO Situation Centre (SITCEN), the Euro-Atlantic Disaster Response Coordination Centre (EADRCC), and the UN's Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA).

The NOC organises the resource management of the FSCP units involved in the mitigation and eradication of emergencies in 2 or more districts in accordance with the National Disaster Protection Plan and standard operating procedures.

CZECH REPUBLIC

Crisis management is the analysis and evaluation of security risks and planning, organising, implementing and controlling activities undertaken in preparation for crisis situations and their solutions. In the Czech Republic, crises are either defined as related or unrelated to the provision of Defence of the Czech Republic against external attack

The Czech Republic develops the risk assessment, which describes the procedure of risk identification and appoints the most significant ones, including a special part dedicated to the risks with high impact and low probability. To strengthen the response to major emergencies resulting from the most significant risks, the Czech Republic also develops 16 documents in a form of checklist, which describes such an emergency and appropriate measures to ensure an effective response. All the documents are available on the website of the Ministry of Interior - Directorate General of the Fire Rescue Service of Czechia (Moi – DG FRS CR).

The Czech Fire Brigade covers all areas of the Czech Republic. Firefighter units are part of the Integrated Rescue System of the Czech Republic, which is designed to coordinate rescue during emergencies. This system was developed in the Czech Republic in 2001 and includes fire protection units, EMS providers and the police. The Czech Republic is divided into 14 separate territorial areas and each of them is operated by the regional headquarters of the FRS, which administers its regional operational centre. These emergency centres can receive emergency calls from the national emergency number.

DENMARK

The national crisis management system serves to provide government coordination of the response to incidents in Denmark or abroad. It consists of:

- The Government Security Committee
- The Senior Officials Security Committee
- The National Operational Staff (NOST)
- The International Operational Staff (IOS)
- 12 local operational staff with standing members from the police districts (chair), DEMA, the Home Guard, the regions and the municipalities.
- Local incident command, made up of on-scene police, fire & rescue, and health preparedness incident commanders

In Denmark, the fundamental principle of emergency management and response is sector responsibility. This means that the authority or organisation with the daily responsibility for a certain area also has the responsibility for that area in case of an emergency.

The Danish fire and rescue service consists of 24 municipal fire and rescue services, the municipal and national support sites, and the national, regional fire and rescue service under the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA). The municipal fire and rescue services are responsible for initiating immediate emergency response, while DEMA assists at larger or more complex incidents that require specialised equipment or personnel.

As of 1 January 2016, Denmark has 24 municipal fire and rescue services and 6 national emergency management centres.

ESTONIA

Estonia has a decentralised risk management structure. Every ministry is responsible for crisis management in its own area of governance.

The Ministry of the Interior is responsible for internal security policy and coordination and has a central role in risk and crisis management. It also sets internal security legislation and guidelines, coordinates emergency risk management and contingency planning at national level, coordinates risk assessment and planning for the continuous operation of vital services, coordinates emergency management exercises at national level, and supervises a number of agencies including the Rescue Board and the Police and Border Guard. National defence-related activities as well as strategic communication are coordinated by the Government Office.

Crisis committees at the national, regional and local level monitor national crisis management, including emergency preparedness and response.

Emergency response is based on a system divided into 4 levels and 4 stages. Levels show rescue capability and resources; stages assess the complexity of a rescue event. On the order of the Emergency Centre, 1 rescue team responds to a Stage I event, and more teams respond to Stage II, II, III and IV events, respectively. Most of the events require the help of 1 or a few rescue teams. In Estonia, there is a relatively small number of high-level response and rescue works with many teams. The larger number of participating teams also means greater management challenges. The management model is also 4-level.

The Rescue Board's 24/7 readiness is based on 72 professional rescue teams, 4 bomb groups, 118 volunteer rescue teams and a North and East Voluntary Reserve Rescue Team. 300 professional and 200 volunteer rescuers are ready to help people around the clock. Estonia is covered by the rescue network.

FINLAND

In Finland, Rescue Services operate under the Rescue Act (379/2011) and other similar acts. The Department for Rescue Services at the Ministry of the Interior is in charge of the organisation of rescue services at national level, guides and directs rescue services, and coordinates the activities of various ministries and sectors in the field of rescue services and their development. The Department also makes decisions about international assistance.

There are 22 independent regional rescue departments in Finland that provide urgent help in the event of an accident or natural hazard. Annually, the rescue services carry out approximately 100,000 rescue missions. Volunteer fire brigades, contracted with regional rescue departments, play an important role in the rescue services system. They contribute to firefighting and rescue operations and participate in approximately 60% of annual rescue service operations. In addition, there are 53 different voluntary organisations that support the national rescue services authorities in Finland.

Emergency response centres (112) are the first step in the emergency response chain for help and safety in Finland. They receive emergency calls for the rescue, police, and health and social

services, and relay the information they receive to the appropriate assisting authorities or partners. Emergency response centres also advise and guide the caller in first aid and follow-up.

The Emergency Response Centre Agency provides emergency response centre services throughout Finland, except for the Åland Islands. There are 6 emergency response centres in Finland located in Kerava, Kuopio, Oulu, Vaasa, Pori and Turku, with a common headquarters in Pori.

The Emergency Response Centre Administration is an agency under the Ministry of the Interior. The Ministry is jointly responsible for the performance management of the agency together with the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health.

GERMANY

The federal structure of Germany is reflected by its national disaster management system of shared responsibilities between the Federation and the federal states.

“Civil protection” in the general sense of “protection of the population” (“Bevölkerungsschutz”) is an overarching term and comprises 2 different elements: “Katastrophenschutz” and “Zivilschutz”.

According to the Constitution, the federal states (“Länder”) are responsible for disaster management (“Katastrophenschutz”) in times of peace. They have enacted respective disaster management laws, defining - inter alia - the responsible disaster management authorities and delegating several administrative and operational tasks to the regional and local level.

In the case of defence, e.g. in times of war or armed conflict, the Federation is in charge of civil protection (“Zivilschutz”), as laid out in the Federal Civil Protection and Disaster Relief Act (ZSKG).

The Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) is the superior federal government authority for civil protection. It coordinates inter-ministerial collaboration and is generally responsible for national/internal security. The BMI supervises the 2 national civil protection agencies:

- The Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK)
- The Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW)

The operational basis at the local level relies on the volunteer potential of e.g., the fire services, local disaster management authorities and participating relief organisations and the THW.

In case of an incident, the fire brigades and relief organisations form the operational and tactical units for immediate technical and medical assistance at the local level.

When asked for assistance, the Federation may support the local and regional authorities and the Länder with their own operational forces (e.g., the Federal Agency for Technical Relief, the Federal Police, and, with certain limitations regarding the use of weapons, the Armed Forces) and with services provided by The Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance.

According to its legal mandate, the Federal Agency for Technical Relief provides technical assistance within the framework of the Civil Defence Act, i.e., in major disasters, emergencies

and accidents, upon request of the responsible authorities as well as abroad on behalf of the Federation.

GREECE

Structure of the **National Mechanism** (according to Law 4662.2020)

1. The National Mechanism, which is supervised by the **General Secretariat of Civil Protection** (GSCP), is structured and operates operationally through the following structures and functions:

- a) The National Coordination Centre for Crisis Management
- b) Of the Coordinating Bodies of Civil Protection
- c) Of the Regional Business Centres of Civil Protection
- d) The Emergency Management Frameworks

The above (b), (c) and (d) operational structures and functions are supported by the support services of the Independent Directorates of Civil Protection of Regions and the Independent Departments of Civil Protection of Municipalities.

Civil protection in Greece is organised as a coordinated resource system where national, regional and local authorities work together with local and public institutions and services. The Greek bodies responsible for the implementation of civil protection measures include the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP) and several authorities, organisations and institutions, e.g. the ministries, the fire service, the Hellenic police, the armed forces, health authorities, the decentralised administrations, the regions, and the municipalities.

The mission of GSCP is to protect the citizen's life, health and property from natural, technological and other major hazards.

The GSCP studies, plans, organises and coordinates the country's policy concerning issues of public awareness, prevention and confrontation of natural or man-made disasters. It coordinates the actions of the public services and the civil protection volunteers.

The General Secretary for Civil Protection, the regional authorities and the local government authorities are in charge of coordinating all operational forces depending on whether the disaster is general, regional, or local.

Each ministry is responsible for prevention plans and taking preventive structural measures in the area of their competency. GSCP issues circulars with guidelines not only on prevention, but also in preparedness and disaster response.

The National Civil Protection Plan "Xenokrates" (Ministerial Decision no. 1299/2003) sets the national framework for an effective risk management planning and provides for the development of hazard-specific plans at the local, regional and national level.

HUNGARY

The National Directorate General for Disaster Management of the Ministry of Interior is a national law enforcement agency. Its main task is the official prevention of disasters; execution of rescue in civil emergencies; the organisation and management of disaster management; eliminating the consequences; implementation of restoration reconstruction. The Directorate

General is responsible for fire protection and civil protection and can draw from a large asset pool to serve this purpose.

The Directorate General is responsible for civil emergency planning and defence management. It regulates and manages the fire service system, technical rescue, protection, and public information.

The Directorate General maintains extensive international relations based on bilateral agreements. Additionally, it maintains regional training bases, and systems related to telecommunication, IT, and detection. The Directorate General collaborates with law enforcement agencies, the defence forces, and local governments. Finally, it liaises with civil and charitable organisations, educational and scientific institutions, and the media.

The National Directorate General for Disaster Management coordinates the activities of other authorities to prevent emergencies. The National Directorate participates in civil emergency management, planning, defence management, mobilisation of national economy, and state reserve management.

It provides information related to events by operating a duty and operation control system, and activates the forces and assets needed for liquidation. The National Directorate carries out firefighting, technical rescue, protection, information, and alerting local authorities.

ICELAND

The Minister of Justice is the supreme authority for civil protection matters. The Civil Protection and Security Council draws up Government policy on civil protection and security for periods of 3 years at a time. The Council consists of government ministers and their permanent secretaries, representatives of local authorities, heads of critical infrastructure sectors, volunteer organisations, and civil protection organisations. The Prime Minister chairs these meetings. The government's policy on civil protection and security gives an account of the current situation and prospects in civil protection and security matters. This includes prevention and preparedness actions, response and coordination of response plans, recovery, stock levels necessary to ensure the survival of the nation in the case of disasters, the function of public infrastructure and other vital measures that the council considers necessary to achieve the aim of the Civil Protection Act. The National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police/Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management (NCIP/DCPEM) role is to implement measures in accordance with the government's Civil Protection and Security Policy. Icelandic Search and Rescue (ICE-SAR) and the Red Cross are the backbone of civil protection in Iceland Protection.

The National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police maintains a National Crisis and Co-ordination Centre for Civil Protection and is responsible for operating the centre in emergency situations. According to The Civil Protection Act No 82/2008 and regulation No 650/2009 the National Commissioner is responsible for declaring an emergency and alert levels at any given time. This decision is made in consultation with the relevant regional police commissioner and the Minister of Justice is informed. There are 3 levels of activation; uncertainty phase, alert/hazard phase, and emergency/distress phase. The administrative levels of response are on-scene command, area command at local level, and the National Crisis Coordination Centre at national level.

IRELAND

The first response to major emergencies in Ireland is led by the 3 principal emergency services. A Garda Síochána (police force), the ambulance service, the fire service and the Irish coast guard. These principles agencies are responsible for the response to an emergency situation up to and including a major emergency in Ireland. At national level, the Government Task Force on Emergency Planning co-ordinates and oversees the emergency management policy and activities of all government departments and agencies under their aegis. The lead government department has the mandate and responsibility to co-ordinate all national level activity for its assigned emergency. The National Emergency Co-ordination Group is the central government platform established as part of the response to a threatened or ongoing national level emergency and is convened and chaired by the relevant lead government department.

The Office of Emergency Planning, Department of Defence, provides a key support role to the Government Task Force on co-ordination and oversight of emergency planning.

The coordination of a national-level emergency responses is addressed in chapter six of the Strategic Emergency Management National Structures and Framework document. This outlines the function and work of the National Emergency Coordination Group (NECG) that would be convened by the local government department responsible for such national-level responses. The NECG, as a national-level structure, when necessary, would link into the corresponding regional local level structures that are outlined separately under the Major Emergency Management framework and the associated guidelines, which cover a wide range of operational responses.

ITALY

According to **Law 24 February 1992, n. 225 - Establishment of the National Civil Protection Service** the National Civil protection Service is established in order to protect the integrity of life, assets, settlements and the environment from damage or danger of damage resulting from natural disasters, from disasters and other calamitous events. 1. In order to ensure the unitary direction and coordination of the emergency activity is the Civil Protection Operational Committee established. 2. The Committee: a) examines the emergency plans prepared by the prefects pursuant; b) evaluates the news, data and requests from the areas affected by the emergency; c) coordinates the interventions of all the administrations and entities interested in the rescue; d) promotes the application of the directives issued in relation to the priority needs of the areas affected by the emergency. 2. National operational structures of the National Civil Protection Service are: a) the National Fire Brigade as a fundamental component of civil protection; b) the Armed Forces; c) the Police Forces; d) the State Forestry Corps ;e) the national technical services; f) the national scientific research groups referred to in Article 17, the National Institute of Geophysics and other research institutions; g) the Italian Red Cross; h) the structures of the National Health Service; i) voluntary organizations ;l) the National Alpine Rescue Corps-CNSA (CAI).

On the basis of the criteria determined by the National Council of Civil Protection, the operational structures the request of the Civil Protection Department, carry out the activities envisaged by this law as well as support and consultancy tasks for all the administrations making up the National civil protection service.

Clear chain of command: The President of the Council of Ministers, his delegated minister, or the Head of the Department of Civil Protection has the authority to take command of the

management of an emergency situation and coordinate all the resources necessary to deal with it effectively.

Decision-support centres: The *Centri Funzionali*, a network of coordinated decision support centres, work 24 hours a day to make real-time data available to the National Department of Civil Protection and regional governments. This facilitates the sharing of the decision-making process to determine when alerts should be issued and what actions should be taken. The upshot is that when an alert is issued there is no conflict between authorities at central and regional level.

LATVIA

The national disaster management system of Latvia is organised and regulated under the legislative framework of Civil Protection and Disaster Management Law. The law determines the competence of civil protection system and disaster management subjects to ensure the safety and protection of people, the environment and property in case of a disaster or threats.

The civil protection system is a component of the national security system, formed by the state and local government authorities.

The prime minister is responsible for the functioning of the system and the implementation of tasks, while the state fire and rescue service of Latvia, which is subordinate to the ministry of interior management, manages, coordinates, and controls the operation of the system and civil emergency planning.

In the event of a crisis, the crisis management council, led by the prime minister and supported by the crisis management council secretariat, coordinates civil-military cooperation and the operational measures of state administrative institutions to ensure a rapid response and coordination of unified and timely implementation of political decisions. The civil protection commission of the local government cooperation territory, established and managed by the municipal authorities, is responsible for the coordination of civil protection measures in the event of disaster in the relevant administrative territories.

The legislative framework of Civil Protection and Disaster Management Law determines disaster management subjects and their area of responsibility for coordination of disaster management.

LUXEMBOURG

The Minister of Home Affairs is in charge of the organisation, coordination, and implementation of civil security. The mission of civil security in Luxembourg is to protect people, animals, property and the environment against calamitous events and disasters. Civil security includes informing and alerting the population in addition to the preparation and implementation of measures and appropriate means. The Luxembourg Fire and Rescue Corps (Corps grand-ducal d'incendie et de secours (CGDIS)), a public institution established by the law of the 27 March 2018, carries out civil security.

The definition of the term "civil security" delimits the scope of action of the CGDIS in relation to that of the High Commission for National Protection (HCPN), a public body under the remit of

the member of government with responsibility for national protection – the prime minister. In accordance with the law of 28 July 2016, the HCPN has the task of implementing the concept of national protection. This concept consists of preventing and protecting the country and the population against the effects of a crisis. In the event of a crisis, the HCPN manages the measures and actions required to deal with the crisis and its effects. Crisis management is carried out under the responsibility of a crisis unit, which is chaired by a member of the government. The CGDIS and the HCPN work closely together.

The CGDIS is operating the national emergency number 112 and is also the contact point for international emergencies. In the event of emergencies and disasters, the CGDIS leads rescue operations and reports to the Minister of Home Affairs. In case of a national crisis with national impact, the inter-agency coordination is managed by the HCPN.

MALTA

The Civil Protection Department in Malta responds to natural and man-made emergencies in Malta and Gozo. During major incidents, the Civil Protection Council is the coordinating body which facilitates cooperation with other entities such as the Police Corps, the Armed Forces of Malta, other governmental entities and civil society organisations in order to successfully implement the protection of its citizen's life, health and property from major hazards and natural or man-made incidents.

The Civil Protection Act (Chapter 411 of the Laws of Malta) and accompanying Legal Notices help deliver the framework with which the Civil Protection Department assisted with other agencies and is able to ensure the protection of the civilians in Malta.

MONTENEGRO

The field of protection and rescue in Montenegro is regulated with the Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction, Law on Protection and Rescue, Law on Local Governance and plans for protection and rescue against different types of natural and man-made hazards.

The Ministry of the Interior, Rescue and Protection Directorate, is in charge of rescue and risk management, disaster protection and emergency remediation management. This enables unified prevention, preparedness and response to natural, technical, technological, and other disasters.

According to the Law on Protection and Rescue, 3 levels of management and coordination of protection and rescue are established, national, local and entrepreneurial. In addition to the resources of the operational units at the 3 levels, the protection and rescue system in Montenegro relies on the human and material resources of state administration bodies, local self-government units, companies, and other legal entities and individuals, who are obliged to deploy their resources in the events of disasters and major accidents. Resources of the Armed Forces of Montenegro and the Police Directorate also have developed certain capacities for assistance in case of disasters.

For managing and coordinating protection and rescue activities, Montenegro formed the Coordination Team for Protection and Rescue for the territory of Montenegro and the Municipal Protection and Rescue Teams for the municipalities. The Coordination Team for Protection and Rescue includes all the relevant ministers/municipal bodies for protection and rescue and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). The team is headed by the prime minister at the national

level, and by the president of the municipality at the municipality levels. Through those teams, coordination and response is more efficient.

Companies, other legal entities and entrepreneurs performing meteorological and hydrological measurements and observations have the obligation to supply available data and relevant information.

A centralised collection of information and data on all types of risks is done in the Operational Communication Centre 112, which is obliged to inform the relevant stakeholders and citizens to undertake preventive and operational measures.

NORTH MACEDONIA

Protection and rescue in the Republic of North Macedonia is organised as a single system for tracking, preventing, and mitigating consequences caused by natural disasters or other emergencies. The system is regulated by the Protection and Rescue Law. The Law indicates how responsibilities are divided between the participants in protection and rescue activities, including the state, local authorities, private companies, public enterprises, facilities, and services.

Based on the Protection and Rescue Act, rescue organisations have to participate in protection and rescue activities in case of disasters and major accidents.

The Law on Crisis Management regulates all risks management approach from local to national level in crisis management. The crisis management system in the Republic of North Macedonia has been established due to needs for continuous monitoring and assessment of the security risks and dangers.

After a crisis is declared in the country, the Crisis Management Centre takes over the international communication and coordination with international institutions. It coordinates the requests, reception, and distributing of international assistance.

Regarding disaster response resources, the Crisis Management Centre developed a national platform with a database of national resources for cross-border operations. Related institutions declare their own capacities for international disaster response operations.

NORWAY

The Ministry of Justice and Public Security is responsible for emergency response in Norway and for the preservation and development of basic guarantees of the rule of law. Norway's Minister of Justice oversees the Police, which is run by the National Police Directorate.

The **Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB)** reports to the Ministry of Justice and Public Security. Among DSB's responsibilities include local, regional and national preparedness, emergency planning, fire safety, electrical safety, handling and transport of hazardous substances, as well as product and consumer safety.

The **Norwegian Emergency Response Services** comprise a multi-agency collaboration between several organizations from the government, voluntary and private organizations.

The first responder agencies (**police, emergency medical services – EMS, and the fire and rescue services - FRS**) are the main stakeholders when handling an acute crisis, both for agency-specific

and multi-agency operations. These first responder agencies each have their individual Command and Control Centres (C3) with different structures, working processes, and technological tools that are not well integrated. They also have different emergency phone numbers (110 - FRS, 112 - Police and 113 - EMS) however, the different systems include a function to easily route the calls between the centres. In all operations, the main goal for the first responder agencies is saving lives, regardless of their distinct roles which are determined by agency, rank, and type of incident.

To ensure an efficient information sharing process between the three agencies in specific scenarios, Norway implemented a national **triple-alert routine** in 2019.

The triple-alert routine consists of a tool for inquiry and action covering nine scenarios (bomb threat, fire in a building, acute pollution, tunnel accident, ongoing life-threatening violence, a person in the water, accident at sea, avalanche, and traffic accident) and describes when and how triple-alert between the first responders should be initiated and implemented. When the incident requires more resources, other relevant organizations, such as voluntary organizations and the affected municipality/-ies, may be contacted. However, these organizations are not included in the triple-alert routine.

An important tool for supporting collaboration is the **Norwegian Public Safety Network (NPSN)** implemented in 2015, which is a common emergency radio network platform for secure collaborative communication between all organizations involved in rescue and emergency management.

The lack of access to NPSN for several stakeholders in the crisis operation was found to be challenging, and many of the involved actors argued for the need for broader access to the NPSN to secure enhanced communication flow.

POLAND

The act on crisis management establishes the composition and functioning of the crisis management system and specifies the tasks to be conducted by the state administration and territorial self-government units at all levels.

The leading crisis management authority is the Council of Ministers. In urgent situations, this responsibility lies with the Minister of Interior and Administration.

The leading civil protection authority is the National Headquarters of the State Fire Service (KG PSP) which is subordinate to the Minister of Interior and Administration.

The Chief Commandant of the State Fire Service also acts as the Chief of the National Civil Defence.

The leading risk assessment and planning is the Government Centre for Security (RCB) which is subordinate to the Prime Minister.

The National Firefighting and Rescue System (KSRG) is a network of professional and voluntary rescue services, supplemented with numerous agreements with agencies, associations and other entities. The KSRG is managed by professional firefighters. It is organised in such a way that provides for satisfactory response times, backup for larger or simultaneous emergencies, as well as expertise and capacities for rare types of emergencies.

PORTUGAL

The **National Civil Protection Emergency Plan (PNEPC)** is an instrument to support civil protection operations in the event of imminence or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe in mainland Portugal. As defined in the Basic Law of Civil Protection, this Plan is classified as general, in terms of purpose, and as national, as to the geographic area of coverage.

According to PNEPC, The National Command Structure (CNOS) is responsible for monitoring and managing all occurrences in the national territory. During the activation period of the PNEPC, the National Command Post must be activated and is responsible for the management of all civil protection and relief operations directly resulting from the serious accident or catastrophe that gave rise to the activation of the PNEPC and for the activation of all national means for the proposal to activate complementary means at an international level. After that CNOS remains in operation to monitor other occurrences.

National Command Post – main missions: 1) ensuring command, control, communication and information, 2) ensuring the minimization of loss of life, 3) ensure that adequate emergency psychosocial support is provided, 4) guarantee the safety of all the forces involved, 5) guarantee the safety of citizens with reduction of number of casualties to minimum, 6) guarantee the access control and maintenance of emergency circulation corridors, 7) ensuring the effective execution of population movement operations, 8) ensure adequate medical care is provided, 9) ensure the coordination of public health, 10) ensure the coordination of emergency assistance and resource management, 11) ensure the prompt cleaning of communication routes, 12) coordinate the action of reconnaissance teams and terrestrial and aerial assessment, 13) directing and coordinating the use of the means under their responsibility.

National Command Post is organized into following cells:

- Command Cell
- Communication and Command Cell
- Planning and Operations Cell
- Operational Response Cell
- Command Support Logistics Cell
- Technological Resources Cell
- Specialized Technical Advisory Cell

REPUBLIC OF CROATIA

The Government of Croatia manages the activities of the civil protection members operating in disasters, with the support of the Civil Protection Headquarters.

The Government, following a proposal of the competent minister, can adopt a decision to request and receive international assistance, or to provide assistance to other countries affected by disasters.

Measures and activities in the civil protection system are implemented by the following participants:

- The Government of the Republic of Croatia
- The Ministry of the Interior, as the central state body competent for civil protection activities

- State administration bodies and other government authorities
- Armed forces of the Republic of Croatia and the police
- Units of local and county (regional) self-government.

The Civil Protection Headquarter (HQ) is an operational and coordinating body. When disasters strike, it oversees and coordinates activities of the civil protection operational forces in the preparatory phase (before the emergency) and during the implementation of civil protection measures and activities.

The HQ is established at the national level, and at the level of units of local and county (regional) self-governments.

The Civil Protection Headquarter consists of representatives of relevant sectors from public administration bodies, operational forces of the civil protection system, and representatives of other legal entities of special importance for the civil protection system of the Republic of Croatia.

County civil protection headquarters have been established at the regional level and there are 21 in total (20 counties and the City of Zagreb).

As a rule, the Head of the Civil protection HQ and the deputy Head of the Civil protection HQ are appointed from the operational forces of the civil protection system, deputies of executive bodies and heads of administration bodies of the units of local and county (regional) self-government.

REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS

According to legislation, the Civil Defence Force is organised as civil defence units in almost all urban areas, which are mainly staffed by conscripts and volunteers. The Cyprus Civil Defence members, who are apportioned among the various units, receive basic training and are later trained and positioned in different divisions of the Civil Defence. These different divisions are first aid, the telecommunication section, the welfare section, the rescue and fire-fighting section, and the neighbourhood watch section.

The Council of Ministers approves the General Civil Defence Plan, which defines the role, duties, and responsibilities of all components of the civil defence system. According to these roles, duties and responsibilities, each component of the civil defence system (mainly the "essential services") has to elaborate civil defence plans to deal with contingencies, which may arise due to natural hazards or manmade disasters.

According to the ZENON plan that the Council of Ministers approved, relevant services had to prepare specific national plans concerning the range of disasters. The plans provide for different levels of activation according to the size of the disaster. When the event is deemed to be a large-scale disaster, a special ministerial group convenes to coordinate the measures taken to address the disaster.

ROMANIA

At national level, the National Committee for Special Emergency Situations – CNSSU (inter-ministerial body), is responsible for emergency management. The CNSSU is headed by the

Minister of Internal Affairs and is composed of ministers and directors of central public administration.

At strategic level, the Department for Emergency Situation (DSU) has coordinating powers for prevention and management of emergencies, ensuring and coordinating the human, material, financial and other resources necessary to cope with emergencies, including qualified first aid and emergency medical assistance within emergency units and emergency compartments.

In December 2004, the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations (IGSU) was created by merging the Military Fire-fighters Corps and the Civil Protection Command, under the Ministry of Internal Affairs. IGSU is managed by a General Inspector. As integrator of the National Emergency Management System, a concept created also in 2004, IGSU coordinates all institutions involved in the process of emergency management and also works as national point of contact for all relevant international governmental and non-governmental organisations.

At county level, emergency response is ensured by professionals from the Inspectorates for Emergency Situations Bucharest and 40 county inspectorates under the command of the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations. They also provide – at county level – guidance and control of prevention measures and management of emergencies.

According to the type and complexity of emergencies, the County Inspectorates cooperate with all institutions with responsibilities in emergency response (defence, public order and national safety, public administration) in order to ensure an efficient response.

112 is the single number for emergency calls available free of charge, which can be called from all fixed or mobile networks. Citizens in emergency situations can call 112, to request assistance from services (ambulance, Mobile Emergency Service for Resuscitation and Extrication, police, fire brigades, gendarmes).

SLOVAKIA

Crisis management system in the Slovak Republic is divided geographically, with each level of public administration playing its part in the system. The aim of civil protection is to protect lives, health, and property. The Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic cooperates with other state authorities, self-governing regions, municipalities, legal entities, individuals and with public-legal institutions with the humanitarian mission that in case of emergency are deployed in rescue operations. It also participates in rescue operations and evacuation in situations stipulated in the Act on Civil Protection.

Regional departments of civil protection and crisis management (at the district offices) plan, manage, and provide the activities relative to the protection of civil population in the case of an emergency. The most important tasks of municipalities on their territory are the following: development of analysis of possible emergency events, preparing plans of protection of the population, organisation and control of civil protection training, oversee and control rescue operations on their territory, planning, controlling and implementation of the declaration of population evacuation.

Local authorities are primarily responsible for emergency response on emergencies in their territory. The mayor of the affected municipality is the head of rescue operations, the head of the district is responsible for response on district and regional level. Emergency response is carried out by first responders who are coordinated by the Integrated Rescue System, which is composed of the Fire and Rescue Service; the Emergency Medical Service; the Mountain Rescue Service; the Mine Rescue Service; the Control Chemical Laboratories, which are supported by local, corporate and volunteer fire fighting corps; the Armed Forces of the Slovak Republic, the Slovak Red Cross, and other civil protection units. Intervention from national level is provided whenever the emergency is a large-scale event (more than 2 counties are affected) or national capacities from state reserves need to be deployed to assist the rescue operations.

The **Slovak Emergency Response System** is by law (Law No. 129/2002 Col. of laws of Integrated Rescue System) named as **Integrated Rescue System** and is a coordinated approach of its components to ensure their readiness and to carry out activities and measures related to providing assistance in emergency situations.

IRS operating centres operates **emergency call line 112**, deploys rescue forces, manage and coordinates rescue operation. It is recognized as “Operational (tactical) C2”, also known as “**Emergency Call Centre**” and on regional level “**Coordination Centre**”.

SLOVENIA

Disaster management (civil protection) in Slovenia is organised as an integrated system, which includes various parties: rescue units and services (professional and voluntary, civil protection), humanitarian organisations, research institutions, other organisations and governmental administrative bodies. The unified system is based on humanitarian principles and in line with international standards. The system is regulated by the Act on Protection against Natural and Other Disasters and other sector specific acts. It addresses all phases of the cycle: prevention, preparedness, response to disasters, and recovery.

The responsibilities for the disaster management system lie with the government, local communities, commercial companies, and citizens. The system is based on a bottom-up approach and systematic (subsidiary) principle.

The national authority responsible for disaster management is the Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief (ACPDR) within the Ministry of Defence.

Operational command and coordination are carried out at different levels. In cases of minor accidents, commanders of individual protection and rescue units command the response (incident commanders).

The management of the response in major accidents or disasters is in the hands of civil protection commanders and their staff at municipal or regional levels. In case of major disasters, the civil protection commander of the Republic of Slovenia manages the response, and he is directly accountable to the government. He is assisted by the Civil Protection Headquarters, which is formed by the members of various respective ministries, experts from different fields and heads of different protection and rescue units.

SPAIN

As a fundamental instrument of public security, the organisation, functioning, and implementation of civil protection is carried out by the different public administrations and by other entities involved in the risk management.

The Ministry of Interior is the highest authority in charge of Spanish Civil Protection. The Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) plays an essential role at national level.

Law 17/2015 on the National Civil Protection System (NCPS) ensures the coordination, cohesion, and efficiency of civil protection (CP) public policies. It also regulates the competences of the State General Administration on this matter. The NCPS integrates all public or private organisations and institutions, and citizens participating in CP activities.

Emergency situations imply the mobilisation of human and material resources. These belong to public administrations – national, regional and local – along with public institutions, private entities and citizens.

Autonomous communities are responsible for the direction and coordination of the emergencies in their territory, unless declared as a national emergency.

The cooperation of the various entities responsible for civil protection at both national and supranational level is key for joint action in the field of prevention, planning and disaster response.

The CP system is based on four key pillars: a comprehensive and actionable legal framework, the coordinating bodies, CP planning and training activities.

When an emergency occurs at local level, the local territorial plan is activated and local resources are used. This is considered a level one emergency situation.

If the emergency escalates and the local level is unable to tackle with the situation, the autonomous community CP plan is activated and the emergency management responsibility is taken over by the community's CP authority, which also provides its own resources. This is a level two emergency situation.

However, if the situation overcomes the capacity of the autonomous community or in case of nuclear emergency or war situation, or if it affects other autonomous communities, the Minister of Interior may declare a national emergency and take over the overall coordination of the activities. This is a level three emergency situation.

In all emergency situations, the national level is in charge of requesting international assistance to the Union Civil Protection Mechanism and/or under the umbrella of the bilateral agreements.

SWEDEN

The Swedish system for disaster management is based on an all-hazards approach. The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) facilitates coordination of measures for prevention, preparedness and response, across sectors and levels of government.

The responsibility for crisis and disaster management resides at national, regional, and local levels.

The crisis and emergency management system is based on 3 principles. The principle of responsibility that means that actors retain their ordinary responsibilities in situations of crisis and disaster. This principle also includes a responsibility to support other involved parties as necessary. The principle of proximity that means that crises and disasters should be managed as close as possible to those primarily concerned. The principle of similarity, which means that the methods and structures used in crisis and disaster management, should be as similar as possible to those used in normal circumstances. The geographical responsibility to manage an event lies with those parties most directly affected. The rescue services are organised at the local level.

In the Swedish disaster management system municipalities and country administrative boards have respective responsibilities within their geographical areas. On a local level, this entails a responsibility to maintain services like water distribution, schools and rescue services during crises, while the county administrative board primarily has a regional coordinating role. As a national agency, the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency's (MSB) operative assignment is to coordinate, support and facilitate involved parties in response to accidents, crises and emergencies, nationally and internationally. MSB can provide additional resources to municipalities and county administrative boards and other countries, EU and the UN in the form of materials or competency. MSB has registered a number of national capacities within the European Emergency Response Capacity.

5.3.2.3. Standards and methodology

As starting point is the different abbreviations used in the context of command and control; thus, is interesting to know C2 Command & Control, C3 Consultation, C3I Communications and Intelligence, C4 Computers, C4ISR Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance. C4ISTAR Intelligence, Surveillance, Target Acquisition and Reconnaissance²¹. Command and Control inside context VALKYRIES correspond to C2.

Facing different disaster threats, command and control should resolve the next challenges to build a correct coordination response²²:

- Authority. Identify who is in charge between principal actors
- Information. Useful data to resolve and take decisions
- Needs. Comprehensive needs for the country who suffers the disaster,
- Analysis of the situation. Taking account standard differences between equal professionals, institutions and/or countries and additionally political considerations should be considered
- Strategy. This strategy depends on the analysis and requires role assignment and responsibilities.
- Logistic. Define standards logistic protocols for resources and communications.
- Cultural differences. Recognise different goals for all participants from bottom to up making decisions.
- Resources. Assignment of resources and coordination about responsibility for them

²¹ Delgado JL. Command and Control Systems and their humanitarian-aid function. Verteidigung und Sicherheit. <https://www.gmv.com/de-de/node/4262/printable/print>

²² Hedström L et al. Command, control and coordination in international relief operations. Exercise Bogorodsk 02. Noginsk, Russia, 2002. <https://www.nato.int/eadrcc/bogorodsk/d021216c.pdf>

To operate command and control exist some tools:

- Virtual OSOCC. Virtual Disaster Alert and Coordination System
- GDACS. Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System
- CIMIC. Civil-Military Cooperation Centre of Excellence
- OCHA-UNDAC. United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. UN Disaster Assessment and Coordination.
- Copernicus Emergency Management Service

5.3.3. Landscape

The following items have been consulted in the WP5 questionnaire in relation to this section Command and Control:

- Crisis Emergency Operations Centre:
 - Available?
 - Involved Emergency Agencies (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
 - Other Involved Emergency Agencies (Free text)
- General Incident Command Responsibility (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other General Incident Command Responsibility (Agency) (Free text)
- On Scene Global Command (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other On Scene Global Command (Agency) (Free text)
- On Scene Rescuers Command (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other On Scene Rescuers Command (Agency) (Free text)
- On Scene General Medical Command (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other On Scene General Medical Command (Agency) (Free text)
- Medical Command Responsibility (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other Medical Command Responsibility (Agency) (Free text)
- On Scene Security Command (Agency) (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Other On Scene Security Command (Agency) (Free text)
- Perception of needs: (Free text). Needs/shortcomings existing in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

Following the analysis of the questionnaires/surveys during the Valkyries project WP5 execution, the Landscape picture on operational/workflows/engaged roles and practices in COP organization procedures and between different countries is as in the following table:

Items	Most common answers in the survey	Homogeneity between countries
Crisis Emergency Operations Centre (EOC) Available?	Yes	Very High
Emergency Agencies involved in the EOC	EMS = Police > Firefighters > Civil Protection > Rescuers > Red Cross = Army	High
General Incident Command Responsibility (Agency) at EOC	Firefighters > Civil Protection > Police > Rescuers = EMS > Army = Red Cross	High
On Scene Global Command (Agency)	Firefighters > Police > Civil Protection = Rescuers > EMS = Red Cross > Army	High
On Scene Rescuers Command (Agency)	Firefighters > Rescuers > EMS > Red Cross > Others	Very high
Medical Command Responsibility (Agency) at EOC	EMS > Others > Firefighters	Very high
On Scene General Medical Command (Agency)	EMS > Rescuers > Red Cross > Others	Very high
On Scene Security Command (Agency)	Police > Army > Firefighters > Rescuers	Very high

Table 8 - WP5 questionnaire: Command and Control answers

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS:**EMERGENCY OPERATIONS CENTER (EOC)**

In approximately 77% of the cases there is an Emergency Operations Center (EOC) available for overall crisis coordination. The proportion is higher in the case of agencies potentially involved in cross-national emergency response.

Figure 40 - Emergency Operations Center (EOC) availability

In general, the presence of EMS and police in the EOCs is almost constant, and the presence of firefighters and, to a lesser extent, Civil Protection is also in the majority.

On the other hand, the integration of the army in the same EOCs is rare, as well as that of rescue groups or NGOs such as the Red Cross.

Figure 41 - EOC: involved emergency services

GENERAL INCIDENT COMMAND AT THE EOC AND ON SCENE

Depending on the characteristics of the disaster, General Incident Command Responsibility at the Emergency Operations Center (EOC) involves firefighters in the highest percentage of cases (57% approximately), with a large difference between agencies potentially involved in cross-border disaster response (85%) and those that are not (28%).

In 50% of the cases this responsibility involves Civil Protection, with no major differences in relation to the possible cross-national activity of the agency surveyed.

On fewer occasions the responsibility falls to the police (35%), and exceptionally to emergency Medical Services (EMS), rescuers, the military or the Red Cross.

Figure 42 - Agency responsible for General Incident Command in the EOC according to the Emergency Response Plan

Figure 43 - Agency responsible for general Incident Command in the EOC according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

When the distribution of responsibilities in the field is analyzed, a different profile is found in the attribution of the Global Incident Command at the scene of the disaster. At the disaster site, depending on the type of accident, the percentage of cases in this global command responsibility falls to firefighters increases to over 78%, but the percentage of Civil Protection (just over 21%) drops significantly to the benefit of the Police (approximately 43%). This difference in favor of firefighters is further accentuated when we look at the results for agencies with potential responsibility for cross-national incident response, reaching 100% in our surveys.

No significant changes were observed in relation to EOC / on scene global incident command in the other emergency services surveyed.

Figure 44 - Agency responsible for on scene General Incident Command in disasters

Figure 45 - Agency responsible for on scene General Incident Command according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

RESCUE COMMAND

Rescue command at the disaster site falls mostly on firefighters (more than 78%), and in approximately 29% of cases on other rescuers or EMS. Other agencies would have a very occasional role in the command of rescue operations, limited to cases without cross-national involvement.

Figure 46 - Agency responsible for ON SCENE Rescue Command according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

MEDICAL COMMAND

As expected, when the responsibility for the command of the medical care of the victims is analyzed, it is almost unanimously agreed that it falls on the Emergency Medical Services, both in the EOC and at the accident site.

It should be noted the participation of rescuers in the medical command at the accident site, although it does not reach 15%.

Figure 47 - Agency responsible for Medical Command in disasters according to the Emergency Response Plan

SECURITY COMMAND

Also following logic, security command at the disaster scene generally involves the police (approximately 86%) and to a lesser extent the army (just under 29%). In a minority of cases this command responsibility may also involve firefighters or other rescuers.

There are no differences between agencies with or without potential responsibility for responding to cross-national disasters.

Figure 48 - Agency responsible for on scene Security Command according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

5.3.4. Perception of needs

As result of the questionnaire survey, there is a need for better cross-agency, cross-sectorial and cross-border C2 communication. When managing incidents or disaster of various type and size, communication between different involved elements (e.g. agencies, ministries, countries) is crucial. The goal it to harmonize standards for fluent, on-time, flexible and smooth communication between all elements. In connection with other WPs within VALKYRIES project firstly technical aspects should be ensured, of course personal capacities and based on those the C2 communication can be provided in proper way. It means that firstly at national level EU countries should harmonize standards to build a base for unified standards afterwards implemented in each country.

The main problem is coordination of different institutions between different regions. Standards and procedures between emergency agencies are not completely unified and interconnected. It is also important to point out that technology and systems are old and outdated.

Even though EU Civil Protection Mechanism provides a sound broad framework for common practices between countries for C2 organization and deployment, practices and workflows reported relay mainly on local procedures, which in most cases are a mixture of Civil and military practices. As a result, workflows within different C2s were reported as poorly standardized and, in most cases, as needed to be supported by more robust training programmes to the engaged personnel of agencies involved in planning or deployment of C2 resources. Communications

standardization and flow of information has been reported as one of the major challenges to improve.

5.4. Common Operational Picture

5.4.1. Introduction

5.4.1.1. *Sharing information in disaster response*

Disaster response will involve multiple actors from different services, with different operational procedures, different command organisation, different technical terminologies, and even speaking different languages.

However, in order to achieve an effective outcome in such a complex situation, all these actors need to work in coordination, in close cooperation with each other and aligned with certain strategic objectives.

The need to collaborate and coordinate efforts is vital as no single agency has sufficient information or resources to address problems alone. To make the right decisions, emergency response organisations must necessarily share accurate and relevant information in a timely and seamless manner, providing them with a common operating picture that allows them to understand what is happening at any given time.

To do so, they must rely on equipment and information systems that help them in their work and that take advantage of the capabilities enabled by the network.

A culture of information sharing between institutions would also facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning, and adaptation and improvisation.

ACTORS INVOLVED IN INFORMATION SHARING IN DISASTERS

In the usual practice of crisis response services in the EU environment, communications, mainly operational but also to a large extent tactical or even strategic, are still based on radio network solutions with voice information transmission. Although these solutions are secure and extensively tested in these contexts, and although they are capable of transmitting information simultaneously to groups and even data, they have a very limited data transmission capacity. As a result, they are insufficient to provide all the information needed to build a common operational picture to understand the dynamics of the disaster and make the best decisions at any given moment.

Seen-Tveit K et al²³ analysed the messages exchanged over the radio network in crisis response drills. The results showed that a large proportion of the messages exchanged belonged to the situation report category: 21% of the messages. However, there were far more situation reports

²³ Steen-Tveit K et al. Analysis of Common Operational Picture and Situational Awareness during Multiple Emergency Response Scenarios. WiPe Paper – Command and Control Studies. Proceedings of the 16th ISCRAM Conference. València, Spain, May 2019.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333449089_Analysis_of_Common_Operational_Picture_and_Situational_Awareness_during_Multiple_Emergency_Response_Scenarios

than confirmations, 16%, and only 7% of common understanding, i.e. confirmations that all emergency managers understand the situation report.

In disaster response, often complementing the above, emergency services also use mobile and fixed telephone networks, with major limitations on information sharing.

To a lesser extent, some decision-support information systems or networked information exchange systems are used. But the current reality is that disaster managers are not sharing their tools and information to the extent that is necessary. Moreover, in this context there is limited use of eHealth technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics or the Internet of Things, which are currently revolutionising standard healthcare.

Deciding exactly what information is or is not shared and with whom is a challenge. Actors know their own information needs and will share them with other emergency responders, but it is a difficult task to capture all the critical data while at the same time knowing and adequately meeting the needs of other agencies.

Seen-Tveit K et al's studies²⁴ found that the security group and the rescue-firefighter group shared information of more varied categories and had a higher frequency of messages between each other than the other actors. This seems to indicate that these two disaster action groups are providing all involved agencies with common information needs, which is natural in complex scenarios involving mass casualties.

The medical group had a lower frequency of message exchange with the other groups. This could perhaps be explained by the fact that it is more focused on victim assistance (triage, stabilisation and evacuation), and that this type of information is not typically information that needs to be shared by the other action groups in order to carry out their objectives.

CHALLENGES IN INFORMATION SHARING IN DISASTER RESPONSE

Organisations are aware of the importance of information exchange for the success of their own organisation and for the effectiveness of the response as a whole. It is also true that they are generally more concerned with obtaining information from others than providing information to them, and that the actual level of information sharing between organisations is still limited.

Faced with the problem of information management, emergency management agencies are interested in developing more advanced and better equipped information systems, on the understanding that these will help responders achieve shared situational awareness through the creation of a common operating picture.

To enable information management, they focus their efforts on building system architectures, which emphasise the need for integration and linking of information, rapid access, time availability, updating of information and standardisation of information. However, the social aspect of sharing and interpreting information is often overlooked: there is a need to first develop a common base of the different expertise of emergency personnel, from which they can

²⁴ Steen-Tveit K et al. Analysis of Common Operational Picture and Situational Awareness during Multiple Emergency Response Scenarios. WiPe Paper – Command and Control Studies. Proceedings of the 16th ISCRAM Conference. València, Spain, May 2019.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333449089_Analysis_of_Common_Operational_Picture_and_Situational_Awareness_during_Multiple_Emergency_Response_Scenarios

understand how different responders interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.

Authors such as Bharosa N et al²⁵ or Reem Abbas MSc, Norris AC et al²⁶ have identified some challenges in relation to effective communication between actors involved in disaster response. Disaster management outcomes will improve when the different barriers are addressed simultaneously at different levels.

Challenges of authority

The relevance of the operational modalities and capacities of each agency responding to disasters has already been discussed in this deliverable. In disaster management, the classic model of highly vertical and hierarchical command and control has limitations that point to the importance of collaborative situational awareness, pooling of knowledge and expertise, and rapid and adaptive decision-making among response groups.

Differences in authority can impose a leadership conflict when responding collectively to situations as complex as a disaster.

Against this classical C2 model, the idea of a facilitative cross-sectoral leadership emerges that would focus management on selecting appropriate agencies and resources, shaping the operational context and developing ways of dealing with strategic and operational complexity.

Organisational challenges

Even within the same organisation, there are differences in the way different groups of professional's value information. For example, depending on the type of tasks for which each group will use this information within the ultimate goals of their common organisation.

EMS first responders will have their own criteria that are likely to be different from those of EMS managers. The two sectors may view an emergency from different perspectives if one is unaware of the other's decision-making criteria.

This situation makes it even more complex to determine what information needs to be communicated between responding agencies to ensure mutual understanding, a complexity that increases exponentially with the increase in the number of agencies involved.

The standardisation of basic concepts, structures and processes in each sector and their proper dissemination and training among potentially involved actors is essential to advance collaborative disaster response.

Challenges of trust

A critical factor for successful inter-agency collaboration is trust. Trust has two interrelated aspects:

²⁵ Bharosa N, Lee J, Janssen, M. Challenges and obstacles in sharing and coordinating information during multi-agency disaster response: Propositions from field exercises. *Inf Syst Front* 12, 49–65 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-009-9174-z>

²⁶ Abbas R, Norris AC et al., *J Int Soc Telemed eHealth* 2018;6:e3. Pinpointing what is wrong with cross-agency collaboration in disaster healthcare. <https://journals.ukzn.ac.za/index.php/JISfTeH/article/view/354>

- Trust in integrity: this refers to trust that the other parties will act with due diligence, will not withhold information, will willingly share necessary information, will commit to respect established data limits.
- Confidence in competence: this refers to the mutual trust that the other party has the capacities, resources and skills to contribute to the partnership in a complementary way.

This trust has to be established at two levels: inter-organisational trust and interpersonal trust. In emergencies and disasters, aspects such as common training or co-location of responders in the same physical location will foster trust.

Trust in each other will alleviate the need for control by focusing your efforts on problem solving.

Situational awareness challenges

Reliable information that facilitates situational awareness, i.e. knowing and recognising what is going on around us, is crucial for good disaster management.

The usual information exchange in these scenarios is usually vertical across organisations to a command centre, where horizontal information exchange for other organisations should be facilitated.

Information that is not relevant to the situational awareness of the team members, in addition to the sender, results in a waste of time and is best filtered out to avoid unwanted "noise".

The challenge is to determine the minimum data sets that need to be communicated during disasters. Deciding what information is relevant and what is not is an extremely difficult but critical task for the developers of information exchange systems between institutions.

Technical challenges

In disaster management, much of the communication is facilitated by technology. And the use of technology in disasters is conditioned by factors such as cost, the complexities associated with its adoption and implementation, the difficulties of technological interoperability, access restrictions due to confidentiality or information security.

The information exchange process should be simplified, as fewer steps mean fewer possible points of failure.

Legislative challenges

There is a legal dimension to the exchange of information that stems from the need to protect the privacy and confidentiality of those affected, and which substantially conditions the exchange of information between organisations involved in the disaster response.

Different jurisdictions and different countries are likely to have different legislation, and even different interpretations of the same laws, on privacy and data protection could occur. However, a common methodology based on technical interoperability may boost legal interoperability in a collaborative disaster response as well. In fact, the emergency circumstances may identify common legal basis to operate: authorities and laws can stimulate the exchange of information between organisations through the implementation of organisational policies and guidelines, by

applying general principles and commonly assessing the impacts on fundamental rights protection

Regarding the technological aspects of C2 coordination, information exchange processes should employ better mechanisms to ensure that relevant information is not leaked during the exchange process.

For this purpose, special co-operation decision making protocols have been introduced by Valkyries following practices that will allow safe data sharing with minimum operational or other risks.

5.4.1.2. *Situational awareness*

SITUATIONAL AWARENESS (SA) is a phenomenon originally described by military aviators to refer to vigilance in observing and deducing events around them. There are many definitions of situational awareness, which could be simplified as "knowing what is going on".

Steenbruggen et al. consider SA to be particularly important in work environments where the flow of information can be quite high and incorrect decisions can lead to disastrous results.

In the face of emergencies, each organisation will generally have established operational procedures and defined communication processes, ensuring the exchange of knowledge necessary for internal decision-making and action within each institution.

But in disaster response, with multi-agency or even transnational implications, several organisations must work towards common goals. The community of responders includes multiple command and control centres for decision-making, and different internal structures for individual and team decision-making within each agency.

Maintaining situational awareness in managing such dynamic and rapid decision-making situations as disasters is critical to success.

Understanding how situational awareness is developed and maintained can guide the design of systems to support decision-making.

Shared understanding in collaborative work has been addressed from several different perspectives in the research literature. Some of these are discussed below.

INDIVIDUAL SA

Individual situation awareness (SA) is derived from the same context as Boyd's C2 model "Observe-Orient-Decide-Act loop" (OODA).

Various definitions of individual SA have been proposed. The most widely accepted definition and model of individual SA is the Endsley three-level model²⁷, which essentially focuses on the perception of the elements of the environment within a volume of time and space, the understanding of their meaning and the projection of their situation in the near future.

The SA therefore consists of:

²⁷ Endsley, M. R. (1988) Design and evaluation for situation awareness enhancement. Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting. SAGE Journals, 32 (2), 97-101. November 2015]. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/154193128803200221>

- **LEVEL 1: PERCEPTION OF THE ELEMENTS OF THE ENVIRONMENT.** This is the perception of the critical factors, i.e. the state, attributes and dynamics of the relevant elements in the environment. In a command and control centre the perceptions would be, for example, the audio and information that can be obtained from technological tools. Factors that can threaten the SA at this level are: failure of the individual to perceive critical signals that are important, system failure, lack of reliable information, lack of an adequate model to speed up data collection, etc.
- **LEVEL 2: UNDERSTANDING THE CURRENT SITUATION.** This is the understanding of the meaning of these elements once they have been synthesised, in light of the decision-maker's objective. Following the above example of a C2 centre, emergency managers would have to gather the information from level 1 and understand it, to make sense of it. At this level, a possible cause of error could be a misinterpretation of the signals by the individual, a misjudgement of whether or not certain signals are important, etc.
- **LEVEL 3: FUTURE STATUS PROJECTION:** This is the prediction of what will happen to the system in the near future. Taken to the example of the C2 centre, experienced emergency managers would be able to project what might happen in the near future. If the individual, despite perceiving the signals and understanding their scope, fails to predict and anticipate situations that may cause further damage.

Higher levels of SA depend on the success of lower levels.

ORGANISATIONAL SA

It is defined by Oomes²⁸ as an understanding of the multiple parts that make up the organisation and how they relate to each other. If the actors involved focus only on their own tasks, adequate SA will not be possible, they must be aware of each other's key elements such as needs, objectives, expectations, culture, capacities and procedures in order to achieve effective cooperation.

Related to Organisational ES, a shared mental model (SMM) would be a mental representation shared by a community of stakeholders of their decision-making processes (objectives, tasks, needs, procedures), in a way that allows:

- Anticipate the needs of other team members
- Anticipate their actions in order to adjust their own behaviour accordingly
- Proactively assist each other in carrying out their tasks

SHARED SA

²⁸ Oomes, A. H. J. (2004) Organization awareness in crisis management. In: Carle, B. and Walle, B.v.d. (eds.) Proceedings of the International Workshop on Information Systems on Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM), 3-4 May 2004, Brussels.
http://idl.iscram.org/files/oomes/2004/178_Oomes2004.pdf

Endsley et al.²⁹ define shared SA as the degree to which team members have the same SA on shared SA requirements. It involves several people trying to form a common picture, sharing an understanding of that subset of information that is necessary for each of their objectives.

Four factors would be necessary for the development of shared SA:

- The requirements of shared SA (e.g., the degree to which team members understand what information is needed by other team members)
- Shared SA devices (e.g. network systems, communication devices, shared screens and shared environment)
- Shared SA mechanisms (e.g., shared mental models)
- Shared SA processes, which refer to efficient team processes that enable the sharing of relevant information

TEAM SA

Endsley defines team SA as the degree to which each team member possesses the situational awareness required for their responsibilities.

For the development of the SA of the team it would be necessary to

- A high level of SA among individual team members for aspects of the situation relevant to their work.
- A high level of shared SA among members, based on a precise common operational picture of those aspects of the situation common to each member's requirements.

Communication is the most crucial element in the formation of team SA or shared SA.

5.4.1.3. Team sensemaking

Sensemaking is the necessary activity that complements the process of situation assessment, which consists of creating understanding from a set of disparate data.

Like SA, sensemaking is based on available data and existing knowledge or experience, but is triggered when an anomaly occurs or when information does not fit the emergency manager's current understanding. In this situation, the decision-maker attempts to fit the data to existing knowledge, schemas or stories that supported the initial understanding of the situation to explain the surprise/anomaly and generate a new understanding of the situation.

Sensemaking complements the process of situation assessment, but it is also the process through which SA is achieved.

Sensemaking was initially postulated in the context of individual cognition. However, there are cases where surprise or disengagement occurs in situations where more than one person is responsible for assessing and understanding the situation.

5.4.1.4. Common ground

For collaborative groups and teams to make effective plans and decisions in complex work environments, COMMON GROUND refers to the basic shared assumptions and responsibilities

²⁹ Endsley, M. R. (1988) Design and evaluation for situation awareness enhancement. Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting. SAGE Journals, 32 (2), 97-101. November 2015]. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/154193128803200221>

(or basic compact) that a team shares and acts as a baseline against which situations and behaviours can be judged.

5.4.2. State of the art

The representation of the environment is crucial in all emergency operations because it is a necessity for the command and control (C2) function, which provides the operation with direction and coordination. The representation, in the form of a Common Operational Picture (COP), is considered the key element for establishing situation awareness and understanding for the first responders and other actors involved. Successful emergency response actions require all actors and authorities to understand the common intent and maintain a shared picture. The information needs to be organized and validated, easy to search, and of relevance to the decision makers.

5.4.2.1. Definition of a COP

Despite its common use in emergency management, there is no unambiguous definition of COP, although all definitions consistently include characteristics of collaboration.

The origin of the COP concept lies in a specific technical design of a technology interoperability programme for the US military, where the objective was to provide common information and data exchange formats between different systems and software.

The COP is considered one of the most promising solutions in emergency management to improve the quality of information exchange and support the development of situational awareness. It usually manifests itself as a geographical representation combined with a checklist describing the characteristics of the response operation.

5.4.2.2. Conceptions of a COP

There is disagreement about whether a COP is a product, a process or an operating environment two conceptions of COP are differentiated:

- **COP AS AN INFORMATION WAREHOUSE:** is a conception of the COP focused on information dissemination capabilities: the COP is treated as a means of capturing information and putting it in a place where users can selectively access information that is appropriate for them to perform their tasks. It is a visual representation of tactical, operational and strategic information to support rapid assimilation and integration by team members. Achieving a common operating picture allows personnel on and off the scene to have the same information about the incident, including the availability and location of resources, personnel and the status of requests for assistance. But if the COP becomes a repository of large amounts of information that is not properly organised and validated, it becomes useless in assisting decision-making because the emergency manager cannot find what they need in a timely manner. This becomes even more difficult when multiple agencies share the COP and numerous entities enter data into the system and when each is dependent on the others to record or access relevant, timely and accurate data.
- **COP AS A TRADING ZONE:** focused on the need to reach a sufficient level of shared understanding: The COP is not only an "information warehouse" that supports self-synchronisation, but also a tool that helps its users to easily understand each other's limitations and the possible combinations of collaboration and support between them under a given set of conditions. Operating in a totally virtual environment, with limited

human contact, would make it impossible to adequately resolve conflicts involving several institutions. Verbal communication is also a very important part of creating a common understanding of the situation. Not only individual perception is important, but collective perception is also crucial for all actors to develop a shared understanding as a basis for coordinated action. Effective coordination and communication are required both to understand the COP and to achieve a common situational understanding.

The COP is about sharing and building information about the response operation in a way that allows its users to continuously redefine and mutually adjust their relationships. The COP is a collaborative planning enabler that supports all tiers to achieve the situational awareness. The COP is the central product that moves out of the data provision function and into the decision-support guidance function.

5.4.2.3. *Current situation*

Proper information management is considered crucial to overcome the problems of coordination and information exchange between different organisational domains. Emergency management agencies try to solve the problem of information management by advocating information systems that enable shared situational awareness to be achieved by creating a common operating picture (COP).

Currently, the operational picture at the scene of the incident seems to be mainly in the heads of the various emergency service actors, or on whiteboards, flipcharts or crisis managers' papers. This is unlikely to facilitate the sharing of this information beyond the immediate command group dealing with the incident or beyond the incoming command group assuming command in a handover.

Kedia T et al³⁰ published a systematic review in 2020 on technologies that can improve safety and aid decision-making during disaster response operations. They concluded that operational security is particularly difficult to obtain during a disaster because of the logistical challenges of collecting and disseminating complete and high-quality information from first responders to EOCs, the constantly changing needs and resources on the ground, and the fact that organisations use different information-sharing platforms. With incomplete ES, decisions made in EOCs will be inefficient and potentially ineffective, as they address a different situation than the current one.

An earlier review published by Freeman JD et al³¹ found that the use of information and communication technologies in disaster response is:

- Geographical application is generally limited
- Does not identify intended end-users

³⁰ Kedia T et al. Technologies Enabling Situational Awareness During Disaster Response: A Systematic Review. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*. VOL. 16/NO. 1. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/disaster-medicine-and-public-health-preparedness/article/technologies-enabling-situational-awareness-during-disaster-response-a-systematic-review/4B303623ECEF3F0413C68F1462DFC00F>

³¹ Freeman JD, Blacker B, Hatt G, et al. Use of big data and information and communications technology in disasters: an integrative review. *Disaster Med Public Health Prep*. 2019;13(2):353-367. doi: 10.1017/dmp.2018.73 . <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30047353/>

- It does not address the challenges of implementing technology on the ground.

For example, the USA Coast Guard Incident Specific Preparedness Review (ISPR) Team report on the Deepwater Horizon oil spill in 2011 highlighted a:

- Lack of interoperability between technologies and information exchange platforms
- Challenges in interpreting and storing large amounts of collected data
- Delays in data processing

The result is unfeasible information for decision-makers.

This indicates that the technologies currently in use are not adequate to achieve HA, and may limit the speed, efficiency and effectiveness of response efforts, but these specific challenges may not have been appreciated using the previous methodology, motivating the present study.

5.4.2.4. Benefits of a COP

A COP usually represents geographic information, as typical applications are linked to a possible wide geographic area (location awareness). In this line, the COP is considered as a geographical representation combined with a checklist that delineates the evolution of an emergency along with the characteristics and progress of emergency response operations. The information adapted in terms of content and detail is merged into a common frame of reference and displayed on a screen, supporting the response organisations' understanding of the current situation overview.

The common operating picture emerges from the intersection of data/information, knowledge/expertise, the demands of emergency response and the commander's intended response to those demands (objectives and priorities), and the technology that represents them to the various actors. It is not just about data and technology (i.e. common data formats, common data visualisations of sensor information, all seeing the same visualisation elements). Data and technology support, rather than define, the COP.

The role of the COP is to support the common understanding of emergency demands and the coordination of the actions of various actors in response to those demands.

Situational awareness (SA) has been found to be related to how individuals and teams know and understand what is going on around them. In addition, good SA provides a firm basis for effective decision-making. The development of this good SA is facilitated by the deployment of an effective COP that visualises relevant information. A COP that includes all available information but does not prioritise the relevant elements to be shared will lead to information overload, i.e. the dissemination of redundant and irrelevant information. Not all organisations need the same information to perform their tasks, and even within organisations, different levels of management do not need the same level of detail, so it is necessary to determine what level of information is relevant to their functions. Humans have a limited capacity to retain the information available for processing, which is called working memory. Thus, information overload complicates decision-making and creates simplified mental models.

In addition, a COP can facilitate collaborative planning and can support various levels of command between the different agencies involved in an operation to achieve a shared SA. A COP tends to support the development of a shared perspective on emergency operations priorities.

In order to achieve shared SA based on a COP between different emergency response organisations, systems based on network-centric working logic must be employed. Better networks can lead to better information feeding into detection, warning and verification processes, which in turn can contribute to the development of a better situational interface.

Better information leads to better response by emergency organisations, which in turn contributes to more efficient use of resources and assets, so that better actions can be taken in the field.

Better actions lead to better results, i.e. a quicker normalisation of the situation and thus minimisation of the consequences of the incident or disaster (socio-economic and environmental losses).

5.4.2.5. Characteristics of a COP

The most relevant aspects found in the literature concerning the characteristics that could be considered in the development of a COP are listed below:

GENERAL ASPECTS

- The common operating picture should be established prior to the disaster. The COP would be created by the actors involved in the operations, as it consists of some elements of the SA, which the actor understands he/she should share based on experience or consultation with colleagues or has knowledge of through procedures, etc.
- It would require knowledge of each other's *modus operandi*, such as information needs, objectives, capacities, processes and resources. Training and investigation of specific information needs from assessment reports and/or discussion with experts provide insights into what needs to be implemented in the COP as static and dynamic information requirements. Analysis and data entry must be timely, accurate. COP structures must be able to combine static and dynamic information that is known to be needed in different scenarios.
- It should be governed by harmonised terminology, both in vocabulary and symbols and in the recording, analysis and exchange of information. The emergency response system lacks a common language and common data analysis procedures. The differences are due to the different jurisdictions, responsibilities and requirements of those responsible.
- It would provide “translated” data through symbols mapping
- Symbols should contain information beyond static information, e.g. directions, speed of travel, etc.
- It should have standardised mapping, with digital maps at the national level that include hazards, vulnerable objects and risk analysis results related to the different potential types of events.
- A standardised communication framework should be followed to avoid useless information and information overload.
- It would include emergency plans for crisis response, as well as decision and rescue plans. The intent of an incident action plan can be drawn on the COP disaster response map, indicating the evacuation route for people, areas of concentration for rescue teams and dispatch activities, etc.
- It would standardize procedures for Level Awareness Activation/Deactivation

C2 DECISION-MAKING SUPPORT

- The C2 support system should not become less effective due to an excessive information burden.
- The COP should allow the commanders' interpretation of data to be represented, so that subordinates can align their actions with the commander's plan and intent. It should include the ability to insert dynamic operational information based on the current needs of the officers.
- It should be possible to visualise the evolution of damage or response over time using GIS overlay layers.
- All factors relevant to an emergency should be able to be automatically incorporated into a comprehensive and real-time overview of present and future needs, which may include the availability of resources and assets, their appropriate deployment and control on the ground, i.e. actionable knowledge.
- In addition to information about what has happened, disaster response would require prediction of the future state of what will happen, based on computational models. This is very important when responding to a disaster.
- It should generate real-time situation reports on disaster losses, such as casualties and material losses, and the allocation of resources, such as rescue equipment and relief goods.
- The COP should provide users with scripts for inter-agency collaboration and tools for an equitable response, regardless of which actor is the direct observer or manager of the situation. This script would ensure that all actors receive the same information, regardless of which agency is in charge of the response. It should include scripts or procedures that are generic or flexible enough to be implemented in different scenarios.
- It would provide advanced analysis functions, such as disaster modelling and simulation capabilities.

DATA

- It should have high levels of automaticity in relation to data collection, processing and dissemination.
- The COP should include data from sensors, including technological and human sensors. In a disaster scenario, users populate the COP with data. These users are most likely to provide the data through manual input rather than through automatic or sensor systems. This information is often less accurate or less relevant and therefore does not meet the need of decision-makers.
- It should display default static information in the preparedness phase of emergency management, as well as dynamic information related to the evolution of an event.
- It would incorporate dynamic data from different sources, such as reconnaissance and surveillance assets, emergency response teams in contact, intelligence gained from analysis, information from higher echelons and estimates of incomplete information, external resources (satellite images, weather info, CCITV channels, behavioural analysis from social media etc).
- By leveraging inputs from different intelligence sources, all units deployed in the field of operations could be mapped in real time. It would allow visualising the spatial distribution of emergency response teams, such as police, medical teams, fire brigades, or search and rescue teams.

- The data should be automatically updated
- All this information should be properly recorded and stored.

PRESENTATION OF THE DATA

- It should have pre-defined filters to ensure that the data requested by the guidance function is presented in an appropriate style, adapted to that specific level of command and level of conflict.
- It should be possible to share the filtered data with other agencies to achieve shared views of data accessed from databases on the network.
- It should show the process of risk evolution and the development of the emergency response action, facilitated by the use of a visualisation of the COP.
- Different emergency response organisations should be able to obtain the desired operational picture on a single screen.
- The cartographic representation of the operational area could include the location of all units involved, casualties, areas of interest, evacuation points and different types of resources, certain terrain features, etc.

COMMUNICATIONS

- It could be used to improve communication with subordinate levels about the desired end state and the different phases leading to that end state.
- Ability to collaboratively map, send instant text messages and hold video conversations on the web.

5.4.2.6. Some examples of COP development

EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (EMIMS)

In the US, in October 2007, FEMA began using the Emergency Management Information Management System (EMIMS) real-time information exchange software, which was to serve as a single repository of disaster information that was to provide decision-makers with a broad view of response actions and needs during a national crisis. EMIMS was to serve as FEMA's COP.

However, in 2009 it was determined that the system was not capable of integrating the plethora of existing state systems. Consequently, FEMA officials decided to abandon the EMIMS programme.

Following the demise of EMIMS, FEMA management recognised the need to provide the monitoring centres with doctrinal guidance on standardisation and reporting requirements.

FEMA Regional Offices recognised the value that a comprehensive COP would add to response activities and started regional initiatives to create their COPs (such as the Emergency Response Unified Planning Tool (ERUPT) in Seattle, or the Spatial Tool for Operations and Response Management (STORM) in Atlanta).

Since 2010, FEMA has begun investing time and resources in the Disaster Management and Support Environment (DMSE), which is a system of systems designed to support response and recovery that is intended to leverage and enable existing capabilities, not result in the development of a new solution. The Situational Awareness Viewer for Emergency Response and Recovery (SAVER2) is the visualisation component of the DMSE.

MOBILE URBAN SITUATION AWARENESS SYSTEM (MUSAS)

Björkbom M et al³², proposed in 2013 an online location and situational awareness system, called Mobile Urban Situation Awareness System (MUSAS), to gather and maintain location information with a focus on an urban environment. It is an integrated system that provides location services of various types to enable situational awareness in order to form a common operational picture.

MUSAS provides multiple location services, as well as visualisation of other sensor data, in a common frame of reference. The information and the common operational picture of the system is transmitted to all parties involved in the operation, the field team and the people at the command post.

A key contribution of MUSAS is to provide a system for online location based on situational awareness using multiple location and mapping methods. Compared to other similar systems, MUSAS does not assume or rely on anything in the target environment. MUSAS builds its own infrastructure using wireless sensor network (WSN) and wireless local area network (WLAN) technologies. It maps the unknown area and updates knowledge as entities are located. Location information of moving targets is tracked and updated to the COP model and all users. The system can operate both outdoors and indoors and has through-wall observation capability.

Compared to other similar systems, MUSAS focuses on multiple localisation services and localised information presentation. The system can be deployed in search and rescue and seismic disaster situations to map the environment and locate people. It also has applications in police hostage situations, indoor firefighting scenarios and military operations.

5.4.3. Landscape

The following items have been consulted in the WP5 questionnaire in relation to this section Common Operational Picture:

- Service First Responders Communications:
 - Description (Free text)
 - Features (Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level)
 - Data capability (Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others)
 - Other Data capabilities included (Free text)
- Service First Responders Support Software:
 - Description (Free text)
 - Features (Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level)
 - Data capability (Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others)

³² Björkbom, M., Timonen, J., Yiğitler, H., Kaltiokallio, O., García, J.M.V., Myrsky, M., Saarinen, J., Korkalainen, M., Cuhac, C., Jäntti, R. and Virrankoski, R. (2013) Localization services for online common operational picture and situation awareness. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/301130146.pdf>

- Other Data capabilities included (Free text)
- C2 Support Software:
 - Description (Free text)
 - Features (Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level)
 - Data capability (Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others)
 - Other Data capabilities included (Free text)
- What information should be available to have a common operational picture that enables a good crisis situational awareness and facilitate C&C decision-making?: (Crisis zone map, Hazard Mapping, Climate, Vulnerable critical points mapping, Healthcare infrastructures mapping, Vehicles tracking, Access routes, Evacuation routes, Traffic conditions, Vehicles contact points, Zonation, Facilities deployment, Responders tracking, Victims data, Hospital capacities, Other)
- Other Information that should be available (Free text)
- What characteristics should have this common operational picture?: (Configurable, Real-time Information, Forecast based on dynamic inputs, Forecast based on Artificial Intelligence, C&C Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence)
- Perception of needs: (Free text). Needs/shortcomings existing in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

Following the analysis of the questionnaires/surveys during the Valkyries project WP5 execution, the Landscape picture on operational/workflows/engaged roles and practices in COP organization procedures and between different countries is as in the following table:

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Service First Responders Communications Features	Available > Available on scene = Cross-agency Capability > Standardized at National Level > Dedicated	Medium
Service First Responders Communications Data capability	Voice > Data > GPS > Picture = Maps > Vehicles > Video = Victims = Responders > Hazards = Hospitals	High
Service First Responders Support Software Features	Available > Dedicated > Standardized at National Level > Available On Scene	High
Service First Responders Support Software Data capability	Data > Maps > GPS > Voice = Picture > Video = Hazards = Victims =	Very high

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
	Responders = Vehicles = Medical supplies	
C2 Support Software Features	Standardized at National Level > Available = Available on scene = Dedicated > Cross-agency Capability,	High
C&C Support Software Data capability	Data = Maps = GPS > Voice = Picture > Video > Vehicles > Hazards = Victims = Responders	Very high
Information that should be available to have a common operational picture that enables a good crisis situational awareness and facilitate C2 decision-making	Vehicles > Crisis zone map = Hazard Mapping = Healthcare infrastructures mapping > Climate = Evacuation routes > Vulnerable critical points mapping = Responders tracking = Hospital capacities > Traffic conditions, Vehicles contact points = Facilities deployment = , Victims data	High
Characteristics should have this common operational picture	Real-time Information > Forecast based on dynamic inputs > Configurable = Healthcare Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence > C&C Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence > Forecast based on Artificial Intelligence	High

Table 9 - WP5 questionnaire: Common Operational Picture answers

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS:

SERVICE FIRST RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS NETWORK FEATURES:

The vast majority of the services surveyed (85.71%) have operational communications networks, but a minority (28.57%) ensure their availability at the scene.

Figure 49 - Service first responders communications network features

A minority also have a network that allows cross-agency communications, and it is paradoxical that the agencies surveyed that do not have responsibility for cross-national MCI response have a greater capability in this regard than those that do.

Figure 50 - Service first responders communications network features according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

These are generally non-dedicated networks, and not standardised at the national level.

No relevant differences are shown between the different types of Service.

SERVICE FIRST RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS NETWORKS DATA CAPABILITY:

As for the information transmission capacity offered by the communication networks of the different services surveyed, in about 2/3 of the cases they allow the transmission of voice messages, and in half of the cases of data and GPS geopositioning. In slightly less than 1/3 of the cases, also images or maps.

Figure 51 - Service first responders communications data capability

In relation to the deployment of on-scene response, the Services rarely have the capacity to transmit information concerning vehicles, and even less to emergency services personnel or the victims themselves.

Less than 10% of the Services surveyed would have the capacity to exchange information relating to aspects such as the risks associated with the accident or the hospitals potentially involved in the health response, and none of them would have it in relation to logistical resources and supplies or to the facilities deployed at the scene.

Analysing by type of Service, the networks used by firefighters show better capabilities than the rest in relation to the communication of information such as voice, data, images, maps, vehicles and GPS geopositioning.

Figure 52 – Service first responders communications data capability according to the type of emergency service

The group of Services with potential responsibility for responding to cross-national MCI shows notably higher percentages in data communication capabilities than the others, being more similar in terms of the remaining capabilities.

Figure 53 – Service first responders communications data capability according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

SERVICE FIRST RESPONDERS SUPPORT SOFTWARE FEATURES:

Just over half of the services surveyed have software tools that support the operational intervention of FRs. This proportion is higher (75%) among fire services than among EMS and other types of services (50%), with otherwise very similar profiles across all services.

In half of the cases where this software is available, it is a dedicated system.

A minority have such software at the incident site and have no multi-agency capability.

Figure 54 - Service first responders support software features

In general, these are software solutions that are not standardized at national level. For services with potential responsibility for responding to transnational multi-victim incidents, the situation does not improve at all, but rather the opposite.

Figure 55 – Service first responders support software features according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

SERVICE FIRST RESPONDERS SUPPORT SOFTWARE DATA CAPABILITY:

When we analyse the software that support the operational intervention of FRs, there is hardly any application for the transmission of voice messages and the capabilities in relation to GPS geopositioning are in a very low segment, less than 30%. Otherwise, the information transmission capacity is similar to that described for communications network.

Figure 56 - First responders support software data capability

Analysing by type of Service, the software solutions of the firefighters again show better capacities, in this case for the transmission of data and maps.

Figure 57 – First responders support software data capability according to the type of emergency service

In relation to data transmission capabilities, the group of services with potential responsibility for responding to cross-national MCI shows a slightly better percentage.

C2 SUPPORT SOFTWARE FEATURES:

In terms of C2 decision support software, slightly more than half of the services surveyed have such software, but a minority still have such software at the scene of the incident and a minority work with dedicated solutions.

Figure 58 - C2 support software features

In this case, the degree of standardisation among the firefighter services surveyed is high (75%) and very low in the remaining cases.

Figure 59 – C2 support software features according to the type of emergency service

These are solutions that generally do not allow for multi-agency working.

Overall, a somewhat more favourable picture emerges for services with potential responsibility for cross-national MCI response, for example in relation to the ability to work together across agencies

Figure 60 – C2 support software features according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

C2 SUPPORT SOFTWARE DATA CAPABILITY:

The software tools that would support C2 command and control also show a rather limited application for the transmission of voice messages, although they show more capability for the transmission of pictures and maps than the software tools supporting the operational intervention of FR. The other capabilities and limitations are very similar to those described for networks and software supporting FR.

Figure 61 - C2 support software data capability

Figure 62 - Comparative graph of communications network and software data capability

The software tools of firefighters and those of services with potential responsibility for responding to transnational MCI show better information transmission capabilities, in this case in terms of data, images, maps and GPS geo-positioning.

Figure 63 – C2 support software data capability according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

Figure 64 – C2 support software data capability according to the type of emergency service

INFORMATION THAT SHOULD BE AVAILABLE IN A COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE :

When asked what information should be available to have a common operational picture (COP) that enables a good crisis situational awareness and facilitate C2 decision-making, there is general agreement on the desirability of including Crisis zone map, Hazard Mapping, Climate, Vulnerable critical points mapping, Healthcare infrastructures mapping, Responders tracking, Vehicles tracking, Evacuation routes and Hospital capacities.

There was less consensus on Access routes, Traffic conditions, Vehicles contact points, Facilities deployment and Victims data.

The information that obtained the least relevance in the survey on the common operational picture is that relating to Zonation.

Figure 65 - Results of the survey on information that a COP should include

There are no major differences in the analysis by type of Service.

Figure 66 – Results of the survey on information that a COP should include according to the type of emergency service

As for the Services with potential responsibility for responding to cross-national MCI, they are more interested than the rest in the COP including information on Vulnerable critical points mapping, Access routes, Vehicles contact points, Responders tracking and Hospital capacities. On the other hand, they are somewhat less interested than the rest in Traffic conditions.

Figure 67 – Results of the survey on information that a COP should include according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

CHARACTERISTICS THAT SHOULD HAVE A COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE:

When asked what characteristics this common operational picture should have, the general opinion is that it should show Real-time Information, and there is a fairly high agreement (approx. 2/3) on the interest in the Forecast based on dynamic inputs.

Less relevance (less than 30%) is given to the fact that it should be configurable and that it should provide C2 or Healthcare recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence.

Figure 68 - Results of the survey on characteristics that a COP should have

No relevant differences by type of Service are observed in the surveyed sample.

Figure 69 – Results of the survey on characteristics that a COP should have according to the type of emergency service

Services without potential responsibility in the response to cross-national MCI basically focus their interest on real-time data, expressing less interest in having a COP with the rest of the functionalities proposed.

Figure 70 – Results of the survey on characteristics that a COP should have according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

5.4.4. Perception of needs

In order to provide adequate situational awareness to first responders in an accurate and timely manner, data and information from multiple sources need to be collected, processed (analysed when necessary), transported, merged, placed in appropriate contexts and presented in a way that facilitates timely and correct decisions by C2 disaster managers.

In addition to harmonised joint operating procedures, this requires the availability of technological resources to support the recording, centralisation, processing and sharing of information among disaster response actors. However, the technological capacities for this are still low in EU countries.

In relation to needs perceived by the experts surveyed, the following needs emerged from the questionnaires carried out:

- Different C2 centres located for Medical and non-medical Responses to disasters
- Coordination of different institutions and between different regions
- In common outdated technology and systems. Create unific system

5.5. Alert and warning

5.5.1. Introduction

Traditionally, “alerts” have been used to indicate that something significant has happened or may happen, while “warnings” typically follow alerts and provide more detail information indicating what protective action should be taken. However, the distinction between the two terms has blurred over time, as a more nuanced understanding of people’s need for information

and response to that information has emerged and as new communications technologies that can transmit both types of messages have come into use. The purpose of alerts and warnings is to provide the necessary information to warn the public and effect the necessary actions that will lead to their safety and to deliver the messages to populations at risk of imminent threats with the goal of maximizing the probability that people take protective actions and minimize the delay in taking those actions.

Early warning is one of the main elements of disaster risk reduction. It prevents the loss of life and reduces the economical and material impacts of disasters. To be effective, early warning systems must actively engage communities at risk, facilitate public education and awareness of such risks, effectively disseminate messages and alerts and ensure ongoing preparedness.

5.5.1.1. General concepts in alert and warning

Some authors define the concept of early warning systems (EWS), in each of these definitions, there are common elements that allow us to define EWS as the set of tools, control devices, management capabilities, and technological tools, which key institutions identify to disseminate information in a timely manner to communities exposed to a risk, and whose result is mitigation measures aimed at reducing the effect of disaster and economic and life losses, as well as injured.

Risk is defined as the combination of the probability of an event to occur and its negative consequences.

Early warning systems has two aspects:

- Receiving alerts on various threats through designated systems. Scientific institutions and organisations provide the input data, which is needed for decision making. Meteorological, Seismological, Hydrological are common required for risk assessment.
- Warning and alarming the population on threats.

Effective incident response needs a structured and pre-planned public warning. Public warning is based on two functions: hazard monitoring and warning dissemination. It is also necessary to establish a mechanism for risk identification, hazard monitoring, decision-making, warning dissemination, and to evaluate and improve.

Alerts and warnings may be sent before, during, or after an event. The type of information needed and the population that at risk will shift throughout each phase of an event.

Alerts and warnings may be sent by government agencies, fundamentally Civil Protection, fire departments or Emergency Systems, regional or local administration, media station or private systems.

Another objective of this task is to provide recommendations and guidelines to issue alerts and warnings in disaster.

5.5.2. State of the art

5.5.2.1. Current situation in alert and warning

The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 was adopted at the Third United Nations World Conference on Disaster Risk Reduction, held from 14 to 18 March 2015 in Sendai, Japan. In this Framework in order to support the assessment of global progress in achieving the outcome and goal of the document, seven global targets had been agreed, and the seventh

consists on substantially increase the availability of and access to multi-hazard early warning systems and disaster risk information and assessment to people by 2030.

<https://www.undrr.org/implementing-sendai-framework/what-sendai-framework>

EU Civil Protection Mechanism brings together a total of 33 countries: 27 EU members States and 6 participants States (Norway, Iceland, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey) This EU Civil Protection shares operational challenges and similar approaches to managing disaster, while the structure and composition of emergency services varies considerably from country to country. Under the mechanism, countries stand ready and prepare to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced.

The EU's early warning and information systems help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre monitor hazards and events worldwide. Examples of hazards that the Centre monitors are earthquakes and tsunamis, tropical cyclones, volcanoes, droughts, floods, and forest fires.

Detailed scientific information on emergencies increases the safety and protection of EU citizens. The EU's monitoring tools also complement information available to Member States and help their emergency services channel response whenever needed.

The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings.

Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.

Close cooperation with various research institutes facilitates the development of disaster forecasting and disaster management tools for both natural and human-induced hazards:

- Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System: provides alerts and estimates impacts of earthquakes, tsunamis, tropical cyclones, floods, volcanos, and droughts worldwide.
- European and Global Flood Awareness Systems: give notifications on floods up to 15 days in advance in Europe and worldwide.
- European and Global Forest Fire Information Systems: forecast dangerous weather conditions up to 10 days ahead and provide near-real-time information on active fires and burnt areas. The systems analyse the severity and risk that each forest fire poses for the local population and the environment. This allows informed decisions on the deployment of the rescEU firefighting capacity.
- European and Global Drought Observatories: give information on droughts risks in Europe and worldwide, including meteorological indicators, soil moisture anomalies, vegetation stress and river low flows.

These early warning and information systems are part of the EU's Copernicus programme. <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/ems/what-copernicus>

The Copernicus programme is developed by the European Commission (EC) with the support of the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). Its main objective is to provide useful information for the efficient management of emergency situations, citizen security and mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

Users are entities and organizations at regional, national, European and international level active in the field of crisis management in the EU Member States, the States participating in the European Civil Protection Mechanism, the Directorates-General (DG) and the EU agencies of the Commission, the European External Action Service (EEAS), as well as international humanitarian aid organizations.

This program monitors data obtained by satellite and through a global network of ground, air and marine sensors to create the most detailed images of the Earth and transforms them into services and products such as informative maps and datasets:

- The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
- The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
- The Copernicus Earth Monitoring Service
- The Copernicus Climate Change Service
- The Copernicus Emergency Management Service
- The Copernicus Security Service

When it comes to managing the risk of both natural and induced disasters, Copernicus EMS Early Warning and Monitoring provides critical geospatial information at European and global level through continuous observations and forecasts of floods, droughts and forest fires.

On the other hand, Copernicus EMS On Demand Mapping is able to provide detailed information on demand to support the response to a crisis. Thus, you can request geospatial information immediately after the disaster to support emergency management (Rapid Mapping) and disaster management, including the phases of prevention, preparedness, risk reduction and recovery (Risk & Recovery Mapping).

www.copernicus.eu

<http://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/space/copernicus>

<http://emergency.copernicus.eu>

5.5.2.2. Current situation in Europe

EU Directive 2018/1972 on the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) - This Directive, adopted in December 2018, sets out common rules for the provision of electronic communications services across the EU. The Directive includes provisions related to alert and warning systems, including requirements for Member States to develop and implement alert and warning systems based on standardized protocols and procedures. Regarding public warning systems, the article 110 of the European Electronic Communication Code requires that by 21 June 2022, Member States shall ensure that, when public warning systems regarding imminent or developing major emergencies and disasters are in place, public warnings are transmitted by providers of mobile number-based interpersonal communications services to the end-users concerned.

The EECC (European Electronic Communications Code) Article 110 directive states that the public warning system must be mobile phone-based and capable of sending geo-located mass alerts. The alerts must be received by the mobile phones of everyone within an emergency area. These systems take time to implement as they require collaboration with the major mobile telecom carriers in each country. European member states are also given the option to

implement alternate systems if it can be proven that they are just as effective as the phone based systems. Two years after the release of the EECC, BEREC released guidelines on how to assess and compare effectiveness to ensure these potential alternate systems are viable.

EU-Alert is the generic term for the European Public Warning Service based upon Cell Broadcast technology (this is a method of sending messages to multiple mobile telephone users in a defined area at the same time). EU-Alert is compatible with Wireless Emergency Alerts (WEA) formerly known as the Commercial Mobile Alert System (CMAS) standard as used in the United States. Since 2012, and by default, mobile phone OSes like Android, iOS, and Windows support EU-Alert/WEA/CMAS via Cell Broadcast for public warning messages

Two technologies make it possible to reach everyone present in a specific area on their mobile phones and thus comply with EU legislation:

- Cell Broadcast is a standardised technology that makes it possible to send alerts to a geo-targeted population, directly on their mobile phones. When people are present in an area (whether they are residents or visitors) where a disaster is ongoing or might happen in the near future, their phone would display an alert with a distinctive ringtone and vibration. Public authorities can use this technology to alert instantly (usually within 10 seconds) the population present near a disaster (possibility to narrow it down to a few meters) and in a privacy-friendly manner.
- Location-Based SMS is another technology that can be used to alert all the population of a given area in near real-time. The main difference with cell broadcast is that alerts are transmitted to the users by regular SMS. Public authorities can use the cellular base stations to disseminate alerts to all the phones connected to these stations in an anonymised way. Authorities may also be able to access information on the country of origin of the users' SIM cards, making it possible to send the alert in different languages to different phones and to get real-time.

EU early warning tools complement national public warning systems. To that end, the EU works closely together with Member States in establishing and further developing their national public warning systems. The aim is to protect citizens from disasters. The EU is working with all Member States to put systems in place to reach and alert people affected by a natural or human-induced hazard.

https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/early-warning-and-information-systems_en

In Web, some Member States and Participating States publish a little introductory overview of key elements of the national disaster management system, including early warning systems, in order to warn and inform the population, or surveillance systems monitoring the environment and trigger an alert to authorities when defined threshold are exceeded. The most common activations of the warning systems are meteorological and hidrological phenomena. Seismological monitoring and forest fire risk during the summer period are reported in many countries.

https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/national-disaster-management-system_es

The following is a summary of the situation of EU members with regard to risk communication, awareness raising and early warning systems.

AUSTRIA

Risks are communicated via different channels on all governmental levels. At the local level, citizens are involved in planning activities and in the elaboration of local hazard maps and risk management plans. The results of local and regional hazard and risk assessments are also communicated through various local channels and regional media. Participation of citizens is ensured in different local and regional participation forums. In addition, comprehensive information about hazard and risks is also made available to the general public mainly on the internet.

On the national level information portals are available for natural hazards, radiation protection and other risks. To warn the population, the Ministry of the Interior and the federal states installed a national warning system. More than 8,000 sirens will warn the population in an emergency. An alarm can be triggered nationwide or regionally. In addition, the warning system “KATWARN” was introduced in Austria, which uses a mobile app and short messages to warn the population about various types of danger. The Austrian National Weather Service operates a warning system for extreme weather conditions, which is used to warn the authorities and response organisations but it is also available to the media and the public on the internet. On the main rivers, there are fully automatic flood warning and control systems managed by the hydrological services.

BELGIUM

In 2018, the National Crisis Centre (NCCN) coordinated a large-scale risk assessment for Belgium for the period 2018-2023.

A [special website https://www.risico-info.be/en](https://www.risico-info.be/en) is dedicated for risk communication towards the public.

Since 2017, BE-Alert has been operational throughout Belgium. This is an **alarm system** that allows the government to inform in an emergency situation. Mayor, governor or minister activates Be-Alert to send a message via SMS, e-mail or voice call to everyone impacted by the emergency situation. Currently, more than 1 million addresses are already registered and 85% of the municipalities are already registered on BE-Alert.

BULGARIA

Civilians are informed about disaster risks through information campaigns such as leaflets, banners, handbooks, videos, and TV and radio ads.

At the national level, the dissemination of information is mainly through electronic media and social networks via the press centre of the Ministry of the Interior, the web page of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Directorate-General, specific information website, and the online Fire Safety and Civil Protection magazine SOS 112.

The regional and municipal FSCP directorates also use regional and local mass media and interact with regional and municipal administrations.

Children and students receive 5 school hours per year dedicated to disaster risk awareness training.

The Early Warning and Population Alert System (siren system) is designed to simultaneously alert a large group of people throughout the country or in a certain region in case of upcoming or emerging disasters. It also provides instructions on necessary measures and actions through acoustic signals and "live" voice information for citizens for acting in emergencies. The sirens can be operated locally by the local fire safety and civil protection operations centre or centrally by the National Operations Centre (NOC). Actually, around 36% of the population can be alerted.

CZECH REPUBLIC

The public can get information on disaster risks via television and radio. The government also liaises with the press to promote suitable topics. Information is available via websites and social networks, and via posters in public transportation and municipal buildings.

The public also have access to preventive educational activities.

The United Alert and Notification System (UANS) is an early warning system used in the Czech Republic. The most common activations of the warning system are meteorological and hydrological phenomena. Based on warning from the Czech Hydro-meteorological Institute (CHI) and after considering the extent and degree of risk, the UANS may be activated throughout the whole of the Czech Republic or in a chosen area only. The warning consists of several types of sirens and all available mass media. In the Czech Republic, the siren system has pre-recorded warnings such as dangerous flood wave, chemical accident, and radiation accident. People who live in the zone of emergency planning could be informed through mobile phones and they have available information leaflets informing of possible dangers and what to do in case of accident.

DENMARK

Denmark operates with sectorial responsibilities that extend to risk communication and awareness. This means that the sector responsible for an area with a public risk involved also has the responsibility to communicate about that risk.

The Danish Emergency Management Agency coordinates the publication of a National Risk Profile, in which the most severe risks are profiled, and conducts a biannual survey on the public awareness of these threats.

On a national level, the warning system, consisting of a nationwide siren system and a direct line to national broadcasters, who, in severe emergencies, are obliged to post and broadcast warning messages unedited – is tested once a year, both to create awareness and to test the system. This system is supplemented by information via an SMS-service for the hearing impaired, a warning app, and authorities' social media and web platforms.

Early warning systems in Denmark are currently exclusively weather related. They include slippery road-warning from roadside measurements being shown on authorities' websites and apps and being the basis for traffic radio information.

The Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) maintains a warning system for nuclear and radiological emergencies. DEMA receives automatic alarms from 11 automatic online measurement stations located throughout the country and can react.

ESTONIA

The government has composed a list of those emergencies for which risk communication is organised and designates the authorities responsible for the organisation thereof. Estonia faces few emergencies therefore public interest in risk management is low.

Risk communication takes place for specific risks. Especially in areas where there are plants or factories handling dangerous materials, people must be informed about the possible risks, how to prepare and what to do if there is an incident.

The Rescue Board is one authority that carries out risk communication by drawing people's attention to the threats that might occur.

Estonia does not have a nationwide warning system. In an ongoing emergency, people can be warned via radio, TV, internet, text messages, and - in some areas - sirens.

The Estonian Emergency Response Centre (EERC) is a national rescue organisation and the main task of the EERC is to handle the emergency messages forwarded to the single European emergency number 112 and dispatch for ambulance, fire and rescue services, informs and involves other services, companies and organisations, if necessary.

FINLAND

Safety communications in Finland consist of safety advice, training, and education covering guidance, education and counselling work mentioned in the Rescue Act.

Safety communications strategy guides the planning, evaluation and development of safety communications of all rescue services actors and organisations. Regional rescue departments are responsible of safety communications and awareness raising in their region, for instance, by informing citizens of their self-acting obligations regarding emergency prevention and planning.

General awareness and communication is often coordinated through social media and news. Densely populated areas are equipped with stationary sirens and loudspeakers, which are used to warn the population with a predefined signal. These systems are maintained by the regional rescue services.

In addition, emergency warnings are broadcasted on the radio channels and TV. The Finnish Broadcasting Company (YLE) also issues emergency warnings via its website and teletext service. Warnings are always issued in Finnish and Swedish. If the danger or its consequences affect the Saami areas, the warning will also be given in Saami language.

Finland's main early warning system in the field of natural disasters, the LUOVA system, is a service for authorities that provides natural disaster warnings both in Finland and abroad. Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) works as LUOVA's main information provider and produces real-time situation awareness pictures with comprehensive information on dangerous weather, floods and earthquakes among other things. Other information providers include the Institute of Seismology of the University of Helsinki and the Finnish Environment Institute. FMI's LUOVA duty officer follows different information and observation sources every day around the clock and produces and conveys LUOVA-bulletin to the system when needed.

GERMANY

Risk communication is a strategic tool with a long-term orientation. It aims to raise awareness amongst the public of possible risks and to promote self-protection and self-help. There is a large

number of institutions and organisations that ensure the availability and dissemination of general information and data in different sectors, especially climate and environment, thereby contributing to raising public awareness of disaster risks (e.g., Deutscher Wetterdienst, Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz, Umweltbundesamt, Robert-Koch-Institut, Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum or Helmholtz Association etc.).

The Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance, as the responsible national executive agency for civil protection, offers a wide range of information, guidelines, and recommendations on disasters and risks. The aim is to improve the level of self-protection and self-help amongst the public, targeting both youth and adult population.

Early warning system is based on risk: Germany's national meteorological service (Deutscher Wetterdienst, DWD) is responsible for weather forecasting and issue of official warnings for weather phenomena posing a potential danger to the public or having high potential to cause damage. Flood forecasts and assessments are carried out by the flood forecasting and control centres of the Länder and in cooperation with the Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration. Seismological monitoring is ensured within the Länder, whilst the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR) collects a major amount of data.

The Federal Radiological Situation Centre (GRS) becomes active in the event of a radiological emergency.

The German Joint Information and Situation Centre (GMLZ) within the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance is a central interface to improve the sharing of knowledge and cooperation between the Federation and the Länder. As a specialist situation centre in the field of civil protection, GMLZ (i) prepares situation reports and prognosis, (ii) coordinates information and resources at the federal level, and (iii) serves as the national point of contact for a range of national and international information and warning procedures for the Federal Republic of Germany.

The authorities of the Länder (at the local level) are responsible for warning the population in case of an incident.

Possible types of communication channels include radio announcements, written information material, the internet or social media platforms, loudspeaker announcements from emergency response vehicles, "door-to-door" information or the use of sirens.

The Federation has set up MoWaS, a satellite-based modular warning system, for defence and crises that is available to the Länder as a central warning and information system.

A smartphone application called NINA, developed by the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance, is one of the possible channels used to disseminate warnings.

In the case of defence, the Federal Government is responsible for recording threats from aerial warfare and large-scale radiological hazards. For this purpose, a warning centre and two civil protection liaison cells (CDLC) are maintained. The CDLC's are co-located to NATO aerial warfare command posts (CAOC and CRC).

GREECE

Public information covers the whole disaster management cycle.

The General Secretariat for Civil Protection has a cross-sectoral and all-hazards competence, while hazard-specific communication is provided by public authorities in their sphere of competences. Information on all kinds of natural and man-made disasters including guidelines for self-protection is available, in Greek and foreign languages (English, Spanish, French, Albanian, and Arabic). These guidelines can be found on the site of the General Secretariat for Civil Protection.

Information is disseminated via various methods such as campaigns, TV and radio spots for specific disasters, publication of leaflets and brochures, electronic material, and school visits.

The General Secretariat for Civil Protection issues the daily forest fire risk map during the summer period. It is uploaded on its website and sent to all competent and local authorities involved in forest fires management.

Severe weather phenomena warnings are issued by the Hellenic National Meteorological Service.

Tsunami early warnings are provided by the Institute of Geodynamics, which hosts the Hellenic National Tsunami Warning Centre.

HUNGARY

The National Directorate General for Disaster Management Hazardous Plants Department within the nuclear emergency response area performs the tasks of the National Center for Nuclear Emergency Early Warning and International Radiological Monitoring Data Exchange System. It also plans, organises and coordinates the operation of the national RODOS Center, and manages data exchange at a national and international level. It analyses and evaluates the available data, and international radiological measurement data and results. The department provides data and information to the public on normal and extraordinary periodical information on the national and international background situation, carries out an assessment of the national broadcasting situation, and arrange for an emergency preparedness service for industrial purposes. It provides data and information for national nuclear safety and radiation protection assessment and decision-making. The department contributes to the work of the Committees on Nuclear Safety and Nuclear Emergency and participates in national and international nuclear emergency exercises, in-service training, and conferences. It is responsible for nuclear accident prevention and manages the tasks of the regional authorities of disaster management in the authorisation of radiological activities.

ICELAND

During disasters, the National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police/Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management plays an important part in the National Crisis and Coordination Centre to deal with risk communication. The team includes representatives from the ministries, Search and Rescue, the Red Cross and other key players in civil protection. The main purpose of the team is to inform the public, governmental and international organisations about the situation, send out situation reports and news releases.

Communication and awareness raising is through workshops, education and outreach. The public and government institutions are involved in the exchange of information on risk assessment, scenarios, and policy. Risk communication tools such as guidelines, SMS, social

media, websites, and information meetings with involved parties and the public promote risk reduction, risk awareness, and response.

The Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO) is the official monitoring organisation for natural hazards including early warning. During the early warning process, there is a daily communication between the National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police/Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management and the IMO. The same process applies for other monitoring organisation with early warning such as public health (the Directorate of Health and Epidemiology), the environment (the Environmental Agency) and infrastructure risks. When needed there is a meeting with the Civil Protection Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) which consists of specialists from the Icelandic Meteorological Office, the Institute of Earth Sciences, the Environmental Agency, the Medical Directorate of Health (epidemiology), the Occupational Safety and Health Agency, and the Food and Veterinary Agency. Experts from other agencies or institutes are called in if their expertise is required. During the early warning period information meetings are held with stakeholders from different organisation.

IRELAND

Met Eireann, the Irish Metrological Service, is responsible for issuing weather related warnings and alerts under a well-established “Traffic Light” and scaled system for severe weather events and is also responsible for naming storms within its remit. In addition, Met Eireann is at an advanced stage of developing a national flood forecast and warning system.

In relation to other public safety warnings, these would be matters for the National Emergency Coordination Group, chaired by the lead government department responsible, to consider on a case-by-case basis and who may utilise various protocols for allowing such messages to be broadcast across the national broadcast outlets over radio and television.

LATVIA

Civil Protection and Disaster Management Law states that people have the right to receive an early warning and recommendations regarding action in case of a disaster or threats, and to receive assistance from the state and local government authorities.

Brochures, social media channels such as Facebook and Twitter, and mass media channels such as TV and radio stations are used to inform people on how to prepare and what to do in the case of emergency or disaster.

Civil protection is integrated in the educational system of Latvia, where a mandatory course for the civil protection has been introduced, providing education about civil protection from young age.

The national risk assessment is a starting point for implementing early warning systems. After identifying risks, measures of preventive solutions can be undertaken, such as monitoring of the risks to detect potential forthcoming or occurring emergency. Latvia has implemented floods, radiological and nuclear emergencies, earthquakes, meteorological emergencies (storm, blizzard, tornadoes), epidemic emergencies, epiphytotic emergencies, forest fire early warning monitoring systems.

The Cabinet of Ministers Regulation No.440 ‘Procedures for the establishment, operation and financing of the National Early Warning System’ determine the State Fire and Rescue Service of

Latvia as the responsible institution for receiving information about threats of or information about the disaster from international organisations, state and local authorities, as well as individuals. The decision to activate the country-wide early warning system can be taken by the Chief of the State Fire and Rescue Service. However, in the administrative territory, this responsibility lies with the head of the territorial unit of the State Fire and Rescue Service. Not all disasters can be predicted, such as road accidents with a hazardous substance leak or a main gas pipelines accident. In such cases, the manager (incident commander) of rescue works informs the State Fire and Rescue Service of the need to activate early warning systems.

LUXEMBOURG

The CGDIS is the national contact point for multiple international early warning systems, and is in charge of transferring urgent messages to the relevant authorities. Depending on the type and scale of situation, the relevant authority manages public information.

In case of a major incident, Luxembourg has a dedicated nationwide network of electronic sirens, operated by the CGDIS.

Furthermore, information can be provided through TV, radio or internet by the communication service of the CGDIS or the crisis communication service of the HCPN.

The population alert system, which is an integral part of the state's crisis communication strategy, is an alert and information system via the sending of an SMS with national or even regional coverage and on a mobile application to inform and alert the population via notifications on mobile phones.

The GouvAlert application can be downloaded free of charge by smartphone users. The application allows the geolocation of the user and subscribers receive alert messages based on their exact geographical location.

MALTA

The National Risk Assessment report identifies several criteria on how to enhance public awareness and methods of communication and the mitigation of identified hazards.

The public is also informed by the Civil Protection Department via various methods such as safety awareness campaigns, TV programmes dealing with public safety, school visits and information pamphlets addressing different sections of society. Information is also disseminated to the public via the Civil Protection Facebook page and the official Ministerial website.

The early warning process to the public is the responsibility of the organisation or entity that is conducting its operations as stated in the pertinent legislation and the relative risk assessment.

The Civil Protection Department together with other agencies that respond to emergencies conduct information sessions during public activities together with the utilisation of other social media platforms, in order to bring awareness of identified risks to the public in general and also of specific emergencies that Malta could experience.

MONTENEGRO

The Rescue and Protection Directorate, through the Operational Communication Center (OCC 112), receives information on the occurrence of a hazard and using standard operating procedures, informs the competent authorities and other participants in protection and rescue.

The municipality is responsible for informing the public. OCC 112 collects data from municipal services and bodies involved in protection and rescue activities. The Rescue and Protection Directorate or the Operational Protection and Rescue Headquarter give official statements on the state of emergency.

Through projects supported by the EU, UN and other international organisations, the Rescue and Protection Directorate carried out campaigns for raising awareness of citizens. Target population were children, students at schools, people with disabilities and citizens in risk prone areas. The Directorate organises visits of the 112 Centre and presentations at schools to raise awareness.

The department for weather forecast within the Institute for Hydrometeorology and Seismology (IHMS) provides daily operational weather forecasts, based on the official prediction materials of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF Reading-London). In case of extreme weather, warnings are issued within EUMETNET (The Network of European Meteorological Services) in the Meteoalarm (Alert Europe for extreme weather) system (<http://www.meteoalarm.eu>). The Meteoalarm system is an integrated system, which consists of the national weather services, that warns of extreme weather situation. Within the system, online alerts for extreme weather are issued based on forecasts.

NORTH MACEDONIA:

The Crisis Management Centre is the central office for communication and its media centre informs the public and the mass media. The joint media centre is responsible for the preparation and transfer of information to the public and responsible ministries, preparing press conferences, and communicating with international media.

Within the Crisis Management Centre, the State Operations Centre functions at the national level 24 hours a day, 7 days in the week. The early warning and alert system is also part of the State Operations Centre.

POLAND

The basic characteristics of 19 risks with an assessment of their likelihood have been included in the national crisis management plan. Various brochures and manuals are available on the websites of national, regional and local authorities. Flood hazard and flood risk maps are available online. Flood risk management plans have also been developed after public consultations.

The Polish Geological Institute – National Research Institute (PIG – PIB) coordinates the landslide counteracting system (SOPO), which aims to assess the risk of landslides and develop forecasting and risk reduction systems. In addition, the initiative supports local authorities in performing their tasks related to geological mass movement. Text messages (“Alert RCB”), sirens and media are in use for early warning and alerting the population.

The Government Centre for Security (RCB) monitors threats in a 24/7 system, cooperating with various national and foreign authorities, depending on the type of threat. After receiving information about the threat, the RCB sends it to mobile networks operators, who immediately forward it to their subscribers. Anyone who has a mobile phone switched on, if present within the emergency messaging area (the ‘danger zone’), will receive a short text message (SMS)

informing about the type of threat. SMS will be issued only in exceptional life or health-threatening situations.

The mobile application RSO – Regionalny System Ostrzegania (the Regional Warning System) can be used to acquire detailed warnings and manuals on proper behaviour in the event of an emergency (it is currently only available in Polish).

PORTUGAL

The National Civil Protection Authority (ANPC) is the organic unit responsible for managing and advising on communication. This team is composed of elements with diverse training and experience, but the involvement of elements from other units of the organisation is common. It is also common for ANPC to establish partnerships with other organisations in order to adapt its risk information practices to specific target audiences. ANPC is the contact point with the Monitoring and Information Centre (MIC) based in Brussels, through its National Command for Rescue Operations.

The ECURIE (European Community Urgent Radiological Information Exchange) system is a programme run by the Directorate-General for Energy and Transport of the European Commission. Its aim is to ensure the rapid exchange of information in the event of an imminent or occurring nuclear accident/radiological emergency affecting any of the adhering countries (European Union countries and Switzerland). In Portugal, there are 2 points of contact:

- PT-1 - Portuguese Environment Agency whose mission is to receive the notifications of nuclear accidents or radiological emergencies occurring outside the national territory
- PT-2 - National Civil Protection Authority, which is responsible for international notifications of nuclear accidents or emergencies occurring on national territory. The ANPC acts as the permanent contact point

BICHAT is the information exchange system for chemical and biological threats and attacks of the European Commission and aims to provide Member States with a mechanism for rapid information sharing, consultation and coordination of health aspects related to possible or actual chemical and biological threats and attacks. In Portugal, the contact points are:

- National Contact Point (Competent Authority): Directorate-General of Health
- Permanent Point of Contact (24 hours): ANPC (National Command for Rescue Operations)

The National Tsunami Alert System which will issue messages in the event of a tsunami on or near the Portuguese coast. It is at the Portuguese Sea and Atmosphere Institute (IPMA). It relies on hundreds of sensors installed along the Portuguese coast that can detect any land movement or water displacement.

Portugal has a Specialised Centre for Urban Risks (CERU), based at the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon.

REPUBLIC OF CROATIA

Following the Act on Civil Protection System, the Ministry inform the public of the possible occurrence of a disaster, and about its developments. This is done together with competent

authorities of other government bodies, bodies of units of local and county (regional) self-government, and other professional services.

Furthermore, in the event of a major accident or disaster, also Civil Protection Headquarters inform the public.

If there is a threat, or in the event of a major accident or disaster, the media used for broadcasting the information are obliged to put their communication network/communication system at the disposal of the public authorities. This allows to transmit signals and notifications, and publish official statements.

The early warning system has 2 aspects: receiving alerts on various threats through designated systems (for example, EFAS – floods, EFFIS – fires, ECURIE – nuclear and radiological threats, etc.); warning and alarming the population on threats.

The focal point for exchanging information in case of emergency is the Civil Protection Operations Centre, which communicates with the Commission's Emergency Response Coordination Centre through CECIS. The excellent inter-institutional cooperation and exchange of information contribute to the efficiency and effectiveness of the early warning systems. The system is also supported by a regulation, which stipulates that all legal persons who could be source of risks in the perimeter of a threat need to have in place an alarming system. Early warning is carried out through sirens and media providing additional information on threats and measures to be taken.

REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS

Cyprus Civil Defence is currently in the process of creating a risk communication strategy.

Early warning systems towards professionals: IAEA; ECURIE (radiological/nuclear); NEAMTWS.
Early warning systems towards the population: Electronic sirens with island-wide coverage.

An island-wide ultra-high frequency radio system is used as an operating system. The sirens can be activated to alert the population during different disasters. The system also allows the transmission of vocal and pre-recorded messages.

ROMANIA

In order to disseminate preventive messages, the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations (IGSU) provides information and participates in live actions within the "RomaniaSigura" pages created on social networks (Facebook and Instagram). Among the support materials used in this campaign, video spots have been broadcasted nationally since November 2018. Together with the county emergency inspectorates, prevention activity is present on radio and TV programmes, also through articles in print media. Moreover, printed materials, such as brochures and flyers, related to preventive information are disseminated within local communities.

In Romania, early warning systems consists of detection stations with analytics software, alarm stations, email, fax and phone to alert local authorities and cell broadcast messages systems (the emergency warning system "RO-ALERT"), television, radio, and alarm sirens. For example, in case of earthquakes, within the emergency operation centre there is a software application for monitoring and sending rapid notifications in case of strong earthquakes. The population

receives post-earthquake information messages on the recommended measures (cell broadcast messages via RO-ALERT and voice messages via electronic sirens).

SLOVAKIA

Communicating risks to the population is an established and on-going effort, with the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic as a main authority. Communication to the public is carried out by communication departments specifically designated for this goal.

Raising awareness is a task carried by multiple stakeholders coordinated by the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic. Responsibilities are divided geographically (from local/regional to national level) and by target audience. Several examples of awareness raising activities include: educational activities in schools, competitions for children and young people, international 112 emergency number day, publications for general and/or expert public.

Early warning systems are a collaborative work of public authorities operating and maintaining national civil protection warning systems with private operators of important infrastructure, which are responsible for autonomous warning systems. The main warning method is sirens supplemented by spoken information and also broadcasting the alerts on radio and TV.

A section of Crisis Management of the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic, more specifically its coordination and response centre bears the responsibility of engaging the warning and providing the necessary information.

Scientific institutions and organisations provide the input data, which is needed for decision making. These are the Slovak Hydro-meteorological Institute, the Public Health Office, the Nuclear Supervision Office. Organisations such as these are operating a nationwide network of sensors and monitoring equipment that feeds into the system and is used as a basis for early warning.

The most frequent (annual) use of early warning systems is during extreme weather events (thunderstorms, torrential rain) when the population is informed about the potential flooding risks or landslides, which are the most common threat at every level.

SLOVENIA

Disaster or emergency related information is disseminated to the public via traditional media and social media, including television, radio, the Internet, Facebook, twitter, and teletext. Awareness raising is also integral. The public are given instructions for personal protection and preparedness before and during a range of different types of natural and man-made disasters.

In recent years, the Internet has proven to be a useful tool for informing the public. Therefore, the ACPDR's website provides comprehensive information on how to act before and during disasters and on preventive and preparedness measures, as well as information about warnings, alarm signals, and other important information.

In Slovenia, sirens are a public warning system for the population. The alarm signals includes: general warnings signals and special local signals. The testing of sirens takes place every first Saturday in a month at noon. There are three general warning signals: threat warning, imminent threat, and end of threat. There are special local signals for an imminent threat of a chlorine accident and imminent threat of a flood wave.

Additionally, traditional and social media are used as a means to broadcast additional information about the natural or man-made disaster.

The Emergency Notification Centre of the Republic of Slovenia is responsible for monitoring the events and issues alerts and warnings when emergencies occur and for the activation of sirens to raise the alarm in case of emergencies. The centre receives meteorological information and compiles a bulletin in which warning information is inserted and distributed to the public. The centre is also responsible for informing other countries (bilateral agreements) and organisations (EU, UN, NATO) about the disasters in Slovenia and possible cross-border effects, and for sending requests for international assistance. It is also the contact point for the information on disasters in other countries and requests for provision of international assistance in the case of major disasters abroad.

SPAIN

The communication of risks and the population awareness is carried out through an active methodology based on community meetings and the dissemination of videos, posters, brochures and guides adapted to children, teenagers, and adults. Self-protection recommendations are provided to the population in written language and through explanatory videos about how to behave in case of emergency. Besides, guides dealing with the different risks have been issued for the primary and secondary school pupils in order to learn and practice prevention and self-protection measures. A technical guide for prevention was recently published. The guide is addressed to the responsible bodies in charge of implementing information and awareness programmes for the population potentially affected by the different risks.

In addition, Twitter is used to disseminate information on risks and emergency information in real time.

The National Meteorological Agency (AEMET) issues warning bulletins related with meteorological hazards such as rain, storms, wind, and snow. Hydrological data are collected by the National Water Office and the river basins offices and submitted to the civil protection authorities. A project is currently in development to unify the information collected in each river basin and to define the threshold that could alert the authorities when the level of water would reach a certain level.

The radioactivity alert network (RAR) constantly measures Gamma radiation levels throughout the national territory, monitors its trends, and immediately detects abnormal radiation levels that would require the triggering of the corresponding actions as defined in the emergency plans for nuclear and radiological hazards. The network contains more than 900 measurement points (sensor plus control unit) distributed across the mainland and the two archipelagos, with the central node located at the DGPCE.

The National Seismic Network, is the public body responsible for detection, monitor and alert triggering to all civil protection and government authorities in order to allow response plans activation against seismic and volcanic risk. It runs, deploys and maintains more than 150 seismic detections devices and accelerometers country wide, with other techniques for volcano monitoring connected in real time to a data centre located at the National Geographic Institute facilities.

Other agencies, like the Oceanographic Institute, Geological Institute and the National Seaport Management Authority collaborate with other complementary instruments, such as sea level and tidal waves detection instruments, in order to set up a national tsunami warning centre.

All the information provided by the monitoring organisations, is distributed close to real time to the National Emergency Centre (CENEM), at the Dirección General de Protección Civil y Emergencias (DGPCE).

SWEDEN

In 2017 Sweden decided that it was necessary to inform the population about how different crises and war can affect daily lives and about the ways to prepare in order to handle a severe strain on society. The booklet *If Crisis or War Comes* was distributed to all households. The Emergency Preparedness Week was initiated by the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) to increase risk awareness and crises preparedness of population, and make the municipalities develop measures to communicate about crisis preparedness to their inhabitants.

The website *Dinsäkerhet.se* gives risk information to the public (films, podcasts, checklists). Social media platforms are another platform for communication. The primary early warning system is radio, TV, and the outdoor alarm system of 4,500 alarm installations using sirens. A SMS system sends warnings to mobile phones in an affected area.

The fire brigades who mainly use this system and the chief in command has the mandate to use it. The police and other organisations can also use this system.

Separate indoor and outdoor alarm systems operate in the inner emergency planning zone around Sweden's nuclear power stations.

The Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) issues weather reports and warnings to the public via the official radio and TV-channels. SMHI is also a service provider to the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS). SMHI calculates the fire risk for grass fire and forest fires. SMHI communicates information about when there is a high fire risk to municipalities, county administrative boards, the public, the forest industry, and the media. Sweden communicates the risk levels for forest fire divided into 6 different levels. The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency and SMHI, have a special service that also shows the risk of thunder and lightning strikes and various weather indicators.

5.5.2.3. Current situation in other countries focused in channels and means

We have seen that there are different means of communicating alerts and warnings. This communication ranges from more traditional systems, such as sirens, to the use of more modern technologies and the exploitation of social networks.

Electronic siren's that can be activated to alert the population during different disasters are a common early warning system and alert developed in many EU countries.

The population alert system based on mobile, which is an integral part of the disaster crisis communication strategy, is an alert and information system via sending of a SMS or voice calls with national or even regional coverage and on a mobile application to inform and alert the population via notifications on mobile phones. The purpose of the SMS alert and information system for the population is to inform and alert the entire population or to inform and alert only a part of the population in the immediate environment of the danger (risk zone). This system

also called Wireless Emergency alert (WEA) is widely used in several countries around the world including the **United States of America (USA)**, formerly known as the Commercial Mobile Alert System, is an alerting network in U.S. designed to disseminate emergency alerts to mobile devices such as cell phones and pagers.

WEA is a public safety system that allows customers who own compatible mobile devices geographically targeted, text like messages alerting them of imminent threats to safety in their area.

Wireless companies volunteer to participate in WEA, which is the result of a unique public/private partnership between the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the Federal Communications Commission, and the U.S. industry in order to enhance public safety.

<https://www.fcc.gov/consumers/guides/wireless-emergency-alerts-wea>

Several counties in U.S have adopted the use of the Integrated Public Alert and Warning System (IPAWS). This System was created under Executive Order 13407 to integrate various alerting systems— Emergency Alert System, National Warning System, Wireless Emergency Alerts, and NOAA Weather Radio All Hazards—into one modern network. IPAWS takes advantage of the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), an XML-based data format for exchanging alerts and warnings.

Technical standards play an important role in communication systems. As such, a single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, WiFi, Bluetooth). The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities (alert originators, the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, public safety, broadcasters and mobile operators. This standard takes the form of an XML format and is one of the many standardized XML formats that the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards maintains. The CAP standard describes how the information is formatted. While CAP provides a common format, any changes in the type of information exchanged in CAP or any changes in how the carriers might communicate this information to a wireless subscriber requires additional standards and versions of those standards.

Emergency Alert and Warning Systems: Current Knowledge and Future Research Directions (2018) <http://nap.nationalacademies.org/249358>

WhatNow Service, developed by the Red Cross and Red Crescent's Global Disaster Preparedness Centre, in partnership with [Google](#), is designed to increase the speed and dissemination of disaster preparedness and risk reduction messages. It is founded on [IFRC's Public Awareness and Public Education \(PAPE\)](#) key messages for disaster risk reduction, covering 20+ hazards. Red Cross/Red Crescent (RC/RC) National Societies adapt these multi-hazard key action messages to their local risks, language, and context to ensure consistency, clarity, and safety.

Figure 71 - WhatNow Service operates in a five-step process

- **Step 1:** Red Cross Red Crescent National Societies work with GDPC to upload localized messages on the global WhatNow Message Portal.
- **Step 2:** Red Cross Red Crescent National Societies engages with Media partners about WhatNow.
- **Step 3:** Media networks access WhatNow messages through API and broadcast alongside hazard alerts they already disseminate on their platforms. The Message Viewer is available for printing and sharing and social media communications.
- **Step 4:** At-risk communities receive WhatNow messages from many communication channels.
- **Step 5:** Red Cross Red Cross National Societies engage with communities for feedback.

As part of the global Red Cross and Red Crescent network, the [Global Disaster Preparedness Center \(GDPC\) - Home Global Disaster Preparedness Center \(preparecenter.org\)](#) - promotes innovation in disaster preparedness and supports learning and knowledge sharing amongst disaster preparedness practitioners worldwide. Through the [Universal App Program Universal App Program - PrepareCenter-](#), the GDPC has created a platform to facilitate the adaptation and localization of mobile applications (apps) with first aid and hazard information for use in countries across the globe. This easily-adaptable mobile app platform—based on [American Red Cross mobile apps](#)—is designed to be customized by RC/RC National Societies around the world, ensuring that the content is appropriate and relevant to each local context.

A crucial part of the customization of Universal App is the requirement to enable access to official alerts that are targeted to people in the particular area covered. The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) - an XML-based data format for exchanging public warnings and emergencies between alerting technologies standard, also known as ITU-T Recommendation X.1303, is essential to achieving this requirement because it standardizes the format and some aspects of the content of alert messages. For instance, CAP-enabled warnings typically include geographic information so that alerts can be more precise in geo-targeting just those people who need to be alerted. Various elements of a CAP alert message are designed for automated filtering and t Guide describes how the Universal App Program uses those CAP elements to identify alert messages that should be disseminated by RC/RC National Societies in their role in helping official alerting authorities to communicate emergency warnings to the public. It is likely that more than 50 countries will have at least one operational CAP alert feed operational by the end of 2016, serving more than half of the world's population. As of this writing, 70 countries have deployed Universal First Aid apps (in 31 languages).

Documents and guides have been published in order to describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings" that is used by the Universal App Program -[Universal App: Identifying High Priority Public Warnings - PrepareCenter](#), for example, this guide describes the technique used by the Universal App Program for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property.

Whether any particular alert should be treated as a high priority public warning is primarily a matter of policy. However, this Guide does not deal with policy; it deals only with the technical matter of how an alert in CAP format is identified as a high priority public warning in the Universal Hazard app context.

OASIS project, an organization that supports open source communities in a wide range of open collaboration projects, has developed Technical Committees for member-developed works about information exchange to advance incident preparedness and response to emergency situations. The OASIS Emergency Management Framework (EMF) is a reference implementation and toolkit for enabling standardized emergency information exchange using the OASIS Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL). With the EMF, developers and users can create, send, store, template, visualize, search, and organize emergency messages. EDXL provides standardized alerting, resource sharing, situation reporting, tracking of emergency patients and clients, hospital availability, as well as packaging and addressing of emergency messages and attachments. Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) is a family of standards, providing a common language, or interface, for data exchange across emergency-related systems.

https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=emergency

5.5.2.4. Public response to alert and warning

Another very relevant aspect is the response of the public to alerts and warnings. Research has evolved over the last several decades so that we have much more information about how individuals respond to alerts and warnings. Nevertheless, as technologies shift, so do public responses. It is necessary to continue research. These responses rely on several things, including characteristics of the messages themselves, demographics of the individuals who receive the messages, and, given our increased ability to geo-target messages, the understanding of an individual's risk in relationship to their location and the hazard. Research is also needed to understand how best to educate the public about both alerting systems and impacts of and appropriate response to different hazards.

Principal conclusions from the literature that influence the effectiveness of warnings are:

1. Warnings are most effective when delivered to just the people at risk. If people not at risk are warned, they will tend to ignore future warnings. Thus, if tornado or flash-flood warnings, for example, are issued for a county or larger region, but only a small percentage of the people who receive the warning are ultimately affected, most people conclude that such warnings are not likely to affect them.

2. If warnings that are not followed by the anticipated event are inconvenient, people are likely to disable the warning device. For example, if you are awakened in the middle of the night to be warned of several events that do not ultimately affect you, you are likely to disable the warning device.

3. Appropriate response to warning is most likely to occur when people have been educated about the hazard and have developed a plan of action well before the warning (Liu et al., 1996 Assessment of a severe-weather warning system and disaster preparedness. Alabama. Journal of Public Health vol.86 (pag 87-89)).

4. There is a window of opportunity to capture peoples' attention and encourage appropriate action. Studies of responses to tornado warnings, for example, found that those who sought shelter did so within five minutes of first becoming aware of the tornado warnings (Balluz et al., 1997 Predictors for people's response to a tornado warning: Arkansas. Disaster 24 (1) 74-77).

5. A variety of warning devices needs to be used in order to reach people according to what activity they are engaged in.

6. Warnings must be issued in ways that are understood by the many different people within our diverse society.

7. The probabilistic nature of warnings, particularly for natural disasters, needs to be made clear.

Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news. Rumours and misinformation have been identified as a significant threat to the utility of social media and other online tools during disaster events. Many emergency responders cite misinformation on social media as a major concern and a barrier to adopting social media in their work. Disinformation includes false or misleading information purposefully spread to mislead or confuse others—possibly for malicious purposes. Disinformation represents a particularly insidious threat, especially in connected information environments where malicious actors from outside of the affected area may try to interfere with response efforts or intentionally manipulate behaviour to put people in harm's way

Among the private initiatives to support administrations in the management of crises in a digital scenario, the Virtual Operation Support Team (VOST) appears.

These teams are made up of professionals from the world of emergencies who collaborate altruistically with the accounts of the emergency services on Twitter in the monitoring of social networks to go viral prevention messages and the detection of hoaxes.

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American Red Cross launched the first Digital Operations Centre in 2011 in Washington, extending both throughout the Americas and throughout Europe. Currently these teams exist in Canada, Australia, United Kingdom, New Zealand, Italy, among others.

In Spain, thanks to the success @vostSPAIN during the 2012 forest fire campaign, VOST accounts were extended throughout the autonomous communities and the autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla.

Figure 72 - World VOSG distribution³³

5.5.2.5. Proposal for decision making in alert and warning

Alert and warning systems exist within a larger communication and technical ecosystem, and government-designed and maintained systems must fit within this larger ecosystem.

A more cohesive and all-encompassing alert and warning system is needed that will integrate public and private communications mechanisms and sources of information, and continue to provide the necessary information for the purpose of preserving the health and safety of people, such that new technologies for alerts and warnings can be adopted quickly.

The nation's alerting capabilities, such as alert system based on mobile, like WEA and IPAWS, will need to evolve and progress as the capabilities of smartphones and other mobile broadband devices improve and newer technologies become available. This evolution will need to be informed by both technical research and social and behavioural science research.

Performance monitoring can be undertaken throughout the life cycle of an alert. In some cases, new standards may need to be adopted or new technologies created to support monitoring and

³³ <http://vosteuropa.org>

<http://www.vost.es>

feedback. Similarly, new social science research will be needed to assess the usefulness of metrics.

Examples of possible measurements of interest could include the following:

- Coverage. How many people (or devices) received a message? And what fraction of all affected people is this? What are the characteristics of those who did not receive a message, and how can this gap be closed?
- Message engagement. How long did people view a message? Was it immediately dismissed? Tracking other activity on a smartphone may gain additional evidence of engagement with a message and follow-up activities (e.g., phoning a friend, checking social media feeds). Of course, privacy is a paramount concern here.
- Actions taken. Upon receiving a message, how many people take action? And what actions are these? Perhaps structured responses can be created so that people can do a “safety check” or equivalent, depending on the nature of the alert. Careful design of feedback mechanisms is important.
- Latency. What is the time from the inciting incident to when the message was received by users? Latency here could be measured at different levels of granularity—including network performance measures based on when a message is injected, time from inciting incident to message injection itself, and so on.
- Translation effectiveness. Measurements of engagement with a message can also provide downstream understanding of the quality of upstream decisions. For example, it could be beneficial for social media companies to provide aggregate (anonymized) measurements in the aftermath of an alert.

Among the principles which guided the design of the Alert Message (based on CAP) were:

- Interoperability – First and foremost, the Alert Message should provide a means for interoperable exchange of alerts and notifications among all kinds of emergency information systems.
- Completeness – The CAP Alert Message format should provide for all the elements of an effective public warning message.
- Simple implementation – The design should not place undue burdens of complexity on technical implementers.
- Simple XML and portable structure – Although the primary anticipated use of the CAP Alert Message is as an XML document, the format should remain sufficiently abstract to be adaptable to other coding schemes.
- Multi-use format – One message schema supports multiple message types (e.g., alert / update / cancellations / acknowledgements / error messages) in various applications (actual / exercise / test / system message).
- Familiarity – The data elements and code values should be meaningful to warning originators and non-expert recipients alike.
- Interdisciplinary and international utility – The design should allow a broad range of applications in public safety and emergency management and allied applications and should be applicable worldwide.

Requirements for Design

Note: The following requirements were used as a basis for design and review of the CAP Alert Message format. This list is non-normative and not intended to be exhaustive.

The Common Alerting Protocol SHOULD:

- Provide a specification for a simple, extensible format for digital representation of warning messages and notifications;
- Enable integration of diverse sensor and dissemination systems;
- Be usable over multiple transmission systems, including both TCP/IP-based networks and one-way "broadcast" channels;
- Support credible end-to-end authentication and validation of all messages;
- Provide a unique identifier (e.g., an ID number) for each warning message and for each message originator;
- Provide for multiple message types, such as:
 - Warnings
 - Acknowledgements
 - Expirations and cancellations
 - Updates and amendments
 - Reports of results from dissemination systems
 - Administrative and system messages
- Provide for multiple message types, such as:
 - Geographic targeting
 - Level of urgency
 - Level of certainty
 - Level of threat severity
- Provide a mechanism for referencing supplemental information (e.g., digital audio or image files, additional text);
- Use an established open-standard data representation;
- Be based on a program of real-world cross-platform testing and evaluation;
- Provide a clear basis for certification and further protocol evaluation and improvement; and,
- Provide a clear logical structure that is relevant and clearly applicable to the needs of emergency response and public safety users and warning system operators.

General Recommendations in Monitoring and Warning Service

1. Institutional Mechanisms Established

- Standardized process, and roles and responsibilities of all organizations generating and issuing warnings established and mandated by law.
- Agreements and interagency protocols established to ensure consistency of warning language and communication channels where different hazards are handled by different agencies.
- An all-hazard plan to obtain mutual efficiencies and effectiveness among different warning systems established.

- Warning system partners, including local authorities, aware of which organizations are responsible for warnings.
- Protocols in place to define communication responsibilities and channels for technical warning services.
- Communication arrangements with international and regional organizations agreed and operational.
- Regional agreements, coordination mechanisms and specialized centers in place for regional concerns such as tropical cyclones, floods in shared basins, data exchange, and technical capacity building.
- Warning system subjected to system-wide tests and exercises at least once each year.
- A national or SupraNational all-hazards committee on technical warning systems in place and linked to national disaster management and reduction authorities, including the national platform for disaster risk reduction.
- System established to verify that warnings have reached the intended recipients.
- Warning Centers staffed at all times (24 hours per day, seven days per week).

2. Monitoring Systems Developed

- Measurement parameters and specifications documented for each relevant hazard.
- Plans and documents for monitoring networks available and agreed with experts and relevant authorities.
- Technical equipment, suited to local conditions and circumstances, in place and personnel trained in its use and maintenance.
- Applicable data and analysis from regional networks, adjacent territories and international sources accessible.
- Data received, processed and available in meaningful formats in real time, or near-real time.
- Strategy in place for obtaining, reviewing and disseminating data on vulnerabilities associated with relevant hazards.
- Data routinely archived and accessible for verification and research purposes.

3. Forecasting and Warning Systems Established

- Data analysis, prediction and warning generation based on accepted scientific and technical methodologies.
- Data and warning products issued within international standards and protocols.
- Warning analysts trained to appropriate international standards.
- Warning centers equipped with appropriate equipment needed to handle data and run prediction models.

- Fail-safe systems in place, such as power back-up, equipment redundancy and on-call personnel systems.
- Warnings generated and disseminated in an efficient and timely manner and in a format suited to user needs.

In summary, education, testing and measurement are necessary for early warning systems's success.

5.5.2.6. Standards and methodology

Finally, another necessary aspect is the standardization of procedures, techniques, processes related to alerts and early warning systems. Certification is the procedure by which an external observer evaluates the quality of a product, process, management system or service. In the specific case of the warning systems there are various ISO standards (The International Organization for Standardization) that should be taken into account due to their special international relevance to the issue that we are reviewing: alert and warning. The aspects to be highlighted will be detailed properly below these lines.

UNE-EN ISO 22315:2018

UNE-EN ISO 22315:2018. Societal security. Mass evacuation. Guidelines for planning (ISO 22315:2014) (Endorsed by Asociación Española de Normalización in April of 2020).

It is granted the rank of Spanish normative document UNE. 1st edition. English version.

In this document are given the following terms and definitions: incident management system, preparedness, community-based warning system, area at risk and affected area.

There is a mention about the general aspects for mass evacuation planning, including how should be developed the risk assessments, the compliance with legislation and policies (operating at international, national, regional and local levels), the information gathering and analysis, the planning operational resource allocation and documenting processes, the effective multi-agency partnering arrangements and the training and exercising.

There is also a mention about how should be prepared the public for mass evacuation. This clause describes the value of identifying how the public can prepare for mass evacuation, how to use research findings when developing plans, identify key characteristics of the population depending on the characteristics of the public (age, gender, culture, language spoken, socio-economic etc), evaluate each identified social group, introduce products, services, and activities which improve preparedness and reduce barriers to preparing for mass evacuation.

In the following section it focuses on the visualization of the areas that are at risk or affected. To achieve this it describes the need to contribute with map data about the area that is at risk or affected, considering types of information to capture on maps and ensuring the compatibility of data to build maps, developing what criteria must be met.

Talking about how to make the evacuation decision, the organization should identify a process to help decision-makers be prepared to order and implement an evacuation, describing the

following steps in the process as follows: develop an evacuation decision-making process, use evacuation objectives, resolve conflicting evacuation objectives, identify information needed to order an evacuation, ensure that decision-makers have access to needed information, identify factors that drive decisions for specific risks and develop a system to track and log decisions made.

Same as in ISO standard 22322 and in accordance with the process developed in this, it is addressed public warning. In this it is described the activities related to alerting the public for mass evacuation: systems to warn and inform the public, promote a community-based warning system, protocols for communication with various stakeholders, design and test of a template for the warning message and analyse the anticipated time to warn the public.

In the next section the organization analyse evacuee movement, guaranteeing that plans encourage safe and quick evacuations. To achieve that purpose the organization should: understanding potential population movement, understanding evacuees' transportation behaviour, identifying demand and availability of the transport network, identifying transport performance measures and targets, analysing transport strategies and policies and communicating transport information to the public.

In the last section it is assessed the evacuee shelter requirements, describing how to understand the following shelter requirements: estimate shelter demand, identify suitable shelters, establish shelter agreements, analyse shelter availability during the incident, manage evacuee registration and support services, organize shelter supplies and mutual aid and develop a safe return plan.

ISO 22322:2015

ISO 22322:2015. Societal security. Emergency management. Guidelines for public warning. 1st edition. English version.

This ISO standard reflects the normative references and define the following terms: alert, all clear, hazard monitoring function, warning dissemination function, notification, people at risk, public warning system and vulnerable group.

It relies on 2 figures to describe two main concepts: the public warning system and the public warning process. The public warning system is described with the enumeration of the steps to follow: design the framework, identify public warning objectives, implement the public warning process and evaluate and improve. The result of the assessment made for the organization should determine the type of public warning that may be required and documented for future references.

Speaking of the public warning process, it is described with the same steps structure: hazard monitoring process, operational decision-making, warning dissemination process and human factor considerations.

In both cases the organization develop various interesting approaches in detail: how should be developed the planning, who are the responsible and what are their functions, what are the main characteristics included and what criteria should be met.

This guide also included 2 annexes. In Annex A establish an interesting relationship between alert and notification in public warning. In Annex B makes reference to public awareness.

ISO 22324:2015**ISO 22324:2015. Societal security. Emergency management. Guidelines for colour-coded alerts.** 1st edition. English version.

It reflects the normative references and define the following terms: alert, colour blindness, colour-code and hue.

Colour-coded alerts are used to notify people at risk of status changes on a safety or danger continuum in allowing them to take appropriate actions. This ISO standard develops the guidance for use of colour coded alerts and describe the colour-coded alerts to express the status of hazard. There are mentioned the typical colours for colour-coding system, with several scales (with 3, 5 and 7 colours). It reflects the importance of the order and positioning for the red, yellow and green spectrum and the colour-codes to give supplementary information, explaining the use of each colour.

Figure 73 - ISO colour codes for alert and warning

Moreover, it establishes considerations for human factors and colour blindness.

This guidance also included different annexes: examples on the use of colour codes in practice (international nuclear and radiological event scale, triage tags and meteorological map) and recommendations for colour selection.

As it is structured in coloured figures is a great visual aid.

ISO 22328-1:2020**ISO 22328-1:2020. Security and resilience. Emergency management.****Part 1: General guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warning system.**

1st edition. English version.

It reflects the normative references and define the following terms: community vulnerability, early warning, community-based early warning system/community-based EWS (early warning system), evacuation command and evacuation drill.

The community-based disaster early warning system should comprise five main sub-systems: risk assessment, dissemination and communication of knowledge, monitoring and warning service, response capability and commitment of the authority and community on the sustainability of the EWS.

A special attention is focused on the development of the response capability. The community should be able to respond to disasters in sufficient time with the right manner. For that purpose, the authority should establish a disaster preparedness team, who could determine an evacuation shelter, developing an evacuation map and routes, developing standard operating procedures and conducting an evacuation drill.

Finally, it develops 5 interesting examples of a community disaster preparedness team, of a layout of the evacuation map and routes, of a scheme of a community-based early warning system, of a flow of warning information and evacuation command and of an evacuation standard operating procedure.

5.5.3. Landscape

The following items have been consulted in the WP5 questionnaire in relation to this section Alert and warning:

- Alert and Warning Responsibility (Agency): (Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others)
- Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure Available?
- Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure standardized at national level?
- Crisis Alert and Warning Means (Free text)
- Perception of needs: (Free text). Needs/shortcomings existing in the respondent's environment in relation to the issues raised in the questionnaire

Following the analysis of the questionnaires/surveys during the Valkyries project WP5 execution, the Landscape picture on operational/workflows/engaged roles and practices in COP organization procedures and between different countries is as in the following table.

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Alert and Warning Responsibility (Agency)	Civil Protection > Firefighters > EMS = Police > Rescuers = Army	High
Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure Available	Yes	Very high
Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure standardized at national level	Yes	Medium

Items	Most common answers in the Survey	Homogeneity between countries
Crisis Alert and Warning Means	Media > Mobile SMS > Sirens = Radiostations > 112 EOC > Loudspeakers = email = Internet = Social media	High

Table 10 - WP5 questionnaire: Alert and warning answers

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS:

In relation to the Agency responsible for alerting and warning in the event of an MCI or disaster, the surveys show that in 50% of cases it is Civil Protection, followed by the Fire Brigade and, to a lesser extent, the Police or the EMS. The military or rescuers account for a very low percentage of cases.

Figure 74 – Agency responsible for alert and warning according to the Emergency Response Plan

In approximately 80% of the cases, the existence of a crisis alert and warning procedure is confirmed, and of these 80% would be standardised at national level. Services that have no potential involvement in cross-national MCI or disaster response have a higher percentage of alert and warning procedures than the rest, but it is striking that in these cases the proportion of procedures that are standardised at the national level is lower.

Figure 75 – Alert and warning procedure according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

In disaster situations, the means of alerting and warning are mainly broadcast media and mobile phone notification systems via SMS, in addition to the classic resources of sirens and radio frequency networks. There is curiously little mention of the 112 centres as issuers of alerts, and the use of resources derived from the internet and social networks is still very marginal.

Figure 76 – Crisis alert and warning available means

Emergency services potentially involved in cross-national MCI or disaster response rely almost exclusively on 112 radio networks, broadcast media and SMS systems, as well as sirens. But it is interesting to note that the percentage of broadcast media use is lower than that found in the rest of the services.

Figure 77 – Crisis alert and warning available means according to potential involvement or not in response to cross-national MCI or disasters

5.5.4. Perception of needs

In relation to other needs perceived by the experts surveyed, the following needs emerged from the questionnaires carried out:

- Different C2 centres located for Medical and non-medical Responses to disasters
- Coordination of different institutions and between different regions exchanging COP
- Outdated technology and systems.
- Lack of training and specific standard operation procedures.

6. Legal barriers and ethical concerns

A first ethical and legal challenge to face in developing a homogeneous landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first responders is determined by the necessity to build up structures where decisions are taken considering a proportionate balance between the different fundamental rights affected by the given situation.

Therefore, agencies and institution shall allocate roles and responsibilities among instructed and trained staff that could effectively apply the most efficient and ethically acceptable decision in each circumstance.

Operational and procedural plans and guidelines shall provide the parameters to allow the implementation of technical and organizational safeguards in order to ensure case-by-case the mitigation of general as well as specific risks against fundamental rights protection.

To this end, considering the general goal of first response actions to promptly treat patients, it is mandatory to harmonize procedure of responsible decision-making to timely share information and to pool them for crisis response planning, logistic deployment of resources, and alerts and warnings sharing.

In this regard, training and awareness activities specifically addressed to develop competence oriented to balance different rights in emergency crisis for first responders could be particularly useful to contribute to the ethical-legally dimension of the emergency responses.

In fact, actions shall be the result of a proportionate balance between pros and cons, considering the implementation of possible mitigation measures in alignment with relevant principles that are framing the ethical-legal landscape.

As the data sharing and information plays an essential role, a good understanding of regulatory principles of the European Data Strategy could add value to the first response actions and plans. In particular, especially in triage procedure development, to ensure the application of the data minimisation principle in terms of nature of data collected, duration of collection, and possible recipients of data flows, would ensure to avoid non-necessary data collection, and, therefore, unlawful patients' data processing. Each balance provided under the principle of minimisation, thus, will be functional properly enable data pooling activities, driving the opportunity to share data as open as possible among institutions and organisations for disaster management purposes.

At the same time, considering the value to exploit data for further analysis and monitoring activities, as emerged in this document, operational procedure shall include in each step a section to promptly pseudonymise personal data in order to maintain information available for further uses either to manage different steps of the given emergency or to analyse causes and consequences for future actions. Also under this ground of analysis, the legal dimension consists of ensuring that data management strategy and corresponding regulatory principles are embedded in guidelines, standards, and procedure in order to be applied in the decision-making process.

7. Conclusions

7.1. WP5 conclusion

Mass casualty incidents, MCI, and disasters are situations that overwhelm the response capacity of emergency services, at least for some time.

The response to these events often reveals insufficient resources (rescue personnel, medical personnel, facilities, etc.), communication difficulties and organisational interoperability problems, which are exacerbated in cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical actions.

The first step in a harmonisation process is the description and analysis of the current state of the art. The aim of this document is to complete this first step through literature review, consultation and discussion among experts, to define the existing picture of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response in multi-casualty disasters in the EU, focusing mainly on the VALKYRIES use cases and in the countries participating in the Project.

Throughout its different sections, this document provides an overview related to:

- Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- Maintenance, logistics and Deployment
- Command and Control and support to operational decision-making
- Common Operational Picture
- Alert and warning

The most relevant findings under each of these sections are detailed below.

7.2. Task conclusions

7.2.1. Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning

Disaster management at the European level shares a common approach and structure, so that any country in need of assistance for an MCI or disaster is able to integrate into its civil protection system the teams mobilised through the European mechanism.

The different EU countries have crisis response plans that are standardised at national level. These plans indicate which action groups are part of their structure and what their functions and actions are. The teams that are mobilised to assist a country are integrated into a specific action group, which must have a specific procedure for action adapted, if necessary, to the type of emergency.

It is essential that the plans are implemented and updated, which entails their dissemination among the different agencies involved and the population, as well as their implementation through exercises and drills that allow lessons to be learned and the plan to be revised if necessary.

In relation to the operability of the plans, in the event that they are activated to respond to cross-sector and/or cross-border disasters, it is vital that there are procedures for action, as well as tools that allow for interoperability between services and regions, facilitating the exchange of information for decision-making and coordination.

Relevant aspects such as the minimum information needed to declare a multi-victim incident and activate the specific procedure for its management, or the triage system to be used for victim care, must be taken into account when harmonising and pre-standardising crisis response.

The reality of crisis response plans in our study environment shows that most of the plans in place are national and regional in scope.

There is a high percentage of agencies that could be involved in transnational crises that are part of national response plans, but the percentage of cases where transnational plans are in place is small.

Regarding operational procedures, the degree of homogeneity is generally high in the different territories in relation to the operational responsibilities assigned to the different Emergency Services: Firefighters: risk control and zoning; Police: security; EMS: victim care,

7.2.2. Maintenance, logistics and Deployment

Humanitarian organizations provide services to people in need during emergencies, and therefore those are closed or handed over to local authorities or organizations when the emergency recedes and the need for (international) assistance decreases as they have limited resources.

Logistics in emergency scenarios is heavily influenced by uncertainty, as there is no way to predict where it will occur and to what extent. The standardization of processes and resources must be readjusted to suit the individual event.

Because disaster preparedness is competing with time, have technological and up-to-date tools with personnel who know how to use these tools in disaster preparedness, as effective communication, information sharing, and decision-making play a vital role in order to minimize casualties and restore destroyed areas in a timely manner. Logistics operations involve the management of personnel, assets, supplies, facilities, and vehicles. This is done by cooperating in disaster response operations in the first relief phase and by concretely sharing—at the operational and strategic levels—agility goals, principles, and guidelines implemented in the humanitarian supply chain.

Based on the results obtained in our questionnaires, there is extensive standardisation within each nation in terms of ambulances equipment, ambulances crew and crew training.

In most cases, the items considered basic for emergency services in the event of an MCI or disaster are available, as well as the storage provisions and operational plans necessary for the proper implementation of support logistics, but in most cases not standardised at the national level. In relation to communications logistics, EMS seem to be less well equipped.

7.2.3. Command and Control and support to operational decision-making

The EU Civil Protection Mechanism provides a comprehensive and robust framework of common practices between countries for the organisation and deployment of C2. However, the command and control systems commonly used in MCI or disaster management are based on local procedures, with the result that neither workflows nor communications between the different systems are standardised.

The surveys carried out in the WP5 show that the firefighters assume not only the command of the more specific functions of firefighting or rescue, but that in an almost very majority they also assume the functions of global command of the incident, both from the EOC and in the same scene of the disaster.

Without having extracted from the study specific criteria to justify this fact, in the opinion of the researchers of this Project, this could be justified by the priority that damage control has in this type of response, and perhaps by better specific training of this type of emergency services.

As seems logical and evident, the command in relation to the work of medical care of the victims falls almost unanimously on the EMS. In the same way, the security responsibilities would fall mainly on the police, with some minor intervention of the army and a small space also for firefighters.

When managing incidents or disasters of various types and magnitudes, communication between the different elements involved (e.g. agencies, ministries, countries) is crucial. The different command and control systems clearly specify which agency is in overall command of an incident, or which agency is responsible for medical, security or rescue actions. However, there is room for improvement in C2 communication, both at technical and organisational, inter-agency, cross-sectoral and cross-border levels.

Standards and procedures between emergency agencies are not fully unified and interconnected, and the latest technology in emergency management is not always available.

The VALKYRIES challenge, having analyzed and prioritized the needs, is to

1. Allow different systems, operating different C2s by different agents to exchange tactical information (minimum data set, tactical information of the event)
2. To secure such data interchange against threats or possible future disputes
3. To create a sharable COP to all C2 attached either within a country or between National Coordinators of events in major cross-border events
4. To introduce common practices on activation/deactivation of COP sharing
5. To introduce common practices for post event evaluation or data inquiries.

Two critical factors for the success of this objective are the sharing of COP and the GDBR protection of all exchanged data.

7.2.4. Common Operational Picture

To respond effectively in MCI or disasters, the emergency services involved must have the relevant information at the right time and through appropriate equipment and information systems to assist them in their decisions and to take advantage of technological capabilities and networking.

To this end, much work still needs to be done on critical aspects such as the culture of information exchange, the inclusion of technological advances, interoperability of systems, confidentiality and information security.

The Common Operational Picture, COP, is one of the solutions proposed in emergency management to improve the quality of information exchange and facilitate the development of situational awareness and the coordination of the actions of the different emergency services. It basically consists of a geographical representation of key elements describing the characteristics of the disaster and the response operation.

The challenge is to determine the minimum data sets that need to be communicated during disasters. Deciding what information is relevant and what is not is an extremely difficult but critical task for the developers of information exchange systems between institutions.

Analysis of the current situation in our environment reveals that the Emergency Services generally have operational communications networks, but a minority ensure their availability at the scene and do not allow inter-agency communications.

Firefighters show better capabilities than the rest in relation to the communication of information such as voice, data, images, maps, vehicles and GPS geopositioning.

The group of Emergency Services with potential responsibility for responding to cross-national MCI or disasters shows only a slightly better percentage in data transmission capabilities.

In terms of software tools that support the operational intervention of FRs and of C2 decision support software, slightly more than half of the services surveyed have such software, but a minority still have such software at the scene of the incident.

In the EU we are still far from having a homogeneous COP between services that facilitates a common understanding of the situation in the cross-national response to MCI or disasters.

Based on the state of the art and the landscape obtained from the questionnaires, the following are aspects expected from a COP in MCI and disaster management, even more so when the response involves multiple agencies and even several countries:

- Crisis zone map
- Hazard Mapping
- Climate
- Vulnerable critical points mapping
- Healthcare infrastructures mapping
- Vehicles tracking
- Evacuation routes
- Responders tracking
- Hospital capacities
- Available assets and its location
- And to a lesser degree:
 - Access routes
 - Traffic conditions
 - Vehicles contact points
 - Victims data

- Facilities deployment
- Zonation

And the characteristics that it should have would basically be the following:

- Configurable
- Real-time Information
- Forecast based on dynamic inputs
- And to a lesser degree:
 - Forecast based on Artificial Intelligence
 - Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence
 - Healthcare Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence

A special type of COP is introduced by Valkyries (“SIGRUN Operational Centre”) with the major role to interconnect different COP of federated systems and to create a secured sharable COP between C2s (within a country and/or in cross-border mode)

7.2.5. Alert and warning

EU early warning and information systems help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to monitor hazards and events around the world, thereby increasing the safety and security of citizens.

EU monitoring tools also complement the information available to Member States and help their emergency services to channel the response whenever necessary.

There is no homogeneity across EU Member States in terms of risk communication, awareness raising and early warning systems. Communication ranges from more traditional systems, such as sirens, to the use of more modern technologies and the exploitation of social networks.

Based on the results obtained in our questionnaires, there is also no homogeneity in relation to the agencies responsible for warning and alerting the population in case of disasters, although in most cases it involves Civil Protection and firefighting services. The high availability of standardized warning and notification procedures is striking, but at the same time they are still supported by technological means that are far from those offered by the current state of technology.

Another very relevant aspect is the public's response to warnings and alerts, so that certain aspects that influence the effectiveness of warnings must be taken into account, such as that warnings should only be sent to people at risk, that prior education about the danger and the development of action plans is essential, using different warning devices, etc., taking into account that people's response changes as technologies change. Thus, nowadays, the main means of emergency communication are social networks, which represents both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the large presence of hoaxes and fake news, which poses a significant threat to their usefulness.

Alert and warning systems exist within a broader technical and communication ecosystem, and systems designed and maintained by governments must fit into this broader ecosystem.

A more cohesive and comprehensive warning and alert system is needed that integrates public and private communication mechanisms and information sources, and continues to provide the information needed to keep people healthy and safe, so that new warning and alert technologies can be rapidly adopted.

The country's warning capabilities, such as mobile-based warning systems like WEA and IPAWS, will need to evolve and progress as the capabilities of smartphones and other mobile broadband devices improve and new technologies become available. This evolution will need to be based on both technical research and social and behavioural science research.

In short, education, testing and measurement are necessary for the success of early warning systems.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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9. Annex B - Glossary

Acronym	Description
AACE	Association of Ambulance Chief Executives
ACP	Advanced Command Post
ACPDR	Administration of the Rep. of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief
AMS	Automated manifest system card
C2	Command and control
C&C	Command and control
CGDIS	Luxembourg Fire and Rescue Corps
CIMIC	Civil Military Cooperation
CNOS	National Command Structure
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CNSSU	National Committee for Special Emergency Situations
COP	Common Operational Picture
DMSE	Disaster Management and Support Environment
DGFSCP	Fire Safety and Civil Protection Directorate General
DGPCE	Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies
DSB	Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection
EADRCC	Euro-Atlantic Disaster Response Coordination Centre
EDXL	Emergency Data Exchange Language
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
EMIMS	Emergency Management Information Management System
EMT	Emergency Medical Teams
EOC	Emergency Operations Centre
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
ERU	Emergency Response Unit
EU	European Union
EUCPM	European Union Civil Protection Mechanism
FAC	Federal Alarm Centre
FACT	IFRC Field Assessment and Coordination Team
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GDACS	Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System
GSCP	General Secretariat of Civil Protection
HC	Humanitarian Coordinator
HCPN	High Commission for National Protection
HCT	Humanitarian Country Team
IC	Incident Commander
ICS	Incident Command System
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IFRC	International Federation of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
IMS	Incident Management System
IMT	Incident Management Team

Acronym	Description
IRS	Integrated Rescue System
IOS	International Operational Staff
IPAWS	Integrated Public Alert and Warning System
JESIP	Joint Emergency Services Interoperability Programme
LEMA	Local Emergency Management Authority
LMD	Logistics, maintenance and deployment
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
MDS	Minimum data set
MOI	Ministry of Interior
MSB	Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency
MUSAS	Mobile Urban Situation Awareness System
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NCPS	National Civil Protection System
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
NIMS	National Incident Management System
NOC	National Operations Centre
NOST	National Operation Staff
NSPN	Norwegian Public Safety Network
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OSOCC	On-Site Operations Coordination Centre
OODA	Observe-Orient-Decide-Act loop
resCEU	European Union Reserve of Resources
PPE	Personal protection equipment
PNEPC	National Civil Protection Emergency Plan
RC	Resident Coordinator
SA	Situational Awareness
SITCEN	NATO Situation Centre
UN	United Nations
UNDAC	United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination System
UCPM	Union Civil Protection Mechanism
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USAR	Urban Search And Rescue
WFP	World Food Programme
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Table 11 - Glossary

10. Annex C - Questionnaire

During several working meetings between M4 and M7 of the Project, the participants of the WP5 tasks agreed on a questionnaire with questions related to the preparedness and response of the emergency services to MCI (Mass Casualty Incidents) and disasters.

The definition of the questions and possible answers was carried out under the following fundamental premises:

- To cover all aspects to be studied in the different tasks of WP5
- Avoid repetition of questions or answers (between the different WP5 tasks and between the different WPs of the project)
- To avoid the final questionnaire reaching a size that would discourage the final recipients of the consultation from completing it

The questions were grouped into 5 thematic categories to facilitate the understanding and response of the questionnaire by the consulted expert:

1. Crisis Response Planning
2. Command & Control (C2) and Common Operational Picture (COP)
3. First Responders Operations
4. Communications
5. On Scene Logistics & Deployment

At the end of the response collection time, the data collected in the questionnaires were reorganised according to the different tasks set out in Wp5 for analysis by the researchers.

To support the dissemination of the WP5 questionnaire, collection and processing of the information obtained, it was decided to develop specific software with the following basic characteristics:

- Questionnaire support software to enable targeted and efficient delivery to the final recipients of the consultation.
- Accessible through all the most common browsers.
- User-friendly
- It should provide the participants in the consultation with more information about the project and its results, if they are interested.
- It should also allow the expert consulted to point out existing needs and gaps, based on his or his experience and criteria, in relation to the different consultation categories.
- Must ensure proper and efficient management of the data obtained.

A web application was developed, following these premises, by TASSICA, WP5 leader.

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Figure 78 - WP5 web application: home screen

Figure 79 - WP5 web application: example of a category screen

The questionnaire used in the Wp5 work is included below, listing the fields surveyed and the type/options of answers offered.

Field	Type/Options
Expert Data	
MCI Role	Text
Country	Text
Crisis Response Planning	
In what multiple casualty incidents or disaster situations could the service in which you work be involved?	Local, Regional, Cross-Regional, National, Cross-National
Territorial Crisis Response Plan Types, if available	Local, Regional, Cross-Regional, National, Cross-National
Territorial Crisis Response Plan Standardized at national level?	Boolean
Hazard-Specific Crisis Response Plan, if available	Biological, Chemical, Climatological, Geological, Human, Hydrological, Nuclear, Technological, Terrorism, Radiological, Other
Other Hazard-Specific Crisis Response Plan	Text
Hazard-Specific Crisis Response Plan Standardized at national level?	Boolean
Crisis Emergency Operations Centre Available?	Boolean
Involved Emergency Agencies	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Involved Emergency Agencies	Text
Plan Activation Responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Activation Responsibility Agencies	Text
Incident Categorization Criteria, if included in Crisis Response Plan	By number of victims, By type of hazard, By severity, By extent
Incident Categorization Criteria standardized at national level?	Boolean
Items included in Crisis Response Plan	Hazard Mapping / List, Resources Mapping / List, Plan Activation Criteria, Plan Activation Procedure, Alert and Warning Planning, Evaluation Planning, Evacuation Planning, Sheltering Planning, Operational Planning, Plan Demobilization Criteria, Plan Training Planning, Plan Review Planning
Specific needs	Text
Command & Control and COP in crisis response	
General Incident Command Responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other General Incident Command Responsibility (Agency)	Text

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Field	Type/Options
Medical Command Responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Medical Command Responsibility (Agency)	Text
On Scene Global Command (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On Scene Global Command (Agency)	Text
On Scene Rescuers Command (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On Scene Rescuers Command (Agency)	Text
On Scene Security Command (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On Scene Security Command (Agency)	Text
On Scene General Medical Command (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On Scene General Medical Command (Agency)	Text
Alert and Warning Responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Alert and Warning Responsibility (Agency)	Text
Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure Available?	Boolean
Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure standardized at national level?	Boolean
Crisis Alert and Warning Means	Text
What information should be available to have a common operational picture that enables a good crisis situational awareness and facilitate C&C decision-making?	Crisis zone map, Hazard Mapping, Climate, Vulnerable critical points mapping, Healthcare infrastructures mapping, Vehicles tracking, Access routes, Evacuation routes, Traffic conditions, Vehicles contact points, Zonation, Facilities deployment, Responders tracking, Victims data, Hospital capacities, Other
Other Information that should be available	Text
What characteristics should have this common operational picture?	Configurable, Real-time Information, Forecast based on dynamic inputs, Forecast based on Artificial Intelligence, C&C Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare Recommendations based on Artificial Intelligence
Specific needs	Text
Crisis First Responders Operations	
Service Crisis Operational Procedure Available?	Boolean

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Field	Type/Options
Service Crisis Operational Procedure Standardized at national level?	Boolean
Hazard-Specific Operational Procedure, if available	Biological, Chemical, Climatological, Geological, Human, Hydrological, Nuclear, Technological, Terrorism, Radiological, Other
Other Hazard-Specific Operational Procedure	Text
Hazard-Specific Operational Procedure Standardized at national level?	Boolean
Unified cross-agency crisis operational procedure, if available	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Unified cross-agency crisis operational procedure, if available	Text
On scene hazard control responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene hazard control responsibility (Agency)	Text
Zonation responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Zonation responsibility (Agency)	Text
On scene access control responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene access control responsibility (Agency)	Text
On scene ambulances registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene ambulances registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	Text
On scene victims registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene victims registration and tracking responsibility (Agency)	Text
On scene treatment triage responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene treatment triage responsibility (Agency)	Text
Treatment triage procedure unified?	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Treatment triage procedure unified?	Text
On scene victims stretcher carrying responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene victims stretcher carrying responsibility (Agency)	Text

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Field	Type/Options
On scene victims stabilization responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene victims stabilization responsibility (Agency)	Text
On scene evacuation triage responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene evacuation triage responsibility (Agency)	Text
Evacuation triage procedure unified?	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Evacuation triage procedure unified?	Text
On scene evacuation control responsibility (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other On scene evacuation control responsibility (Agency)	Text
Responsibility to determine the destination hospital of the patient (Agency)	Rescuers, Firefighters, EMS, Police, Army, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Others
Other Responsibility to determine the destination hospital of the patient (Agency)	Text
Specific needs	Text
Communications	
Service First Responders Communications Description	Text
Service First Responders Communications Features	Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level
Service First Responders Communications Data capability	Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others
Other Data capabilities included	Text
Service First Responders Support Software Description	Text
Service First Responders Support Software Features	Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level
Service First Responders Support Software Data capability	Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others
Other Data capabilities included	Text
C&C Support Software Description	Text
C&C Support Software Features	Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level
C&C Support Software Data capability	Voice, Data, Picture, Video, Maps, GPS, Hazards, Victims, Responders, Vehicles, Medical supplies, Resources, Facilities, Hospitals, Others
Other Data capabilities included	Text

Field	Type/Options
Service First Responders Support Hardware Description	Text
Service First Responders Support Hardware Features	Available, Available On Scene, Dedicated, Cross-agency Capability, Standardized at National Level
Service First Responders Support Hardware Devices	Mobile phone, Tablet, Laptop, Walkie-Talkie, Transmitter, Satellite, Others
Other Devices included	Text
Specific needs	Text
Service On Scene Logistics & Deployment	
Standardized Service Ambulances at national level?	Equipment, Crew, Crew training
Indicate the logistical support items available in your service for ICM or disaster response	Communications vehicle, Logistic vehicle, Signalling elements, Triage tag, Personal protection equipment (PPE), Advanced medical post facility, Victims wearables (location, monitoring, etc.), First responders wearables (identification, location, monitoring, etc.)
What elements of the previous logistical support items are standardised at the national level?	Communications vehicle, Logistic vehicle, Signalling elements, Triage tag, Personal protection equipment (PPE), Advanced medical post facility, Victims wearables (location, monitoring, etc.), First responders wearables (identification, location, monitoring, etc.)
Select the specific mobilisation procedures that exist in your service in relation to MCI and disasters	Activation procedure of supplies for MCI, Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders, Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours
What elements of the previous specific mobilisation procedures are standardised at the national level?	Activation procedure of supplies for MCI, Mobilisation plan for reinforcement service first responders, Plan to ensure rescue activity within 72 hours
Indicate the items for which stock procedures exist in your Service, in relation to MCI or disasters, if available	List of medical supplies, Sanitary equipment, Medications, Emergency clothing, Food and water, Gasoline, Electric energy and power supplies, Bathrooms and showers, Communication equipment to be used on the site of MCI
Specific needs	Text

Table 12 - WP5 questionnaire